

PREFACE

It gives us immense pleasure to present the proceedings of the RECENT INNOVATION IN ENGINEERING AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH (NCRIESR'26) organized by John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology is a joint effort by the Artificial Intelligent & Machine Learning Engineering, Biomedical Engineering & Robotic, Civil Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Communication Engineering and Computer Science & Engineering departments of the institute. It was held on March 5, 2026. This national conference served as a platform for scholars, researchers, and industry professionals to engage in meaningful discussions and share their latest findings in their respective fields.

The conference attracted a diverse range of contributions, reflecting the growing interest and innovation in the areas of Geotechnical Structural Environmental, Port Management Systems, Small Scale Farming Industries, Control System and Robotics, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Embedded Systems for Security, Renewable Energy Applications, Pattern Recognition, Data Mining, Robotics, Cyber Security, Neural Network insert relevant fields. After a thorough peer-review process, selected papers were chosen for publication in these proceedings, ensuring a high standard of academic quality and relevance.

We sincerely thank all the authors, reviewers, and participants for their valuable efforts and contributions. We are also deeply grateful to the organizing committee, session chairs, volunteers, and all those who supported the successful conduct of this conference.

We hope that this compilation of research will be a useful resource for future academic and professional reference.

Editors

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**Proceedings of National Conference on Recent Innovation in Engineering
and Scientific Research (NCRIESR'26)**

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Impact of NEP 2020 on Mathematics Curriculum in Engineering Education

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Abstract

The National Education Policy 2020 introduces significant reforms aimed at transforming the Indian education system to meet global standards and industry demands. This paper examines the impact of NEP 2020 on the mathematics curriculum in engineering education. Traditionally, engineering mathematics has been largely theoretical, with limited emphasis on practical application and interdisciplinary integration. NEP 2020 promotes a shift toward experiential learning, outcome-based education, and the incorporation of real-world problem-solving into the curriculum.

The policy encourages the integration of computational tools, data-driven approaches, and emerging technologies, enabling students to apply mathematical concepts in fields such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and engineering design. It also supports flexible curricula, multidisciplinary learning, and continuous assessment methods, which can enhance student engagement and conceptual understanding.

This study examines changes in the curriculum, teaching methods, and challenges in implementation. It also highlights key challenges in implementation, including the need for faculty training, curriculum redesign, digital infrastructure, and institutional readiness. The findings suggest that while NEP 2020 has the potential to significantly improve students' analytical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and employability, its effectiveness depends on coordinated efforts among policymakers, educators, and institutions. Successful implementation will require sustained investment, capacity building, and a gradual transition from traditional teaching practices to innovative, learner-centered approaches.

Keywords— NEP 2020, Engineering Education, Mathematics Curriculum, Outcome-Based Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

The National Education Policy 2020 is a major reform introduced to improve the quality and relevance of education in India. It focuses on creating a more flexible, multidisciplinary, and skill-oriented education system, especially in higher education and technical fields like engineering. The policy aims to prepare students not only with academic knowledge but also with practical skills required for modern industries.

Mathematics plays a very important role in engineering education. It forms the foundation for many core subjects such as physics, computer science, electronics, and data analytics. A strong understanding of mathematical concepts helps students develop logical thinking, analytical ability, and problem-solving skills, which are essential for engineers.

However, in many engineering colleges, mathematics has traditionally been taught using lecture-based methods. These methods often focus on rote learning, memorization of formulas, and solving standard problems, with less emphasis on real-world applications. As a result, students may find it difficult to apply mathematical concepts in practical engineering situations.

The National Education Policy 2020 aims to overcome these challenges by encouraging application-based and experiential learning. It promotes the use of modern computational tools, programming, and digital technologies to make learning more interactive and meaningful. The policy also supports interdisciplinary approaches, where mathematics is connected with real-life engineering problems and emerging fields like artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data science.

In addition, NEP 2020 introduces continuous and comprehensive assessment methods, which evaluate students based on their overall performance rather than only final examinations. This helps in

improving understanding, creativity, and critical thinking among students.

Furthermore, the policy encourages curriculum redesign, flexibility in subject choices, and the development of industry-relevant skills. These changes aim to make engineering graduates more competent, innovative, and job-ready.

This paper explores how the reforms introduced by NEP 2020 influence the mathematics curriculum in engineering colleges, focusing on changes in teaching methods, course structure, and learning outcomes.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of this study are:

1. To analyse the reforms introduced by NEP 2020 related to engineering education.
2. To evaluate how the mathematics curriculum has been modified in response to NEP 2020.
3. To identify key challenges and opportunities in transforming mathematics education under NEP 2020.
4. Assess the adoption of outcome-based education in mathematics teaching.

III LITERATURE REVIEW

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) outlines a major shift in Indian education toward flexibility, multidisciplinary learning, and skill enhancement, emphasizing outcome-based approaches and practical relevance [7]. M. Bhardwaj, A. Ranjan, and J. Sharma [1] “Curriculum and NEP 2020: Perspectives and Inter Connections” provides an in-depth analysis of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 and its impact on curriculum reform in India, with a particular focus on higher education. The authors critically examine how NEP 2020 emphasizes multidisciplinary learning, skill development, and flexibility in course structures. Sharma and Kaur [2] note that although NEP 2020 provides a framework for curriculum reform, successful implementation in engineering institutions requires effective planning, institutional support, and faculty development. Rao and Prasad [3] discussed the adoption of outcome-based education (OBE) as a strategy to enhance student competencies, while also noting challenges such as insufficient faculty training and infrastructure limitations. Gupta and Verma [4] further demonstrate how technology-supported learning enhances analytical capabilities in engineering mathematics. Agarwal and Singh [5] highlight the importance of curriculum reform in engineering

education, particularly in mathematics, to improve real-world applicability and align with industry requirements. Patil and Joshi [6] highlight the benefits of multidisciplinary learning under NEP 2020, which allows mathematics to connect with emerging fields such as data science and artificial intelligence. Sharma [8] emphasizes the integration of computational tools like MATLAB and Python into the mathematics curriculum to improve conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills. Collectively, these studies support the premise that NEP 2020 can transform mathematics education in engineering colleges, provided implementation challenges are adequately addressed.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design based on secondary data. Sources include:

- NEP 2020 policy document
- Research articles and educational reports

Data has been analysed qualitatively to identify trends and themes related to curriculum transformation and pedagogical reform.

V. DISCUSSION

a. Curriculum Transformation

The National Education Policy 2020 encourages updating the engineering mathematics syllabus to make it more practical and useful. Earlier, the focus was mainly on theory and solving textbook problems. Now, more importance is given to applied learning. Topics such as numerical methods, data analysis, and computational modelling are being added so that students can understand how mathematics is used in real engineering situations. Project-based learning and case studies are also encouraged to improve understanding.

b. Outcome-Based Education (OBE)

Outcome-Based Education focuses on what students are able to do after completing a course. Under NEP 2020, engineering mathematics is designed with clear learning outcomes. Students are expected to apply mathematical concepts to solve real-world problems, use computational tools, and think critically. This approach helps in improving problem-solving skills and makes learning more meaningful compared to traditional exam-focused methods.

c. Integration of Technology

NEP 2020 promotes the use of technology in teaching and learning mathematics. Tools like MATLAB, Python, and simulation software help students visualize concepts and solve complex problems easily. These tools make learning more interactive and interesting. Students can perform experiments, analyse data, and understand concepts better through practical applications rather than only theoretical study.

d. Multidisciplinary Approach

The policy encourages connecting mathematics with other subjects such as computer science, physics, and engineering disciplines. It also links mathematics with emerging areas like artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data science. This multidisciplinary approach helps students see the real importance of mathematics and prepares them to work in different fields where combined knowledge is required.

Figure 1: Conceptual Roadmap for Phased Implementation of NEP 2020 in Technical Institutions (2025–2030).

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Traditional vs. NEP 2020 Aligned Mathematics Pedagogy.

Pedagogical Feature	Traditional Curriculum (Pre-2020)	NEP 2020 Mathematics Curriculum
Primary Learning Goal	Theory-focused; concept learning and formula derivation	Skill-focused; application, problem-solving, and logical thinking
Teaching Methodology	Lecture-based (“chalk and talk”) and routine problem solving	Experiential learning; project-based and interactive classes
Key Math Modules	Pure Calculus, Linear formulaic derivation Algebra (Theory), Differential Equations (Analytical).	Applied Numerical Methods, Data Analytics (Statistics), Optimization Techniques
Integration of Technology	Limited use of calculators; software used only in special labs	Regular use of tools like Python and MATLAB in core curriculum
Assessment Model	End-semester exams with high weightage.	Continuous assessment including projects, viva, and practical exams.

VI. CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTATION

- **Teacher Training:** Many instructors need more training in outcome-based teaching and modern software tools.
- **Resources:** Colleges may not have enough computers, software, or lab facilities.
- **Resistance to Change:** Some institutions prefer traditional teaching methods and may hesitate to adopt new ones.
- **Assessment Changes:** Shifting from exams to continuous, outcome-based evaluation is challenging and needs careful planning.

VII. FINDINGS

- NEP 2020 supports the development of applied and skill-oriented mathematics learning in engineering education.
- Addressing challenges such as faculty training, infrastructure, and assessment methods is essential for the successful implementation of NEP 2020 reforms.
- The use of technology and computational tools improves student engagement and enhances analytical and problem-solving skills.
- Outcome-Based Education (OBE) clearly defines learning objectives and expected student competencies.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The National Education Policy 2020 has the potential to bring major improvements in the mathematics curriculum of engineering education. It focuses on making learning more practical, skill-based, and student-centered. By promoting outcome-based education, application-oriented teaching, and the use of modern technology, NEP 2020 helps students understand how mathematics is used in real-life engineering problems.

The policy also encourages the use of computational tools, interdisciplinary learning, and continuous assessment methods, which improve students' understanding and interest in the subject. As a result, students can develop better analytical thinking, problem-solving ability, and creativity.

However, the successful implementation of these changes depends on several factors. Proper training for teachers, availability of digital tools and infrastructure, and support from institutions are very important. Without these, it may be difficult to achieve the full benefits of the policy.

Overall, a well-planned and effectively implemented curriculum under NEP 2020 can help produce engineering graduates who are more skilled, confident, and ready to meet industry demands and real-world challenges.

References

- [1] M. Bhardwaj, A. Ranjan, and J. Sharma, "Curriculum and NEP 2020: Perspectives and Inter-Connections," *Indian Journal of Public Administration*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 237–255, Jun. 2024.
- [2] N. Sharma and R. Kaur, "Implementation Challenges of NEP 2020 in Technical Institutions," *J. Educ. Policy Anal.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 15–24, 2023.
- [3] K. Rao and M. Prasad, "Outcome-Based Education in Engineering: Trends and Challenges," *J. Eng. Educ. Res.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 45–52, 2022.
- [4] S. Gupta and L. Verma, "Integration of Technology in Engineering Education," *Int. J. Tech. Educ.*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 56–63, 2022.
- [5] A. Agarwal and T. Singh, "Role of NEP 2020 in Reforming Higher Education in India," *Int. J. Educ. Dev.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 12–20, 2021.
- [6] S. Patil and A. Joshi, "Multidisciplinary Learning and Curriculum Flexibility under NEP 2020," *Global J. Educ. Stud.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 25–33, 2021.
- [7] Government of India, *National Education Policy 2020*, Ministry of Education, 2020.
- [8] P. Sharma, "Engineering Mathematics Curriculum: A Framework for Reform," *Education Rev.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 30–39, 2020.

Graph Neural Networks in Network Neuroscience

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Abstract -- Non-invasive neuroimaging techniques have led to significant insights into brain connectivity. Several advanced methods for mapping the brain's morphological, structural, and functional connections have been developed, resulting in a comprehensive "brain graph" that represents neuronal activities. Given the non-Euclidean nature of this data, graph neural networks (GNNs) offer an effective approach for learning complex graph structures and have rapidly become the leading method in improving performance across various network neuroscience tasks. In this review, we explore current GNN-based approaches, emphasizing their applications in brain graph-related problems such as missing graph reconstruction and disease classification. Finally, we discuss the future potential of GNN models in advancing neurological disorder diagnosis and integrating population-based brain graphs.

Keywords—noninvasive; brain graph; morphology; GNN; neuroscience

I. INTRODUCTION

Network neuroscience has emerged as a powerful framework for understanding the brain by modeling it as a complex network of interconnected regions, commonly referred to as the brain connectome. In this representation, brain regions are treated as nodes and their structural or functional connections as edges, enabling the application of graph theory to study the brain's organization, dynamics, and disruptions associated with neurological and psychiatric disorders. However, traditional graph-based approaches are often limited in their ability to capture nonlinear interactions, high-dimensional patterns, and hierarchical dependencies present in brain connectivity data.

Graph representation of the brain provides a framework for understanding the lifespan of brain wiring across three axes. The first axis is time, which allows us to track changes in brain connectivity from birth through aging, or to observe transitions from healthy to disordered states. By studying the relationship between connectivity at an initial timepoint and at subsequent stages, researchers can develop novel diagnostic tools for detecting neurological disorders at very early stages. The second axis refers to the resolution of the brain graph, which enables the discovery of inter-regional connections that underlie brain organization. A brain can be modeled using either a low-resolution connectome, with fewer nodes (regions of interest) and edges, or a super-resolution connectome, with more detailed mapping of regions and connections. Each level of resolution provides a unique window into the topographic organization of the brain, offering complementary insights into its structure and function. The third axis relates to the domain

in which the brain data is collected, commonly referred to in network neuroscience as the neuroimaging modality (e.g., functional MRI or diffusion MRI). Each modality generates a different type of connectome—functional or structural—and combining them in cross-domain, multimodal representations offers invaluable complementary information for brain mapping in both health and disease.

II. TYPES OF BRAIN GRAPHS

To create a brain graph, neurons and their synapses could be used as the basic building blocks, with neurons as nodes and synapses as edges. However, this approach is computationally expensive, requiring large amounts of data and complex processing. A more scalable method is to group sets of neurons into single nodes using anatomical parcellation schemes applied to imaging modalities such as MRI. The resulting connectome is typically modeled as an undirected graph, meaning that it does not specify the direction of information flow between brain regions. Based on how the connections are defined, brain graphs are generally classified into three types: morphological brain graphs, functional brain graphs, and structural brain graphs.

A. Morphological brain graph

A morphological brain graph is constructed by analyzing structural features of the brain, such as cortical thickness, surface area, or volume, across different regions. In this graph, nodes represent brain regions, and edges are defined based on the similarity or correlation of these morphological measures between regions. This type of graph helps in understanding how structural properties of different brain areas are related and is often used to study brain development, aging, and structural abnormalities in neurological or psychiatric disorders

B. Functional brain graph

5 A functional brain graph is built using brain activity data,

typically from functional MRI (fMRI), EEG, or MEG recordings. In this graph, nodes represent brain regions, and edges are defined by the statistical dependencies or correlations between their activity patterns over time. Functional brain graphs provide insights into how different regions interact dynamically to support cognition, behavior, and sensory processing. They are widely used to study functional integration, network dynamics, and alterations linked to neurological and psychiatric disorders

C. Structural brain graph

A structural brain graph is constructed from anatomical connections between brain regions, typically derived from diffusion MRI or tractography techniques. In this graph, nodes represent brain regions, and edges correspond to white matter pathways that physically link these regions. Structural brain graphs capture the brain’s wiring architecture and provide insights into how information may flow across the network. They are commonly used to study brain development, connectivity disruptions, and structural changes in neurological and psychiatric conditions.

III. GNN BASED METHODS FOR NETWORK NEUROSCIENCE

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have emerged as powerful tools in network neuroscience because they can directly learn from graph-structured brain data. Unlike traditional methods that rely on handcrafted features, GNNs capture both local and global connectivity patterns across brain networks. They are used to model structural, functional, and multimodal connectomes for tasks such as disease classification, prediction of cognitive traits, brain age estimation, and understanding developmental or degenerative processes. By leveraging hierarchical graph representations, GNN-based methods enable more accurate and biologically meaningful insights, making them valuable for both basic neuroscience research and clinical applications.

IV. BRAIN GRAPH PREDICTION

Brain graph prediction involves using computational models to estimate missing or future connections in brain networks. This can include predicting how structural or functional connectivity will evolve over time, or inferring incomplete connections from noisy data. Techniques such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are widely applied, as they can learn complex patterns from existing brain graphs and generalize to unseen data. Brain graph prediction has important applications in early diagnosis of neurological

disorders, forecasting disease progression, and modeling brain development across the lifespan.

i. Cross-Domain Graph Prediction

Cross-domain graph prediction focuses on inferring or translating brain connectivity patterns across different data modalities or domains. For example, it can involve predicting a structural brain graph from functional data, or combining information from multiple neuroimaging modalities such as fMRI, EEG, and diffusion MRI. This approach leverages complementary features from each domain to build more accurate and robust models of brain connectivity. Cross-domain prediction is particularly useful for filling gaps when one type of data is missing, improving diagnostic accuracy, and enhancing multimodal brain mapping in both healthy and clinical populations.

ii. Cross-Resolution Graph Prediction

Cross-resolution graph prediction aims to infer brain connectivity patterns across different levels of resolution in the connectome. For instance, it can involve predicting a high-resolution graph (with many fine-grained regions of interest) from a low-resolution graph, or vice versa. This is important because different parcellation schemes provide different views of brain organization, and high-resolution data may not always be available due to acquisition or computational limitations. By enabling translation between scales, cross-resolution prediction enhances the integration of multi-scale brain networks and supports more comprehensive analyses of brain structure and function.

iii. Cross-Time Graph Prediction

Cross-time graph prediction focuses on modeling and forecasting how brain connectivity changes over time. Given a brain graph at one or more timepoints, the goal is to predict its future state or reconstruct its past configuration. This approach is particularly useful for studying brain development, aging, and the progression of neurological or psychiatric disorders. By capturing temporal dynamics in brain networks, cross-time prediction enables early detection of abnormal changes, supports longitudinal studies, and provides valuable insights into the lifespan trajectory of brain connectivity.

V. BRAIN GRAPH CLASSIFICATION

Perhaps the first and most fundamental question that one can ask about a brain graph is whether it is useful for early diagnosing a disease. A straightforward way is to train a classifier to distinguish between healthy and unhealthy subjects and to build a model that identifies the most discriminative connectivities in the brain that fingerprints a typical disease. For this reason, we divide the brain graph classification flavor into two categories: brain state classification and biomarker identification.

A. Brain State Classification

Brain state classification refers to the process of identifying and categorizing different mental or cognitive states of the brain based on neuroimaging or electrophysiological data.

B. Biomarker Identification

A complementary but distinct line of work capitalizes on the emerging field of interpretability of GNN intending to develop models that identify the most discriminative biomarkers in addition to predicting the label of brain graphs. Biomarker identification is the process of discovering measurable indicators-biological molecules, genes, proteins, or imaging features that can reliably signal normal or pathological processes, or responses to treatment.

VI. CONCLUSION

Graph Neural Networks have emerged as a powerful and versatile tool in network neuroscience, enabling more accurate modelling and analysis of complex brain connectivity patterns. By leveraging the inherent graph structure of neural data, GNNs effectively capture both local and global interactions within brain networks, surpassing traditional methods in tasks such as brain state classification, disease diagnosis, and biomarker discovery. Despite challenges related to interpretability and data heterogeneity, ongoing advancements in GNN architectures and training strategies hold great promise for deepening our understanding of brain function and dysfunction. Integrating GNNs with multimodal neuroimaging data is poised to accelerate the development of personalized diagnostics and targeted therapeutic interventions, marking a significant step forward in computational neuroscience and clinical applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. S. Bassett and O. Sporns, "Network neuroscience," *Nature Neurosci.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 353–364, 2017.
- [2] D. S. Bassett, E. Bullmore, B. A. Verchinski, V. S. Mattay, D. R. Weinberger, and A. Meyer-Lindenberg, "Hierarchical organization of human cortical networks in health and schizophrenia," *J. Neurosci.*, vol. 28, no. 37, pp. 9239–9248, 2008.
- [3] D. M. Lydon-Staley and D. S. Bassett, "Network neuroscience: A framework for developing biomarkers in psychiatry," *Biomarkers in Psychiatry*, Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2018, pp. 79–109.
- [4] V. Fleischer et al., "Graph theoretical framework of brain networks in multiple sclerosis: A review of concepts," *Neuroscience*, vol. 403, pp. 35–53, 2019.
- [5] A. Fornito, A. Zalesky, and E. Bullmore, *Fundamentals of Brain Network Analysis*. New York, NY, USA: Academic Press, 2016.
- [6] M. P. van den Heuvel and O. Sporns, "A cross-disorder connectome landscape of brain dysconnectivity," *Nature Rev. Neurosci.*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 435–446, 2019.
- [7] I. Mahjoub, M. A. Mahjoub, and I. Rekik, "Brain multiplexes reveal morphological connective biomarkers fingerprinting late brain dementia states," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2018, Art. no. 4103.
- [8] B. G. Booth and G. Hamarneh, "Diffusion MRI for brain connectivity mapping and analysis," *MRI: Physics, Image Reconstruction, and Analysis*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2015, pp. 137–171.
- [9] C. J. Stam, "Functional connectivity patterns of human magnetoencephalographic recordings: A 'small-world' network?," *Neurosci. Lett.*, vol. 355, no. 1/2, pp. 25–28, 2004.
- [10] P. Hagmann et al., "Mapping the structural core of human cerebral cortex," *PLoS Biol.*, vol. 6, no. 7, 2008, Art. no. e159.
- [11] N. K. Logothetis, "What we can do and what we cannot do with fMRI," *Nature*, vol. 453, no. 7197, pp. 869–878, 2008.
- [12] S. Jbabdi, S. N. Sotiropoulos, S. N. Haber, D. C. Van Essen, and T. E. Behrens, "Measuring macroscopic brain connections in vivo," *Nature Neurosci.*, vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 1546–1555, 2015.
- [13] R. F. Betzel and D. S. Bassett, "Multi-scale brain networks," *Neuroimage*, vol. 160, pp. 73–83, 2017.
- [14] A. Fornito, A. Zalesky, and M. Breakspear, "The connectomics of brain disorders," *Nature Rev. Neurosci.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 159–172,
- [15] I. Mhiri, A. B. Khalifa, M. A. Mahjoub, and I. Rekik, "Brain graph super-resolution for boosting neurological disorder diagnosis using unsupervised multi-topology connective brain template learning," *Med. Image Anal.*, vol. 65, 2020, Art. no. 101768.
- [16] M. Soussia and I. Rekik, "7 years of developing seed techniques for Alzheimer's disease diagnosis using brain image and connectivity data largely bypassed prediction for prognosis," in *Proc. Int. Workshop Predictive Intell. Medi.*, 2019, pp. 81–93.
- [17] M. Soussia and I. Rekik, "Unsupervised manifold learning using high-order morphological brain networks derived from T1-W MRI for autism diagnosis," *Front. Neuroinform.*, vol. 12, 2018, Art. no. 70.
- [18] M. F. Glasser et al., "The human connectome project's neuroimaging approach," *Nature Neurosci.*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 1175–1187, 2016.

DFT-Based Comparative Study of Molecular Structure, Hirshfeld Surface, and NLO Properties of 3-Chloro-4-fluoroaniline and 2-Iodoaniline with Para-Substituted Anilines

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Abstract - 3-Chloro-4-fluoroaniline and 2-iodoaniline are novel organic nonlinear optical materials. Density functional theory was used to investigate their structural geometry, charge transfer interactions, electron density, stabilization energy, and non linear optical properties through natural bond orbital analysis, frontier molecular orbital analysis, Hirshfeld surface, and hyperpolarizability analyses.

I. INTRODUCTION

The study of 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline (3C4FA) and 2-iodoaniline (2IA) is significant because substitution by electronegative atoms (F, Cl, I) alters the properties of aniline depending on substituent position, donor/acceptor nature, and non-covalent interactions such as π - π stacking, C-H $\cdots\pi$, hydrogen, and halogen bonding [1,2]. Conjugated π -electron systems exhibit high first hyperpolarizability, making them promising candidates for nonlinear optical (NLO) applications [3,4]. Crystal structure analyses show that 3C4FA (orthorhombic, Pbc_a) and 2IA (trigonal, P3₂) are not isostructural, and comparisons with related haloanilines reveal distinct packing and intermolecular interactions, particularly for iodine due to its larger size [5,6]. Previous DFT studies on p-bromoaniline and p-iodoaniline show stronger intermolecular interactions, greater planarity, and enhanced NLO response in p-IA [7-10].

In this work, DFT calculations are employed to investigate structural parameters, NBO analysis, HOMO-LUMO characteristics, and NLO properties of the title compounds. UV-

Vis analysis is also performed to examine solvent effects, and the results are compared with experimental data and related systems to understand molecular interactions, stabilization energies, and structure-property relationships.

II. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

Crystal Growth: The single crystals of 3-Chloro 4-fluoroaniline and 2-Iodoaniline were grown by slow evaporation method and recrystallized from benzene according to the published procedure [5,6]. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations were performed to obtain optimized geometries and interactions[11,12]. NBO analysis was carried out using NBO 5.0 using the Gaussian 09 program at the B3LYP/SDD level output [13], and Hirshfeld surface analysis was performed with Crystal Explorer 3.1 based on CIF data [14,15] to examine intermolecular interactions. Hyperpolarizability was calculated using DFT, while UV-Vis spectra and HOMO-LUMO energies were obtained through time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT).

Spectroscopic Measurements: The UV-Vis absorption spectrum is recorded using a JASCO UV-Vis spectrophotometer for the sample in chloroform solution in the range of 190-1100 nm [16,17].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Molecular Structure Analysis

The optimized dimer structures of 2-Iodoaniline and 3-Chloro 4-fluoroaniline molecules obtained using Gauss View software are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively.

Atoms numbered 1 to 14 are in unit 1 and 15 to 28 are in unit 2 of the dimers.

Figure 1. Atom Labelling scheme for Optimized structure of 2-iodo aniline dimer molecule.

Figure 2. Atom Labelling scheme for Optimized structure of 3-Chloro 5-Fluoro aniline dimer molecule.

A comparison with the experimental data of aniline [18,19] emphasizes the fact that the dimer of 3C4FA has a good planar structure than the 2IA (Table 1).

Table 1: Dihedral angle showing the planarity of the dimer structures for 2-IA and 3C4FA molecule.

Dimer structure	Dihedral angle	B3LYP/SDD	wb97xd/lanl2dz
2IA	C1-C2-N7-H8	166.35°	169.29°
	C1-C2-N7-H9	18.09°	14.77°
3C4FA	C1-C2-N7-H8	0.08°	0°
	C1-C2-N7-H9	-179.93°	180°

Structural analysis using the basis set B3LYP/SDD reveals that 3C4FA is more planar than 2IA at the NH₂ substitution in the phenyl ring as the dihedral angles (0.08°, 179.93°) corresponding to C₁-C₂-N₇-H₈ and C₁-C₂-N₇-H₉ bonds in 3C4FA are close to that for planar molecule (0°, 180°) compared to 2IA (18.09°, 166.35°). The planarity in the dimer structures of aniline derivatives¹ obtained using wb97xd/lanl2dz basis set is in the order *p*-IA (10.46°, 173.73°) > 2IA (14.77°, 169.29°) > *p*-BA (16.36°, 166.50°). It shows that the substitution of halogen atom with lesser electronegativity provides higher planarity. However, the amino group in 3C4FA (0°, 180°) shows more planarity due to the higher hydrogen bonded intermolecular interactions of the fluorine substituent than other halogen atoms substituted in aniline derivatives. Hence, the effects of the *p*-Cl and *p*-Br substituents on the geometrical parameters of the amino group are just opposite to those caused by the *p*-F substituent [2].

Both the title molecules possess strong hydrogen bonded N-H...X interaction. The N₇-H₈ and N₇-H₉ bond lengths are 1.013 and 1.014 Å in 2IA and 1.008 Å each in 3C4FA. The two different N-H bond lengths may be due to the presence of X...N-H and X...H-N bonds in 2IA in agreement with the structural data.

From the molecular structure analysis, it may be inferred that the two units of monomer molecules of haloaniline are linked by halogen/hydrogen bonded interactions such as N-H...N, C-H...F and C-H...π intermolecular interactions to form the dimer molecules.

B. NBO ANALYSIS

The stabilization energy E(2) of hyper conjugative interactions between each donor (i) and acceptor (j) of 3C4FA and 2IA is calculated on the basis of second order Fock matrix perturbation theory

The higher stabilization energy values 159.89, 59.45, 44.72 and 141.60, 23.99 kJ/mol obtained for the interaction between the lone pair (LP) of N₇ and π*(C₁-C₂) orbital in 3C4FA, LP of F₁₂ and π*(C₃-C₄) orbital in 3C4FA, LP of Cl₁₂ and π*(C₃-C₄) orbital in 3C4FA, LP of N₇ and π*(C₂-C₃) orbital in 2IA and LP of I₁₀ and π*(C₂-C₃) orbital in 2IA respectively confirm the intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) in the molecules. This strong conjugation causes an effective delocalization of electrons within the phenyl rings of both the dimer molecules. The interaction LP (F, Cl) → π* and LP (I) → π* reveal the intramolecular interaction between halogen atom and phenyl ring.

The stabilization energy for the interaction LP (nitrogen) → π* is greater than that for LP (halogen) → π* orbital. Hence it can be inferred that the stabilization energy of n → π* intramolecular interaction in substituted aniline increases in the order, nitrogen (159.89, 141.60 kJ/mol) > Fluorine (59.45 kJ/mol) > Chlorine (44.72 kJ/mol) > iodine (23.99 kJ/mol). This is a confirmation to the effect of electronegativity of the substituents on planarity of the molecule.

High stabilization energies 889.61 kJmol⁻¹ and 889.61 kJmol⁻¹ are obtained for the interactions due to electron transfer from the orbital $\pi^*(C_3-C_4) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_1-C_2)$ and $\pi^*(C_{17}-C_{18}) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_{15}-C_{16})$ in unit 1 and 2 of the 3C4FA aromatic ring. The orbital interactions $\pi^*(C_2-C_3) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_4-C_5)$ and $\pi^*(C_{18}-C_{19}) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_{16}-C_{17})$ lead to greater stabilization energies 640.25 and 793.90 kJmol⁻¹ in unit 1 and 2 of the 2IA aromatic ring. The highest stabilization energy 2307.39 kJ/mol observed for the interaction $\pi^*(C_4-C_5) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_1-C_6)$ orbitals in unit 1 of *p*-IA is less than 2405.73 kJ/mol observed for the interaction $\pi^*(C_3-C_4) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_1-C_2)$ orbitals in unit 1 of *p*-BA [10]. The highest stabilization energy for the $\pi^*(C-C) \rightarrow \pi^*(C-C)$ orbitals interaction shows that greater intramolecular interaction is in the order *p*-BA > *p*-IA > 3C4FA > 2IA [10].

The stabilization energy *E* (2) of $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ intermolecular interaction in 2IA (24.45 kJ/mol) > 3C4FA (6.66 kJ/mol) > *p*-IA (4.31 kJ/mol) > *p*-BA (3.60 kJ/mol). The presence of $\pi^*(C_1-C_6) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_{15}-C_{20})$ and $\sigma(C_{15}-H_{28}) \rightarrow \pi^*(C_1-C_6)$ stacked intermolecular interaction energy (1.59 kJ/mol and 1.38 kJ/mol) enhances the NLO activity of 2IA > 3C4FA.

C. HIRSHFELD SURFACE ANALYSIS

Hirshfeld surface analysis provides details regarding a continuous overlapping atomic charge distribution. It is a powerful technique to understand the proximity of the neighboring atoms and the nature of intermolecular interactions apart from its graphical visualization. The d_e denotes the distance of the surface point nearest to the exterior atom and d_i denotes the distance of any surface point nearest to the interior atom, illustrates the donor and acceptor nature of the hydrogen bonds, which displays red spots on the respective plots. Hydrogen bond interactions are identified from deep red spots on the d_{norm} surface. The curvedness and shape index also support the C-H... π interactions (Figure 3 & 4 for 2IA and 3C4FA).

Figure 3 Hirshfeld 3D surface of 2IA molecules.

Figure 4 Hirshfeld 3D surface of 3C5FA molecule.

The curvedness is a measure of relative curvature (large green region separated by dark blue edges), which specifies large root mean square curvature for blue color and one-unit root mean square curvature for green color. The shape index map represents the shape of the molecular surface by dips (red) and bumps (blue) which [20] indicate the place where two molecular Hirshfeld surfaces touch one another. The characteristic π - π stacked interactions of the phenyl ring represented by shape index are highlighted as red and blue triangles.

The 2D fingerprint plot (Figure 5 for 2IA and 6 for 3C4FA) of the 3D molecular structure gives information regarding the contribution of several bonds towards the total molecule.

Figure 5. 2D fingerprint plot of 2IA molecule

Figure 6 2D fingerprint plot of 3C4FA molecule

The decreasing order of the short contacts are observed as H...H/H...H (39.2%) > C...H/H...C (24.6%) > I...H/H...I (18.0%) > I...I/I...I (10.1%) > N...H/H...N (5.0%) > C...C/C...C (2.9%) > C...N/N...N (0.2%) in

2IA and as C...H/H...C (26.9%) > H...H/H...H (19.2%) > H...Cl/Cl...H (19.0%) > F...H/H...F (13.8%) > N...H/H...N (5.3%) > Cl...C/C...Cl (4.8%) > Cl...F/F...Cl (4.1%) > F...F/F...F (3.0%) > Cl...Cl/Cl...Cl (2.1%) > C...F/F...C (1.6%) > Cl...N/N...Cl (0.1%) in 3C4FA molecules. Hydrogen bond interactions lead to greater contribution of H...H/H...H (39.2%) in 2IA and C...H/H...C (26.9%) in 3C4FA.

D. MOLECULAR POLARIZABILITY ANALYSIS

The static and dynamic values of polarizability α , the average polarizability α_0 , the anisotropy of the polarizability $\Delta\alpha$, the first hyperpolarizability β and dipole moment μ_{total} (D) of the title compound 3C4FA and 2IA using the best suitable level basis set B3LYP/SDD are calculated. The predicted value of the static first hyperpolarizability 289.5×10^{-30} esu for 3C4FA is 4.44 times that of urea (65.14×10^{-30} esu). The value 312.16×10^{-30} esu for 2IA is 4.79 times that of urea. The calculated static and dynamic first hyperpolarizability (β_{total}) value for 2IA > 3C4FA.

The predicted mean polarizability values corresponding to 3C4FA and 2IA molecules are 2.98 and 3.42 times that of urea ($\alpha=25.63 \times 10^{-24}$ esu). The anisotropic polarizability values of 3C4FA and 2IA molecules are 1.48 and 1.90 times that of urea ($\Delta\alpha=48.81 \times 10^{-30}$ esu). Dipole moment of the 3C4FA and 2IA molecules are 2.1679 and 0.8226 Debye respectively. The increase in dipole moment, anisotropy and the mean polarizability provides better polarity in 3C4FA and 2IA system due to its donor group and intermolecular interactions.

E. HOMO-LUMO ANALYSIS

The frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) analysis reveals the spatial distribution of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). Pictorial representation of the frontier molecular orbitals with their positive and

negative regions using the basis set B3LYP/6-311++g(2d,2p) is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7 HOMO-LUMO analysis of 2IA and 3C4FA molecule

In 2IA, the HOMO charge distribution is nearly uniform, while the LUMO is concentrated on the iodine-substituted region of the phenyl ring, indicating electron transfer from the amino group to iodine through the ring. In 3C4FA, the HOMO is mainly localized on fluorine, whereas the LUMO is delocalized over the phenyl ring, showing electron transfer from the fluorine lone pair to the π -system; these transitions ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$) are consistent with NBO analysis. The relatively small HOMO–LUMO energy gaps (4.6926 eV for 2IA and 4.9377 eV for 3C4FA) indicate significant intramolecular charge transfer, enhancing molecular stability and nonlinear optical (NLO) activity. Additionally, the negative chemical potentials (-3.3151 eV and -3.5382 eV) and lower values compared to electrophilicity indices (2.3420 eV and 2.5354 eV) further confirm the stability of both molecules.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The planarity of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group follows the order p-IA > 2IA > p-BA, while 3C4FA shows the highest planarity due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding involving fluorine. NBO analysis indicates stronger $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ intermolecular interactions in 2IA than 3C4FA, and $\pi-\pi$ interactions further enhance NLO activity in both molecules. Hirshfeld and HOMO–LUMO analyses confirm significant intermolecular interactions and intramolecular charge transfer with small energy gaps (2IA: 4.6926 eV; 3C4FA: 4.9377 eV).

Experimental and simulated IR/Raman spectra agree well, with band splitting attributed to hydrogen bonding and intermolecular interactions. UV–Vis results show higher absorbance in substituted anilines, with dichloromethane as a suitable solvent. Overall, polarizability and hyperpolarizability values indicate NLO efficiency in the order: p-IA > 2IA > 3C4FA > p-BA > urea.

V. REFERENCE

- [1] Yamamoto N, Ohashi K, Hino K, Izutsu H, Mogi K, Sakai Y and Sekiya H, *Chem Phys Lett* 345 (5–6) (2001) pp.532–538
- [2] Wojciechowski P M, Michalska D, *Spectrochim Acta - Part A Mol Biomol Spectrosc* 68 (3) (2007) pp. 948–955
- [3] Sun X B, Wang X Q, Ren Q, Zhang G H, Yang H L, Feng L, *Mater Res Bull*, 41 (2006) pp. 177–182
- [4] George M, John N L, Kumar M S, Sajan D, *J Mol Struct*, 1128 (2016) pp. 754–768
- [5] Ohba S, *Acta Cryst B*, 48 (1992) pp. 849–854
- [6] Parkin A, Christopher K, Pulham R, *Acta Crystallogr Sect E*, 61 (2005) pp. 1087–1089
- [7] Wojciechowski P, Helios K, Michalska D, *Vib Spectrosc*, 57 (2011) pp. 126–134
- [8] Gee C, Douin S, Crepin C, Brechignac P, *Chem Phys Lett*, 338 (2001) pp. 130–136
- [9] Wojciechowski P M, Zierkiewicz W, Michalska D, Hobza P, *J Chem Phys*, 118 (24) (2003) pp. 10900–10911
- [10] Nimmy L John, Sunila Abraham, Sajan D, Sarojini B K, Narayana B, *J Mol Struct*, 1222 (2020) pp. 128939
- [11] Frisch G, Trucks H, Schlegel M, *Gaussian 09*. (Inc Wallingford)2009
- [12] Woon D E, Dunning T H, *J Chem Phys*, 98 (2) (1993) pp. 1358–1371
- [13] Glendening J, Badenhoop A, Reed J, Carpenter J, Bohmann C, Morales F, Weinhold E, *NBO 5.0*. (Theor Chem Insti,University of Wisconsin, Madison) 2001
- [14] Mckinnon J J, Mark A, Anthony S *Struct Sci*, 60 (2004) pp. 627–668
- [15] Ake Kwick, Margit B, *Acta Cryst B*, 40 (1974) 474–480
- [16] Sundius T, *Vib Spectrosc*, 29 (1) (2002) pp. 89–95
- [17] Fuhrer V B, Kartha K L, Kidd P J, Kruger H H, Mantsch H, *Computer Program for Infrared and Spectrometry, Normal Coordinate Analysis*. (Ottawa, National Research Council: Canada) 1976, Vol 5
- [18] Lister D G, Tyler J K, Høg J H, Larsen N W, *J Mol Struct*, 23 (2) (1974) pp. 253–264
- [19] Samdal S, Vilkov L, Volden H, *Acta Chem Scand*, 46 (8) (1992) pp. 712–719
- [20] Hirshfeld F L. *Theor Chim Acta*, 44 (1977) pp. 129–138

Smart Ambulance System for Intelligent Emergency Response Using GPS and IoT-Based Traffic Pre-emption

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Abstract- Traffic congestion in rapidly urbanizing cities significantly delays ambulance movement, directly affecting patient survival during critical emergencies. This paper presents a Smart Ambulance System designed to dynamically create an intelligent green corridor using real-time GPS tracking, IoT-enabled traffic nodes, and priority-based signal pre-emption. The system integrates an Android-based ambulance application that continuously transmits location, speed, direction, and medical priority level to nearby intersections through wireless communication. Distributed traffic controllers compute real-time distance using the Haversine formula and estimate arrival time (ETA) to safely pre-empt signal phases through a finite state machine mechanism. A triage-based priority model (P1, P2, P3) ensures optimized decision-making in multi-ambulance scenarios, granting precedence based on urgency and shortest ETA. Additionally, patient vitals and treatment details are transmitted to hospitals before arrival, enhancing casualty preparedness and reducing response latency. The proposed architecture is modular, scalable, and infrastructure-efficient, eliminating the need for RFID-based junction hardware while maintaining reliability through fail-safe recovery mechanisms. Experimental evaluation demonstrates significant reduction in intersection delay and improved emergency coordination, making the framework suitable for integration into smart city transportation and healthcare ecosystems.

Keywords— Smart Ambulance System, IoT, GPS Tracking, Traffic Signal Pre-emption, Green Corridor, Emergency Healthcare, Smart Cities, Real-Time Monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban transportation systems are experiencing unprecedented pressure due to rapid urbanization, population growth, and the exponential increase in vehicular density. Among the most critical consequences of traffic congestion is the delay faced by emergency vehicles, particularly ambulances transporting patients in life-threatening conditions. Medical research consistently emphasizes the importance of the “golden hour,” the crucial period immediately following a severe medical emergency during which prompt treatment significantly improves survival probability. Even a delay of a few minutes at congested intersections can drastically reduce patient survival rates, making efficient emergency vehicle movement a fundamental requirement for modern cities.

Traditional traffic signal control mechanisms operate on fixed timing schedules or adaptive density-based algorithms that optimize general traffic flow. While these systems improve overall transportation efficiency, they lack a dynamic and dedicated emergency prioritization mechanism. Existing solutions such as RFID-based ambulance detection require physical hardware installation at every junction, increasing infrastructure costs and maintenance complexity. Furthermore, such systems may suffer from signal interference, limited scalability, and vulnerability to unauthorized triggering. Centralized cloud-based traffic management solutions have also been explored; however, their heavy reliance on uninterrupted internet connectivity raises concerns regarding latency and reliability during network disruptions.

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a Smart Ambulance System that integrates real-time GPS tracking, IoT-enabled traffic signal controllers, and intelligent priority-based signal pre-emption. Unlike conventional infrastructure-heavy approaches, the proposed system leverages wireless communication and distributed embedded controllers to dynamically create a synchronized green corridor along the ambulance route. The system continuously monitors ambulance position, speed, and direction, computes Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) using geospatial distance calculations, and safely adjusts signal phases through a finite state machine-based control mechanism.

In addition to traffic preemption, the proposed framework enhances emergency healthcare coordination by transmitting patient vitals, administered medications, and expected arrival time to the destination hospital in advance. This early notification enables medical staff to prepare required equipment and personnel, reducing response latency upon arrival. The integration of transportation intelligence with healthcare communication represents a significant advancement toward smart city emergency infrastructure.

The Smart Ambulance System is designed to be modular, scalable, and cost-effective, enabling deployment in urban as well as semi-urban regions without extensive infrastructure modification. By combining IoT, embedded systems, real-time geolocation processing, and intelligent arbitration logic, the proposed solution aims to significantly reduce emergency response time and improve overall public safety outcomes.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Antriksh Saini et al. [1] proposed an RFID-based traffic management system in which passive RFID tags embedded in emergency vehicles interact with active RFID readers installed at traffic junctions. Upon detection, the traffic controller automatically switches the signal to green for the approaching emergency vehicle. While the approach effectively reduces intersection delay in controlled environments, it requires dedicated RFID infrastructure at every junction, leading to increased installation and maintenance costs. Additionally, RFID systems are susceptible to signal interference and spoofing risks if not properly secured.

Dr. Vikram Bali et al. [2] introduced an IoT-enabled smart traffic management system integrating cloud-based monitoring and automatic signal control mechanisms. The architecture enables centralized supervision and real-time data analysis for traffic optimization. Although the system improves visibility and coordination within smart city ecosystems, its heavy dependence on reliable cloud connectivity may

introduce latency and reliability issues during network congestion or outages. Furthermore, the model primarily focuses on general traffic optimization rather than dedicated multi-ambulance prioritization.

Anum Mushtaq et al. [3] explored the application of deep reinforcement learning techniques for traffic flow management of autonomous vehicles. The system utilizes intelligent rerouting strategies to reduce congestion and improve overall efficiency. While reinforcement learning models demonstrate strong predictive performance and adaptability, they require substantial computational resources and large-scale training datasets. Such requirements may limit their feasibility for lightweight, real-time embedded traffic controllers deployed at individual intersections.

Salem Jeyaseelan W. R. et al. [4] proposed an IoT-based smart ambulance transportation system utilizing wireless sensor networks and traffic signal controllers to facilitate emergency movement. The system enhances coordination between vehicles and traffic infrastructure; however, it relies primarily on rule-based logic without incorporating dynamic ETA computation or advanced arbitration strategies in scenarios involving multiple simultaneous emergency vehicles.

Abdullah Faiz Al Azmari et al. [5] presented a multi-instance learning optimization model for intelligent transportation systems in smart cities. The model focuses on congestion prediction and interaction optimization across traffic nodes. Although the approach improves traffic management efficiency, it does not specifically address the time-critical nature of ambulance prioritization or real-time hospital coordination.

Talia Simoes dos Santos Ximenes et al. [6] examined vehicular traffic flow detection and monitoring for implementing smart traffic lights using GPS and IoT technologies. The system provides accurate tracking and improved signal management but does not incorporate a structured triage-based priority mechanism for emergency vehicles.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

System Overview

The Smart Ambulance System is designed as a distributed IoT-enabled emergency traffic coordination framework that dynamically creates a synchronized green corridor for ambulances in congested urban environments. The system integrates a GPS-enabled ambulance communication module, embedded traffic signal controllers, a centralized monitoring server, and a hospital pre-notification interface into a unified operational architecture. Unlike conventional RFID-based solutions that require physical infrastructure at every intersection, the proposed model leverages real-

time geolocation data and wireless communication to achieve intelligent traffic pre-emption with minimal hardware overhead.

The ambulance is equipped with an Android-based mobile application that continuously captures GPS coordinates, vehicle speed, travel direction, and an assigned medical priority level. These parameters are transmitted at periodic intervals through a Wi-Fi-based communication protocol to nearby traffic intersections and the central monitoring server. Each traffic node independently processes the received data, computes real-time proximity, and determines whether signal pre-emption is required.

A dynamic Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) computation mechanism ensures that traffic signals are adjusted precisely when necessary, avoiding unnecessary disruption to regular traffic flow. In addition to traffic coordination, the system transmits patient vitals and emergency details to the destination hospital, enabling medical teams to prepare before the ambulance arrives. This integrated transportation-healthcare approach significantly enhances emergency response efficiency.

System Architecture

Figure 1: Smart Ambulance System Architecture

The system architecture consists of four primary layers: the Ambulance Communication Layer, the Traffic Control Layer, the Central Monitoring Layer, and the Hospital Coordination Layer.

The Ambulance Communication Layer captures GPS location, speed, and direction data using the smartphone's integrated positioning services. The mobile application packages these parameters along with a predefined priority code (P1, P2, or P3) and transmits them in structured format.

The Traffic Control Layer comprises ESP32-based embedded controllers installed at signalized intersections. These controllers are integrated with Wi-Fi modules and 74HC595 shift registers to efficiently manage multi-directional signal outputs while minimizing GPIO utilization. Upon receiving ambulance data, the controller computes the Haversine distance between the ambulance and the intersection and estimates the arrival time based on current velocity.

The Central Monitoring Layer logs ambulance movements, signal changes, and system diagnostics. This layer provides administrative oversight and facilitates future analytics for optimization and scalability.

The Hospital Coordination Layer receives patient medical data, including vital signs, administered medication, and estimated arrival time. This pre-notification mechanism ensures improved casualty preparedness and reduced treatment latency.

Operational Workflow

When an ambulance begins an emergency trip, the mobile application activates continuous location transmission. Traffic nodes within a predefined radius (typically 2–3 km) receive the ambulance's real-time coordinates. Each node computes the geospatial distance using the Haversine formula and calculates ETA as:

$$\text{ETA} = \text{Distance} / \text{Current Speed}$$

If the computed ETA falls below a predefined threshold, the traffic controller initiates a controlled signal pre-emption process. The signal transitions through a structured finite state machine (FSM) consisting of the following operational states:

- Normal Mode – Regular signal operation
- Warning Mode – Preparation phase before transition
- Clearing Mode – Safe clearance of conflicting lanes
- Green Corridor Mode – Dedicated green signal for ambulance lane
- Recovery Mode – Gradual restoration to default timing cycle

This structured transition mechanism ensures both safety and predictability during emergency prioritization.

Priority Arbitration Mechanism

The system implements a triage-based priority model to manage scenarios involving multiple simultaneous ambulances. Three priority levels are defined:

- P1 – Critical emergency cases
- P2 – Serious but stable conditions
- P3 – non-critical transport

When multiple ambulances approach an intersection concurrently, the arbitration logic grants precedence to the highest priority level. If two ambulances share the same priority level, the system compares ETA values and grants access to the vehicle with the shorter arrival time. In rare cases where both priority and ETA are equal, a first-registered-first-served mechanism is applied.

This structured arbitration strategy ensures fairness while maintaining medical urgency alignment.

Safety and Reliability Considerations

To prevent unsafe signal switching, the system enforces minimum red and green durations for each lane. A watchdog timer continuously monitors

controller performance and automatically resets the system in case of malfunction. If communication between the ambulance and traffic node fails, the controller reverts to default signal operation, ensuring uninterrupted traffic functionality.

Additionally, authentication mechanisms are implemented within the mobile application to prevent unauthorized signal triggering. Only verified emergency units are permitted to request signal pre-emption.

The proposed Smart Ambulance System therefore provides a lightweight, scalable, and intelligent emergency traffic coordination framework. By integrating GPS-based real-time tracking, distributed embedded processing, structured state transitions, and healthcare pre-notification, the system significantly enhances emergency response efficiency while maintaining traffic safety and operational reliability.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Design

The Smart Ambulance System follows a distributed embedded IoT architecture designed to ensure low latency, scalability, and reliability in real-time emergency traffic coordination. The system is structured around decentralized traffic nodes capable of autonomous decision-making while maintaining synchronization with a lightweight central monitoring server. This hybrid architecture reduces dependency on continuous cloud connectivity and enhances resilience during network fluctuations.

Each traffic junction is equipped with an ESP32-based embedded controller integrated with Wi-Fi capability and signal control hardware. The ESP32 microcontroller was selected due to its dual-core processing capability, low power consumption, and built-in wireless communication support, making it suitable for real-time applications. To efficiently manage multiple signal outputs with minimal GPIO usage, 74HC595 shift registers are integrated into the signal control circuitry. This approach allows scalable expansion to multi-lane intersections without increasing hardware complexity.

The ambulance communication system is implemented through an Android-based mobile application that utilizes the smartphone's GPS module for continuous geolocation tracking. The application captures latitude, longitude, velocity, heading direction, and medical priority level, packaging them into structured data packets. These packets are transmitted at fixed intervals to nearby traffic nodes using a Wi-Fi-based communication protocol. The system is designed to ensure minimal transmission latency while maintaining reliable data delivery.

The overall system design incorporates a finite state machine (FSM) model within each traffic node to manage safe signal transitions. This ensures that signal switching occurs gradually and adheres to minimum red and green timing constraints to prevent traffic hazards.

B. Implementation Details

Frontend Implementation

The ambulance-side application is developed using Android Studio, leveraging native GPS and networking APIs to ensure high accuracy and low communication delay. The user interface is designed to be simple and accessible for paramedics, allowing them to assign emergency priority levels (P1, P2, or P3) before initiating a trip. The application automatically begins location broadcasting once emergency mode is activated.

A web-based monitoring dashboard is implemented for administrative supervision. The dashboard displays real-time ambulance movement, traffic node status, and signal phase information. It provides visualization tools for tracking emergency routes and reviewing historical logs for performance analysis.

Backend Implementation

The backend server performs real-time data routing, ETA computation, and priority arbitration. Upon receiving ambulance location data, the server identifies relevant traffic nodes within a predefined radius and forwards the data accordingly. Each traffic node independently calculates the Haversine distance between its stored geographic coordinates and the ambulance's current position.

The Haversine formula is used for accurate geospatial distance computation between two latitude-longitude pairs on the Earth's surface. Based on the computed distance and the ambulance's current velocity, the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) is calculated as:

$$\text{ETA} = \text{Distance} / \text{Speed}$$

If the ETA falls below a defined threshold value, the traffic controller triggers the signal pre-emption sequence.

The system employs asynchronous communication handling to ensure that multiple ambulance updates are processed concurrently without blocking operations. Lightweight data structures are used to minimize computational overhead on embedded controllers.

Embedded Traffic Node Firmware

The firmware running on the ESP32 microcontroller is responsible for real-time decision-making. It continuously listens for ambulance broadcast messages

and updates its internal state accordingly. Once pre-emption conditions are satisfied, the firmware transitions through the finite state machine stages: Normal Mode, Warning Mode, Clearing Mode, Green Corridor Mode, and Recovery Mode.

Timers are implemented to enforce minimum phase durations, ensuring that no lane is abruptly terminated without sufficient clearance time. The embedded system is optimized for deterministic execution to guarantee consistent signal behaviour.

Security Mechanisms

To prevent unauthorized signal manipulation, the mobile application includes authentication mechanisms ensuring that only registered emergency units can initiate pre-emption requests. Unique identification credentials are assigned to each ambulance unit.

Data packets transmitted between the ambulance and traffic nodes are structured to prevent malformed input exploitation. Additionally, the system incorporates fail-safe logic whereby traffic nodes automatically revert to default timing cycles if communication is interrupted beyond a predefined timeout duration.

A watchdog timer is integrated into the embedded firmware to automatically reset the controller in case of software malfunction, thereby improving reliability.

Database Management and Logging

A lightweight database module is implemented at the central monitoring server to store ambulance trip logs, signal change events, ETA computations, and system diagnostics. This data enables performance evaluation, route optimization analysis, and future integration with predictive analytics models.

The database schema includes structured tables for ambulance identification, timestamped location updates, priority levels, signal transition records, and hospital notification events. Efficient indexing mechanisms are used to support fast querying during administrative review.

The design and implementation of the Smart Ambulance System emphasize modularity, real-time responsiveness, and operational safety. By integrating embedded systems, mobile communication, geospatial computation, and structured control logic, the framework provides a robust and scalable solution for emergency traffic pre-emption in modern smart city environments.

V. RESULTS

The Smart Ambulance System prototype was implemented and evaluated under simulated urban traffic conditions to analyse its performance in reducing emergency response delay and improving

coordination efficiency. Testing was conducted using multiple traffic node simulations and real-time GPS data streams to emulate ambulance movement across signalized intersections.

During controlled experiments, the system demonstrated a significant reduction in average intersection waiting time compared to conventional fixed-timing traffic signals. In baseline scenarios without pre-emption, ambulances experienced cumulative delays at multiple intersections due to red signal cycles. After activating the Smart Ambulance System, traffic nodes dynamically adjusted signal phases based on Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), resulting in an average delay reduction of approximately 35–45% across tested intersections. The reduction was more pronounced in high-density traffic simulations where congestion levels were elevated.

The Haversine-based distance computation and real-time ETA estimation mechanisms operated within acceptable latency bounds. Distance calculation and priority arbitration processes were executed within milliseconds on the embedded ESP32 controllers, ensuring that signal transitions occurred without perceptible lag. The finite state machine-based signal control successfully transitioned through Warning, Clearing, Green Corridor, and Recovery states without violating minimum phase duration constraints. This structured transition approach prevented abrupt signal changes and maintained traffic safety.

Multi-ambulance scenario testing was also conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the priority arbitration logic. In cases where ambulances with different priority levels approached the same intersection simultaneously, the system consistently granted precedence to higher-priority cases (P1 over P2 and P3). When equal-priority ambulances were detected, the arbitration mechanism correctly selected the vehicle with the shorter ETA. No deadlock or conflicting signal states were observed during these simulations, indicating robust conflict resolution capability.

The hospital pre-notification module successfully transmitted patient vitals and estimated arrival time to the simulated hospital dashboard. Medical staff simulation logs indicated improved preparedness, as casualty teams were able to arrange equipment and allocate personnel before the ambulance reached the facility. This reduced treatment initiation latency upon arrival.

Reliability testing under intermittent communication conditions demonstrated that traffic nodes automatically reverted to default signal cycles when ambulance data transmission was interrupted beyond the defined timeout threshold. The watchdog timer mechanism effectively restored controller functionality

in simulated fault scenarios, ensuring uninterrupted traffic operation.

Scalability evaluation indicated that additional traffic nodes could be integrated into the network without significant performance degradation, as decision-making is distributed across embedded controllers rather than centralized. This architecture reduces computational load on the server and enhances system resilience.

Overall, the experimental evaluation confirms that the Smart Ambulance System improves emergency vehicle mobility, reduces intersection delay, ensures fair multi-ambulance prioritization, and enhances hospital preparedness. The distributed IoT-based architecture demonstrates both reliability and scalability, making it suitable for deployment in smart city transportation infrastructures.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Although the proposed Smart Ambulance System demonstrates significant improvements in emergency response coordination and traffic signal pre-emption, several enhancements can be incorporated in future work to further strengthen its performance, scalability, and real-world adaptability.

One potential extension involves integrating machine learning algorithms for predictive traffic modelling. By analysing historical traffic density data and ambulance movement patterns, predictive models could estimate congestion levels in advance and dynamically suggest optimal routes even before an ambulance encounters traffic. This would further reduce travel time and improve routing efficiency under highly variable traffic conditions.

Another promising enhancement is the incorporation of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication technology. Direct communication between ambulances and nearby vehicles could enable surrounding drivers to receive real-time alerts through in-vehicle systems or mobile notifications. Such integration would enhance situational awareness and facilitate smoother lane clearance beyond signalized intersections.

The system can also be expanded to support multi-city or statewide deployment using cloud-based microservices architecture. While the current distributed design minimizes cloud dependency, centralized analytics platforms could provide macro-level traffic insights, long-term performance evaluation, and predictive healthcare logistics planning. Integration with existing smart city command centers would allow seamless coordination across emergency services such as fire departments and law enforcement units.

Future improvements may include enhanced security mechanisms such as end-to-end encryption and

blockchain-based authentication to prevent unauthorized access or malicious signal manipulation. As the system scales, cybersecurity becomes increasingly critical to ensure safe and reliable operation.

Additionally, real-world pilot deployment and large-scale field testing would provide more comprehensive performance metrics under diverse environmental and traffic conditions. Integration with live traffic cameras, roadside sensors, and adaptive signal control systems could further refine decision-making accuracy.

Finally, the system can be extended beyond ambulance services to support other priority vehicles such as fire engines, disaster response units, and organ transport vehicles. By expanding its operational domain, the framework can evolve into a comprehensive intelligent emergency mobility management system within smart city ecosystems.

In summary, the Smart Ambulance System provides a strong foundation for intelligent emergency traffic coordination, and with continued technological enhancements and large-scale validation, it has the potential to become a critical component of future urban healthcare and transportation infrastructures.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The Smart Ambulance System presented in this work establishes a strong foundation for intelligent emergency traffic management; however, several enhancements can be incorporated to further improve its efficiency, scalability, and real-world applicability. Future research can focus on integrating advanced predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms to optimize route planning based on historical traffic patterns, weather conditions, and time-of-day congestion trends. Such predictive capabilities would enable proactive corridor creation rather than reactive signal pre-emption.

The incorporation of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication technology represents another promising direction. Direct communication between ambulances and nearby vehicles could provide early warning alerts to drivers through dashboard notifications or mobile applications, facilitating smoother lane clearance even before signal-based intervention occurs. This would enhance coordination beyond intersection-level control and create a more comprehensive emergency mobility ecosystem.

Further development may involve large-scale cloud integration using microservices architecture to support city-wide or inter-city deployment. Centralized analytics platforms could provide long-term performance monitoring, traffic heat-map generation, and system health diagnostics. Integration with municipal smart city command centres would allow coordination among multiple emergency services such as fire, police, and disaster response units.

Security and data integrity enhancements also constitute an important area for future work. Implementation of end-to-end encryption, secure authentication frameworks, and intrusion detection mechanisms would ensure protection against unauthorized signal manipulation. As deployment scale increases, robust cybersecurity strategies will become essential to maintain system reliability and public trust.

In addition, real-world pilot implementation across multiple intersections and diverse traffic conditions would provide comprehensive empirical validation. Performance evaluation under varying environmental factors, peak-hour congestion, and multi-emergency scenarios would help refine arbitration algorithms and optimize signal transition timing parameters.

Finally, the system can be extended to support other priority vehicles such as fire engines, organ transport vehicles, and disaster relief units. By broadening its scope, the framework can evolve into a unified intelligent emergency mobility management system, contributing significantly to smart city transportation infrastructure and public safety enhancement.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a Smart Ambulance System designed to reduce emergency response delays through intelligent traffic signal pre-emption and real-time healthcare coordination. The proposed framework integrates GPS-based ambulance tracking, distributed IoT-enabled traffic controllers, ETA-based decision-making, and a structured finite state machine mechanism to dynamically create a synchronized green corridor. Unlike conventional infrastructure-heavy solutions such as RFID-based systems, the proposed approach minimizes hardware dependency while ensuring scalability, reliability, and cost-effectiveness.

The implementation demonstrates that distributed embedded processing using ESP32-based traffic nodes enables low-latency signal control without excessive reliance on centralized cloud infrastructure. The incorporation of the Haversine distance formula and real-time Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) computation allows precise and timely signal transitions, reducing unnecessary traffic disruption. Furthermore, the triage-based priority arbitration mechanism ensures fair and

medically aligned decision-making in multi-ambulance scenarios.

In addition to traffic optimization, the integration of hospital pre-notification enhances emergency preparedness by transmitting patient vitals and arrival estimates in advance. Reliability mechanisms such as watchdog timers, fail-safe reversion to default signal cycles, and authentication protocols contribute to system robustness and operational safety.

Experimental evaluation under simulated traffic conditions confirms that the system significantly reduces intersection delay and improves emergency mobility efficiency. The modular and distributed architecture ensures adaptability to diverse urban environments, making it suitable for integration within smart city transportation and healthcare infrastructures.

Overall, the Smart Ambulance System provides a scalable, intelligent, and infrastructure-efficient solution for modern emergency response management. With further real-world deployment and integration into broader intelligent transportation ecosystems, the proposed framework has the potential to substantially enhance public safety and critical healthcare delivery in rapidly urbanizing regions.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Saini, R. Sharma, and P. Verma, "RFID-Based Intelligent Traffic Signal Control System for Emergency Vehicles," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET)*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 742–746, Mar. 2016.
- [2] V. Bali, S. Kumar, and A. Gupta, "IoT-Based Smart Traffic Management System," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE)*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1204–1208, Apr. 2019.
- [3] A. Mushtaq, M. A. Khan, and S. Rehman, "Deep Reinforcement Learning for Traffic Signal Control of Autonomous Vehicles," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [4] S. J. W. R. Jeyaseelan, K. Prakash, and R. Balasubramanian, "IoT-Based Smart Ambulance and Traffic Control System," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 1078–1083, May 2020.

[5] A. F. Al Azmari, M. Alqarni, and H. Alharthi, "Optimization of Intelligent Transportation Systems Using Multi-Instance Learning in Smart Cities," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 135421–135433, 2021.

[6] T. S. dos Santos Ximenes, L. R. C. de Souza, and M. A. M. Carvalho, "Vehicular Traffic Flow Monitoring and Smart Traffic Light Control Using IoT and GPS Technologies," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 14, pp. 1–18, 2022.

SPIROBS COPTER

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Abstract—This project introduces a manual operated drone designed for object lifting to easy shipping and for rescue operations, equipped with camera, flight controller, ultrasonic sensor, GSM module, LCD display, servomotor, propeller and arm. The drone might collect items in real-time and provide lifting and also provide delivery system individually. The outcomes of this project hold significant relevance to industries, society, and academic institutions, contributing to technological innovation, societal impact, and advancements in robotics and unmanned systems.

Keywords: Spirobs Copter; Flight Controller; Robotic Arm Integration; Rescue Operation Drone; Object Lifting Drone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drones equipped with robotic arms are transforming industries like logistics, rescue operations, and inspection. By combining aerial mobility with precise manipulation, these systems can grasp, lift, and transport objects in hard-to-reach areas. This prototype opens up new possibilities for tasks like delivering medical supplies, handling hazardous materials, or conducting search-and-rescue missions. As these

systems advance, they're likely to play a key role in shaping the future of autonomous operations.

II. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A. Mechanical Design.

- Frame Design:
 - X-type quadcopter frame (for better stability)
 - Lightweight carbon fiber or aluminum
 - Central plate for mounting robotic arm
- Propulsion System:
 - 4 - Brushless DC Motors
 - 4 - Electronic Speed Controllers (ESC)
 - 4 - Propellers
 - Li-Po Battery

B. Flight Control System

- **Autopilot System:** The Spirobs copter is equipped with an advanced autopilot system, which enables stable and autonomous flight.

- **Sensor Suite:** The sensor suite includes GPS, accelerometer, gyroscope, and barometer, providing accurate navigation and control.

The flight dynamics of the Spirobs copter can be described by the following equations:

- **Pitch Angle (θ):**

$$\theta = \arctan \left(\frac{L \cdot \sin(\phi)}{m \cdot g} \right)$$

where ϕ is roll angle, m is mass, and g is gravity.

- **Roll Angle (ϕ):**

$$\phi = \arctan \left(\frac{L \cdot \sin(\theta)}{m \cdot g} \right)$$

The movement of the quad copter is controlled by varying the relative thrust of each of the 4 motor. Here, we are using quad copter of X shape. In this quad copter, the motor located on the same diagonal moves in the same direction either clockwise direction (CW) or counterclockwise direction (CCW). Flying system has different terminology viz. yaw, roll and pitch.

Before knowing the flying dynamics of a quad copter, we need to understand three main parameters of angular motion of quad copter, which are yaw, roll and pitch.

Roll:

The axis which runs back of the drone to the front of the drone is called a roll axis and rotation about this axis is called roll motion. This motion is also known as aileron. In the image given below, we can see roll motion.

(Figure 1): Roll axis and roll motion

Pitch:

The axis which runs from left of the drone to the right of the drone is called pitch axis. The rotation about this axis is called pitch motion. It is also known as elevator motion. In image given below, we can see pitch motion.

(a.) Pitch axis and pitch motion

Yaw:

The axis which runs from top of the drone towards bottom of the drone is called yaw axis. The rotation about this axis is called yaw motion. It is also known as rudder. In image given below, we can see yaw motion.

(Figure 2): Yaw axis and yaw motion

With the help of image given below, we can understand all the three motions together.

(Figure 4): Three motions are together-Roll, Yaw & Pitch

These are not lateral movement themselves but rotation along the three different axes. Even lateral movement is a result of rotation along these axes. To understand control of the drone, we first need to understand different forces acting on the drone. If thrust = weight (mg), then quad copter will remain in equilibrium. If thrust > weight (mg) then drone will go upward and if thrust < weight (mg) then drone will go downward.

Motion in Forward and Backward Direction:

If we want to move drone in the forward direction, we need to generate the component of thrust in forward direction. This is done by increasing the power of the rear motors and reducing the power of the front motors. If we want to move drone in backward direction, we reduce the power of the rear motors and increase the power in the front motors.

Motion in Left and Right Direction:

To move the drone to the left, we generate the component of thrust in the left direction. This is done by increasing the power of the right motors and reducing the power of the left motors. To move the drone to the right, we increase the power of the left motor and reduce the power of the right motor.

Yaw Motion of Quad Copter:

For yaw movement, things can get a bit tricky, when we want to yaw drone in CW direction, we will increase the power to the counterclockwise propellers the resulting reactive torque will yaw the drone in the clockwise direction. If we want to yaw drone in CCW direction, we will increase the power to the clockwise propellers and the resulting reactive torque will yaw the drone in the counterclockwise direction, so to control the motion of quad rotor, we control the power that we give to its motor.

C. Control System

The control system of the Spirobs copter employs a PID controller, which can be described by the following equation:

- PID Controller:

$$u(t) = K_p * e(t) + K_i * \int e(t)dt + K_d * de(t)/dt$$

where u(t) is control input, e(t) is error, Kp is proportional gain, Ki is integral gain, and Kd is derivative gain.

D. Design of Robotic Arm

(Figure 5): 3-DOF Design of robotic arm

The design appears to be a 3-DOF (degree-freedom) articulated robotic arm mounted on a cylindrical base. The arm has three joints:

1. Base rotation (waist joint) – rotates the whole arm about the vertical axis.
2. Shoulder joint – lifts the upper arm.
3. Elbow joint – positions the forearm.

The end-effector is a two-finger gripper for picking objects.

Typical kinematic equations for a 3-DOF robotic arm:

For forward kinematics (calculating the gripper position (x, y, z) from joint angles $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$):

$$X = L_1 \cos(\theta_1) + L_2 \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + L_3 \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3)$$

$$Y = L_1 \sin(\theta_1) + L_2 \sin(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + L_3 \sin(\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3)$$

$$Z = h + L_2 \sin(\theta_2) + L_3 \sin(\theta_2 + \theta_3)$$

where

- L_1, L_2, L_3 are the lengths of the base, upper arm, and forearm,
- h is the base height,
- $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ are the joint angles.

III. MODELLING OF PROTOTYPE

A. Modelling

(Figure 6): Drone with 3-DOF arm

The setup is a quadcopter UAV with a 3-degree-of-freedom (3-DOF) robotic arm mounted on it.

- The drone has four propellers and a central frame holding electronic components (likely flight controller and sensors).

- The robotic arm appears attached underneath the quadcopter frame, designed for manipulation tasks.

- The configuration enables aerial mobility combined with object handling using the 3-DOF arm:

This setup is suitable for tasks like picking and placing objects in hard-to-reach locations or performing remote inspections with the robotic arm.

The system's ability to grasp and manipulate objects in mid-air highlights its potential for applications like disaster response, infrastructure inspection, and remote delivery.

- **Kinematics & Dynamics:** Deriving equations for the drone's motion and the arm's joint movements.

- **State-Space Representation:** Modelling the system for control design.

- **Disturbance Modelling:** Accounting for arm-induced disturbances on drone stability.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION RESULT

- A. **Objective:** Assess the stability and maneuverability of the drone while operating the integrated 3-DOF robotic arm.

- B. **Methodology:** The drone was flown in a controlled indoor environment with predefined waypoints. The arm performed pick-and-place tasks at each waypoint. Flight parameters (position, attitude, and vibration) and arm joint angles were logged using onboard sensors and an external telemetry system.

- C. **Metrics:** Tracking error of the drone's position, arm joint angle accuracy, and payload disturbance effects on flight stability were measured.

RESULT

- The drone maintained positional accuracy within ± 0.12 m during arm operation, showing minimal disturbance from the arm's motion.

- Arm joint angle tracking error was $< 2^\circ$, indicating good responsiveness.

- Payload handling with the 3-DOF arm increased overall system energy consumption by 8% but did not compromise flight stability.

- The integrated system successfully completed all waypoint tasks with the arm executing the intended manipulations without loss of drone control.

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of a 3-DOF robotic arm with a quadcopter drone enables versatile aerial manipulation capabilities, making it suitable for tasks like remote inspection, object retrieval, and disaster

response. The system's ability to grasp and manipulate objects in mid-air highlights its potential for various applications. With further development, such systems can revolutionize industries like logistics, construction, and environmental monitoring.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhanchi Wang, Nikolaos M. Freris, Xi Wei (2025). SpiRobs: Logarithmic spiral-shaped robots for versatile grasping across scales. *Device* 3, 100646.
- [2] Hauser, H., and Hughes, J. (2024). Morphological computation Past, present and future. *Device* 2, 100439.
- [3] Wang, Z., and Freris, N.M. (2024). Exploiting Frictional Effects to Reproduce Octopus Like Reaching Movements with a Cable-Driven Spiral Robot. In *IEEE International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft)*, papers. 537–542.
- [4] Zournatzis, I., Kalaitzakis, S., and Polygerinos, P. (2023). SoftER: A Spiral Soft Robotic Ejector for Sorting Applications. *IEEE Robot. Automons. Letter.* 8, 7098–7105.
- [5] Sugiura, S., Unde, J., Zhu, Y., and Hasegawa, Y. (2023). High-strength and flexible mechanism for body weight support. *Robomech Journal.* 10, 16.

SMART GARBAGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract— *The Smart Garbage Management System uses IoT and machine learning techniques to automatically segregate waste into metal, wet, plastic, and paper categories. Real-time monitoring is achieved using ESP32 with Wi-Fi connectivity, enabling data transmission to a website for live tracking. This system optimizes waste collection and supports smart city initiatives. Rapid urbanization has resulted in a significant increase in solid waste generation, creating major challenges in waste collection, segregation, and environmental sustainability. Traditional waste management systems lack automation and real-time monitoring, often leading to overflowing bins, health hazards, and inefficient recycling processes. This paper presents a Smart Garbage Management System that integrates Internet of Things (IoT), sensor technology, and machine learning to automate waste segregation and enable real-time monitoring. The system employs an ESP32 microcontroller and ESP32-CAM module for intelligent classification of waste into metal, wet (biodegradable), plastic, and paper categories. Inductive sensors detect metallic waste, moisture sensors identify biodegradable waste, and image-based classification distinguishes plastic and paper materials. An ultrasonic sensor monitors waste levels, while servo motors direct waste into appropriate compartments. Real-time data is transmitted to a web-based platform for monitoring and management. The proposed system reduces manual intervention, improves recycling efficiency, and supports sustainable smart city development.*

Keywords— *IoT, ESP32, Smart Bin, Waste Segregation, Ultrasonic Sensor, Inductive Sensor, Moisture Sensor, Smart City.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Waste management is one of the most critical challenges faced by urban areas worldwide. The rapid growth of population and industrialization has significantly increased the generation of municipal solid waste. Conventional waste collection systems rely on manual inspection and fixed collection schedules, which often result in inefficient resource utilization and environmental pollution. Overflowing garbage bins cause unpleasant odors, spread diseases, and contribute to land and water pollution. Additionally, improper segregation of waste reduces recycling efficiency and increases landfill burden. To address these issues, smart waste management systems using IoT have gained significant attention. IoT-enabled smart bins provide real-time monitoring, automated segregation, and optimized collection routes. This project proposes an intelligent waste segregation and monitoring system that integrates sensors and machine learning to classify waste and transmit real-time data.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several researchers have contributed to the development of smart waste management systems. LoRa-based systems have been proposed for long-range communication between bins and central monitoring stations. IoT-based smart bins using ultrasonic sensors detect fill levels and notify authorities when bins are full. Recent advancements incorporate deep learning models such as MobileNet V3 and Edge TPU accelerators for image-based waste classification. Some systems include gas sensors, weight sensors, and GPS modules for enhanced monitoring. Although existing systems provide monitoring capabilities, many lack integrated waste segregation mechanisms combining sensor-based and image-based classification. The proposed system improves upon previous work by integrating multiple detection techniques within a single automated unit.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing traditional waste management system, garbage collection is performed manually. Workers collect waste from bins at fixed intervals without checking whether the bin is full or empty. Waste segregation is often done manually, which increases human effort and exposure to harmful materials. Some smart systems use ultrasonic sensors only to detect bin level but do not provide automatic waste segregation. Others use single detection methods that are not highly accurate. These systems lack integrated multi-sensor classification and intelligent automation.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed Smart Garbage Management System integrates multiple sensors and image-based classification to automatically segregate waste into different categories such as metal, wet waste, plastic, and paper. When a user places waste inside the bin, the ultrasonic sensor detects its presence. The inductive sensor checks whether the waste is metallic. If metal is detected, the servo motor rotates to direct the waste into the metal compartment. If metal is not detected, the moisture sensor checks whether the waste is wet or biodegradable. If moisture content is high, the waste is directed to the wet waste compartment.

If the waste is dry, the ESP32-CAM captures an image and classifies it as plastic or paper using a trained machine learning model. Based on classification results, the servo motor directs the waste into the appropriate compartment. The ESP32 microcontroller transmits real-time data to a web platform for monitoring garbage levels and waste type statistics.

V. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

A. ESP32 Microcontroller

The ESP32 is a dual-core microcontroller with built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capabilities. It serves as the central processing unit of the system. It processes sensor data, controls servo motors, updates LCD display, and transmits data to the cloud platform.

B. ESP32-CAM

The ESP32-CAM module includes an OV2640 camera capable of capturing images up to 1600×1200 resolution. It performs image-based classification to distinguish plastic and paper waste using a trained machine learning model.

C. Ultrasonic Sensor (HC-SR04)

The ultrasonic sensor detects the presence of waste and measures the fill level of the bin. It works on the echo principle by transmitting ultrasonic waves and measuring the time taken for reflection.

D. Inductive Sensor

The inductive sensor detects metallic waste using electromagnetic field disturbance. When metal enters the sensing range, the sensor output changes, indicating the presence of metal.

E. Moisture Sensor

The moisture sensor measures electrical resistance variation to determine whether waste is wet or biodegradable.

F. Servo Motors

Servo motors provide precise angular control to open and close compartments and direct waste accordingly.

G. LCD Display (16×2)

The LCD displays the detected waste type and bin status in real time.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

The system operates in a step-by-step automated process. When waste is inserted, the ultrasonic sensor detects it and activates the classification sequence. The inductive sensor checks for metal detection. If metal is not detected, the moisture sensor measures moisture level. For dry waste, the ESP32-CAM captures an image and classifies it using a machine learning model. The ESP32 processes all sensor data and controls the servo motor accordingly. After classification, the LCD displays the detected waste type. The ESP32 updates bin status and waste information to the online monitoring platform using Wi-Fi connectivity. This automated workflow reduces manual effort, improves segregation accuracy, and ensures efficient waste management.

VII. BLOCK DIAGRAM

VIII. CONCLUSION

The Smart Garbage Management System provides an efficient and intelligent solution for modern waste management challenges. By integrating IoT, sensors, and machine learning, the system automatically segregates waste and enables real-time monitoring. It reduces manual labor, enhances recycling efficiency, and promotes environmental sustainability.

The system is scalable and can be implemented in residential areas, public spaces, and smart cities. Future enhancements can include GPS tracking, gas sensors, and solar-powered operation.

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REFERENCE

- [1] L. Atzori, A. Iera, and G. Morabito, "The Internet of Things: A survey," *Computer Networks*, 2010.
- [2] T. J. Sheng et al., "IoT Based Smart Waste Management Using LoRa," *IEEE Access*, 2020.
- [3] A. Zourmand et al., "Internet of Things using LoRa technology," *IEEE I2CACIS*, 2019.
- [4] Murniningsih and Setiawan, "Sustainable Smart Waste Management," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2020.
- [5] Jiang and Zhang, "Blockchain applications in waste management," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2023.

DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE ORGANIC PRODUCT FOR DEFLUORIDATION OF WATER

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ABSTRACT

Excessive fluoride concentration in drinking water poses serious health risks, including dental fluorosis and skeletal fluorosis. Conventional defluoridation techniques such as reverse osmosis, ion exchange, and chemical precipitation are often expensive and generate secondary waste. This study proposes an eco-friendly and sustainable approach for fluoride removal using organic adsorbents derived from agricultural wastes such as rice husk and groundnut shells. The raw materials were cleaned, dried, carbonized, ground, and sieved to produce a porous bio-adsorbent with high surface area. Batch adsorption experiments were conducted to evaluate the effect of adsorbent dosage on fluoride removal efficiency. Experimental results showed a maximum fluoride removal efficiency of approximately 58.3%. The developed adsorbent demonstrates potential as a low-cost and sustainable solution for rural water purification systems.

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KEYWORDS

Defluoridation, Bio-adsorbent, Rice Husk, Groundnut Shell, Water Treatment, Fluoride Removal

I. INTRODUCTION

Fluoride is a naturally occurring element commonly present in groundwater. At low concentrations it helps prevent dental cavities, but excessive intake can lead to dental and skeletal fluorosis. According to the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) and the World Health Organization (WHO), the permissible limit of fluoride in drinking water is approximately 1–1.5 mg/L. Many regions in India experience groundwater contamination due to geological processes. Traditional treatment methods are often expensive and unsuitable for rural communities. Agricultural wastes such as rice husk and groundnut shells possess porous structures and functional groups capable of adsorbing fluoride ions from water, making them suitable natural adsorbents.

II. OBJECTIVES

1. To develop an eco-friendly and low-cost product for defluoridation of drinking water.
2. To utilize agricultural waste materials such as rice husk and groundnut shells for water purification.
3. To analyze changes in water quality parameters including pH, turbidity, hardness, and fluoride concentration.
4. To design a simple method suitable for rural and household water purification systems.

III. MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENTS

The materials used include rice husk and groundnut shells as natural adsorbents. Laboratory instruments such as hot air oven, mechanical grinder, sieve set, analytical balance, pH meter, conductivity meter, turbidity meter, spectrophotometer, and thermometer were used for preparation and testing.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology includes preparation of adsorbent, collection of water samples, water quality testing, treatment using the developed adsorbent, and result analysis. Rice husk and groundnut shells were washed, dried, carbonized, ground, and mixed in a 1:1 ratio to produce the final adsorbent material.

V. WATER TESTING AND EXPERIMENT

Water samples were collected from different locations and tested for parameters such as pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity, hardness, chloride, and fluoride concentration. The fluoride concentration was measured using a spectrophotometer. Adsorbent dosages from 0.1 g to 0.5 g were added to 100 mL water samples to evaluate fluoride removal efficiency.

VI. RESULTS

The experiment showed that increasing adsorbent dosage improved fluoride removal efficiency. The highest removal efficiency obtained was approximately 58.3%, reducing fluoride concentration from 1.08 mg/L to 0.45 mg/L.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The adsorption performance can be improved through chemical activation of materials. The method can also be extended to remove other contaminants such as iron and heavy metals. In the future, the adsorbent can be developed into filter cartridges or household filtration systems for rural water purification.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The developed bio-adsorbent made from rice husk and groundnut shells provides a low-cost, eco-friendly, and sustainable solution for fluoride removal from drinking water. The results demonstrate that agricultural waste materials can effectively be used for water purification, especially in rural areas where conventional treatment systems are not feasible.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Brigatti and S. Guggenheim, "Mica crystal chemistry and the influence of pressure and temperature," *Rev. Mineral Geochem.*, 2002.
- [2] K. Taylor et al., *The Encyclopedia of Food Science, Food Technology and Nutrition*, 1993.
- [3] N. Mobeen and P. Kumar, "Defluoridation techniques: A critical review," *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2017.
- [4] National Health and Medical Research Council, "Endorsement of Fluoridation," *Med J Aust.*, 1963.
- [5] S. Peckham and N. Awofeso, "Water fluoridation: A critical review," *Scientific World Journal*, 2014.

AIVORA

Artificial Intelligence for Vision-based Observation & Real-time Assistance

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Abstract—Visually impaired people often face difficulty in detecting nearby obstacles while walking, especially in unfamiliar surroundings. Traditional assistive tools such as white canes provide only limited obstacle awareness and may fail to detect objects at different positions around the user. This paper presents a wearable obstacle detection and haptic alert system for visually impaired people. The proposed system uses one ultrasonic sensor to detect frontal obstacles and three IR sensors to identify nearby obstacles at different positions. Based on the sensor outputs, a vibration motor is activated to provide haptic feedback, allowing the user to sense obstacles without depending on audio alerts. The system is compact, low-cost, and suitable for real-time use. By combining ultrasonic sensing, IR sensing, and vibration-based feedback, the proposed device enhances safe navigation and improves the independence of visually impaired users.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobility is one of the major challenges faced by visually impaired people in daily life. Safe movement in indoor and outdoor environments requires the ability to detect obstacles quickly and accurately. Although the white cane is widely used as a mobility aid, it has several limitations. It mainly detects obstacles on the ground and may not provide timely awareness of obstacles at different heights or directions.

To overcome these limitations, electronic assistive devices have been developed using different types of sensors. Obstacle detection systems based on ultrasonic sensors and infrared sensors are commonly used because of their simplicity, low cost, and fast response. In addition, wearable systems are more convenient than handheld systems because they allow hands-free operation and improve user comfort.

This paper proposes a **wearable obstacle detection and haptic alert system** that uses **one ultrasonic sensor** and **three IR sensors** to detect obstacles around the user. A **vibration motor** is used to provide haptic feedback whenever an obstacle is detected. The system is designed to be simple, portable, and effective for assisting visually impaired users during movement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several assistive systems have been proposed for visually impaired people using different sensing and feedback mechanisms. Ultrasonic

sensor-based systems are widely used for distance measurement because they can detect obstacles ahead of the user with reasonable accuracy. These systems are effective for frontal detection but may not cover side obstacles efficiently.

IR sensor-based systems are also used in obstacle detection due to their compact size and low cost. They are suitable for detecting nearby objects in short-range applications. However, IR sensors alone may be affected by surface properties and environmental conditions.

Some wearable assistive devices use audio feedback to alert the user. Although audio alerts are helpful, they may interfere with surrounding environmental sounds, which are important for safe movement. To solve this issue, haptic feedback using vibration motors has become a useful alternative. Haptic systems provide silent and immediate feedback without disturbing the user's hearing.

From the literature, it is observed that combining different sensors with vibration-based feedback can improve obstacle detection performance and user convenience. Based on this observation, the proposed system integrates one ultrasonic sensor, three IR sensors, and a vibration motor in a wearable arrangement.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is a wearable electronic aid designed for visually impaired users. It consists of:

- **One ultrasonic sensor**
- **Three IR sensors**
- **Microcontroller**
- **Vibration motor**
- **Power supply**
- **Connecting circuitry**

The **ultrasonic sensor** is placed in the front to measure the distance of obstacles directly ahead of the user. The **three IR sensors** are placed to monitor nearby obstacles at different positions. When any sensor detects an obstacle within its set range, the sensor signal is sent to the microcontroller. The microcontroller processes the signal and activates the **vibration motor** to alert the user.

The wearable design allows the system to be attached to the body, such as on the hand, waist, or chest, making it easy to use in daily life. Since the system uses vibration instead of sound, it avoids interference with ambient environmental audio.

IV. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

A. Ultrasonic Sensor

The ultrasonic sensor is used for distance measurement. It transmits ultrasonic waves and receives the reflected signal from an obstacle. The time taken for the echo to return is used to calculate the distance. This sensor is useful for detecting frontal obstacles before the user reaches them.

B. IR Sensors

Three IR sensors are used for short-range obstacle detection. These sensors detect the presence of nearby objects by sensing reflected infrared rays. They provide quick detection at multiple positions and complement the ultrasonic sensor.

C. Microcontroller

The microcontroller acts as the control unit of the system. It receives input signals from the ultrasonic and IR sensors, processes them, and controls the vibration motor based on the detection condition.

D. Vibration Motor

The vibration motor provides haptic feedback to the user. Whenever an obstacle is detected, the motor vibrates to notify the user. This helps the user respond quickly without requiring audio alerts.

E. Power Supply

The system is powered using a compact battery source, making it suitable for wearable use. A regulated power supply ensures stable operation of the sensors and controller.

V. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The system continuously monitors the surroundings using the ultrasonic and IR sensors. The working principle is as follows:

1. The ultrasonic sensor sends a pulse and measures the distance of frontal obstacles.
2. The three IR sensors detect nearby obstacles in their respective sensing zones.
3. The microcontroller reads all sensor outputs in real time.
4. If any obstacle is detected within the predefined threshold distance, the controller activates the vibration motor.
5. The user senses the vibration and becomes aware of the obstacle.

This process repeats continuously, enabling real-time obstacle detection and alerting.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The implementation of the proposed system follows these steps:

A. Sensor Placement

The ultrasonic sensor is mounted in the front-facing direction. The IR sensors are arranged to cover nearby positions around the user for short-range obstacle detection.

B. Signal Acquisition

The ultrasonic sensor provides distance data, while the IR sensors provide digital or analog detection signals based on the presence of nearby obstacles.

C. Control Logic

The microcontroller is programmed to compare the measured distance and detection conditions with predefined threshold values. If an obstacle is present, it triggers the vibration motor.

D. Haptic Alert

The vibration motor acts as the output unit. The vibration gives the user immediate physical feedback regarding the obstacle.

E. Wearable Integration

All components are integrated into a lightweight wearable unit so that the user can comfortably use it for navigation.

VII. BLOCK DIAGRAM

VIII. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

IX. ADVANTAGES

The proposed system offers several advantages:

- Simple and low-cost design
- Wearable and portable
- Real-time obstacle detection
- Silent alert through haptic feedback
- Does not interfere with surrounding sounds
- Easy to implement and maintain
- Suitable for visually impaired users

X. LIMITATIONS

Although the system is useful, it has some limitations:

- It only detects obstacles and does not identify object type
- IR sensors are limited to short-range detection
- Performance may vary based on obstacle surface properties
- No voice guidance or path planning
- Limited intelligence compared to advanced smart assistive systems

XI. APPLICATIONS

The proposed system can be used in:

- Daily mobility assistance for visually impaired people

- *Indoor navigation support*
- *Outdoor walking assistance*
- *Wearable safety alert systems*
- *Low-cost assistive technology projects*

capitalized," J. Name Stand. Abbrev.,

XII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed system is expected to provide reliable obstacle detection in real time. The ultrasonic sensor effectively detects frontal obstacles at a measurable distance, while the IR sensors provide quick detection of nearby objects. The vibration motor successfully converts sensor detection into haptic feedback, enabling the user to sense obstacles without audio assistance.

The use of multiple sensors improves the detection coverage compared to single-sensor systems. The wearable nature of the system increases convenience and practical usability. Since the design uses simple electronic components, it remains affordable and suitable for assistive applications.

XIII. FUTURE SCOPE

The system can be improved further by adding:

- *Multiple vibration patterns for different obstacle positions*
- *Rechargeable battery management system*
- *Smaller and more compact wearable design*
- *Water-resistant casing*
- *GPS support for navigation*
- *Voice module for optional audio alerts*
- *Additional sensors for better obstacle coverage*

XX. CONCLUSION

*This paper presented a **wearable obstacle detection and haptic alert system for visually impaired people**. The system uses **one ultrasonic sensor** for frontal obstacle detection and **three IR sensors** for nearby obstacle sensing. A **vibration motor** provides haptic feedback to alert the user about obstacles in real time. The proposed design is simple, low-cost, wearable, and effective for improving safe mobility. By avoiding audio dependence and using silent vibration alerts, the system supports better environmental awareness while preserving ambient hearing. This makes the proposed system a practical assistive solution for visually impaired users.*

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Eason, B. Noble, and I. N. Sneddon, "On certain integrals of Lipschitz-Hankel type involving products of Bessel functions," *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. London*, vol. A247, pp. 529–551, Apr. 1955.
- [2] J. Clerk Maxwell, *A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism*, 3rd ed., vol. 2. Oxford, U.K.: Clarendon, 1892, pp. 68–73.
- [3] I. S. Jacobs and C. P. Bean, "Fine particles, thin films and exchange anisotropy," in *Magnetism*, vol. III, G. T. Rado and H. Suhl, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Academic, 1963, pp. 271–350.
- [4] K. Elissa, "Title of paper if known," unpublished.
- [5] R. Nicole, "Title of paper with only first word

Design and Deployment of an Attention U-Net Model for Intracranial Hemorrhage Segmentation

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Abstract—Intracranial Hemorrhage (ICH) is a life-threatening neurological emergency that requires rapid and accurate diagnosis using Computed Tomography (CT) imaging. Although deep learning models have demonstrated strong performance in hemorrhage detection and classification, most implementations remain confined to research environments without practical deployment. This study presents a two-phase framework that integrates an Attention U-Net segmentation model into a standalone desktop application for real-time hemorrhage localization. The system combines medical image preprocessing, deep learning-based segmentation, post-processing refinement, and graphical user interface deployment. By bridging the gap between research models and clinical usability, the proposed system demonstrates the feasibility of translating artificial intelligence into practical diagnostic tools.

Keywords— *Intracranial Hemorrhage, Attention U-Net, Medical Image Segmentation, Computed Tomography (CT), Deep Learning, Desktop Application, Computer-Aided Diagnosis.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Intracranial hemorrhage (ICH) refers to bleeding within brain tissues or surrounding cranial spaces and is associated with high mortality and long-term neurological impairment. Early diagnosis significantly improves patient survival rates. CT imaging remains the gold standard for acute hemorrhage detection due to its rapid acquisition and accessibility.

Deep learning has transformed medical image analysis. Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs) introduced end-to-end pixel-wise segmentation [7]. U-Net [8] became the foundational architecture for biomedical segmentation tasks due to its encoder–decoder structure and skip connections. Attention U-Net [9] further enhanced localization by incorporating attention gates that emphasize clinically relevant regions.

Several deep learning approaches have been explored for ICH detection. A fusion framework combining DenseNet-121 and LSTM was proposed for contextual modelling across CT slices [1]. CNN-based systems trained on large RSNA datasets achieved strong classification performance [2]. Conformal prediction methods improved clinical trust by

calibrating model uncertainty [3]. Voxel Scene Graph approaches introduced 3D relational reasoning for volumetric CT analysis [4]. Weakly supervised segmentation using YOLOv7 and SAM reduced annotation burden [5]. Bayesian optimization has been applied to improve DenseNet-based hemorrhage classification [6].

Despite these advancements, most works focus on classification accuracy rather than deployable segmentation systems. This research contributes by implementing an Attention U-Net segmentation model integrated into a user-friendly desktop application.

II. RELATED WORKS

Deep learning models for medical segmentation have evolved significantly. FCNs [7] and U-Net [8] established the foundation for biomedical image segmentation. Attention-based extensions such as Attention U-Net [9] improved focus on small pathological regions.

PadmaPriya and Brindha [1] introduced a hybrid DenseNet-LSTM framework capturing spatial and sequential information across CT slices. Kaur and Singh [2] leveraged large-scale RSNA datasets for robust hemorrhage classification. Gamble et al. [3] proposed conformal prediction to improve clinical reliability.

Sanner et al. [4] introduced Voxel Scene Graphs for 3D contextual modeling, while Spiegler et al. [5] demonstrated weakly supervised segmentation using YOLOv7 and SAM. DenseNet with Bayesian Optimization further improved classification robustness [6].

Milletari et al. proposed V-Net for volumetric medical segmentation [10], and UNet++ introduced nested skip connections for improved feature fusion [11]. Greenspan et al. [12] and Suzuki [13] provided comprehensive reviews of deep learning in medical imaging. Majumdar et al. [14] demonstrated CNN-based ICH detection, and Kuo et al. [15] introduced PatchFCN for localized hemorrhage identification.

However, limited research addresses real-time desktop deployment of segmentation systems, which forms the primary contribution of this study.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system follows a structured two-phase framework consisting of (i) deep learning model development and (ii) desktop application deployment. The overall system architecture is illustrated in Fig 1, which presents the transition from research-level model training to practical software implementation. A more detailed workflow of both phases is shown in Fig 2, describing the step-by-step pipeline for training and integration.

Fig1: Proposed Methodology Framework

Fig2: Proposed Methodology pipeline

Phase I: Deep Learning Model Training (Research Phase)

As shown in Figure 1 and elaborated in Figure 2, the first phase focuses on developing an accurate hemorrhage segmentation model using CT brain scans.

The process begins with data collection, where CT scan images and corresponding ground truth masks are obtained from a publicly available Kaggle dataset dedicated to head CT hemorrhage analysis [17]. The dataset consists of annotated CT slices along with binary masks indicating hemorrhagic regions. These masks represent expert-annotated hemorrhagic areas used as ground truth for supervised learning. Since CT scans are often stored in DICOM format, they are converted into image arrays suitable for deep learning processing.

Following data acquisition, medical preprocessing is applied to standardize the dataset. This includes intensity normalization, resizing all images to a fixed resolution of 256×256 pixels, and optional noise reduction. In medical CT imaging, windowing techniques are crucial for highlighting soft tissue and hemorrhage regions. Therefore, intensity normalization ensures consistent representation across different scanners and acquisition protocols. All images are scaled to a normalized range to improve training stability.

To improve generalization and reduce overfitting, data augmentation techniques such as rotation, horizontal and vertical flipping, brightness adjustment, and minor intensity perturbations are applied. These transformations simulate real-world variability and increase dataset diversity, enabling the model to learn robust features.

The dataset is then divided into training, validation, and testing subsets to ensure unbiased performance evaluation. A portion of the training data is reserved as a validation set to monitor learning progress and prevent overfitting.

Next, the segmentation model architecture is selected. In this work, Attention U-Net is employed due to its ability to enhance focus on relevant hemorrhagic regions using attention gates. The encoder extracts hierarchical features through successive convolution and pooling operations, while the decoder reconstructs pixel-level segmentation maps using upsampling layers. Skip connections preserve spatial information, and attention modules suppress irrelevant background features while emphasizing hemorrhage regions. The model is trained using a combined Binary Cross-Entropy and Dice loss function, which directly optimizes segmentation overlap between predicted masks and ground truth annotations. Optimization is performed using the Adam optimizer with a controlled learning rate across multiple epochs. Early stopping and learning rate reduction techniques are employed to ensure stable convergence.

After training, model performance is evaluated using Dice coefficient and Intersection over Union (IoU). As illustrated in Figure 2, this evaluation step ensures that the trained model achieves satisfactory segmentation accuracy before deployment. The Attention U-Net achieved Dice scores between 0.85 and 0.92 and IoU scores between 0.75 and 0.85, demonstrating strong segmentation capability.

The output of Phase I is a trained model weight file (.h5), which is then transferred to Phase II for application integration.

Phase II: Desktop Application Integration

The second phase transforms the trained deep learning model into a practical desktop application, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2.

The process begins with designing the graphical user interface (GUI). The interface allows users to upload CT images, perform segmentation, and visualize results. The GUI is developed using Python-based frameworks and is structured to ensure intuitive clinical interaction.

Once the interface is prepared, the trained model weights are loaded into the backend inference engine. This engine performs segmentation predictions during runtime.

When a user uploads a CT image, the application applies the same preprocessing steps used during training, ensuring consistency between training and inference phases. This includes resizing to 256×256 resolution, normalization, and format conversion.

The preprocessed image is then passed through the Attention U-Net model to generate a probability map representing predicted hemorrhage regions. The probability map undergoes post-processing, including thresholding to convert probabilities into binary masks, removal of small false-positive regions, and optional morphological smoothing to refine mask boundaries.

The final segmentation mask is overlaid onto the original CT image to create a visual representation of detected hemorrhage regions. The system provides real-time visualization and allows export of segmentation results for documentation or reporting purposes.

Integration of Research and Deployment

Figure 1 emphasizes the transformation from research (blue section) to clinical application (green section). The transition highlights the movement from model training and evaluation to real-world inference, post-processing, and desktop packaging.

Unlike many studies that focus solely on model accuracy, this work ensures that segmentation performance is translated into a functional executable desktop application (.exe), making the system accessible beyond experimental environments. By integrating a Kaggle-based publicly available dataset with a deployable AI system, the proposed framework demonstrates both research validity and practical applicability.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the proposed Attention U-Net model was evaluated using Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Intersection over Union (IoU), which are standard metrics for medical image segmentation. The model was compared against a baseline U-Net [16] architecture to assess performance improvement due to attention mechanisms.

The experimental results indicate that the Attention U-Net achieved Dice scores ranging between 0.85 and 0.92, demonstrating strong overlap between predicted hemorrhage masks and ground-truth annotations. The corresponding IoU values ranged between 0.75 and 0.85, confirming reliable segmentation consistency across validation samples.

In comparison, the baseline U-Net achieved Dice scores between 0.75 and 0.85, while IoU values ranged between 0.78 and 0.86. Although U-Net produced competitive IoU

values, the Dice coefficient for Attention U-Net consistently outperformed the baseline model, particularly in cases involving irregular and moderate-sized hemorrhage regions. The improved Dice score indicates that attention gates enabled the model to better focus on clinically relevant hemorrhagic areas while suppressing background noise. This was especially beneficial in detecting subtle or scattered hemorrhage patterns where standard U-Net struggled with boundary precision.

Interestingly, while U-Net showed slightly higher upper-bound IoU values in certain samples, its Dice performance was less stable across validation cases. This suggests that Attention U-Net provides more consistent segmentation performance, particularly in challenging regions.

Overall, the integration of attention mechanisms improved localization accuracy and reduced false negatives in small hemorrhage areas.

Desktop Application Deployment

Fig 3: Desktop Application

The trained Attention U-Net model was successfully integrated into a standalone desktop application for real-time hemorrhage segmentation.

Fig. 3 shows the graphical user interface of the developed Brain Hemorrhage Segmentation Tool. The application allows users to upload CT images and visualize the segmentation overlay generated by the model. The left panel displays the original CT image, while the right panel presents the predicted hemorrhage mask overlaid on the scan.

The system performs preprocessing, inference, and post-processing in real time, providing visual feedback along with status confirmation. The segmentation overlay highlights detected hemorrhage regions, demonstrating the practical applicability of the model beyond experimental evaluation.

The successful deployment of the model into a desktop application distinguishes this work from many research-only implementations and validates its translational potential for clinical assistance.

V. FUTURE WORK

Future work may extend the framework to 3D volumetric segmentation inspired by V-Net [10] and scene graph approaches [4]. Incorporating uncertainty estimation methods such as conformal prediction [3] may enhance clinical reliability. Semi-supervised approaches [5] could reduce dependency on pixel-level annotations.

Integration with PACS systems and multimodal fusion (CT + MRI) could further improve diagnostic capability. Optimization for GPU acceleration and lightweight deployment will enhance usability in rural healthcare environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presented a two-phase framework for intracranial hemorrhage segmentation using an Attention U-Net architecture integrated into a standalone desktop application. The model was trained using a publicly available Kaggle head CT hemorrhage dataset and achieved strong segmentation performance, with Dice scores ranging from 0.85 to 0.92 and IoU values between 0.75 and 0.85. Comparative evaluation demonstrated that Attention U-Net outperformed the baseline U-Net model in terms of segmentation overlap and consistency, particularly in detecting irregular and moderate-sized hemorrhage regions. The incorporation of attention gates enabled improved localization by suppressing irrelevant background features and emphasizing clinically significant regions.

Beyond algorithmic performance, the primary contribution of this work lies in translating a research-level segmentation model into a functional desktop application. By integrating preprocessing, inference, post-processing, and visualization within an executable software tool, the proposed system bridges the gap between experimental deep learning research and practical clinical usability. The successful deployment demonstrates the feasibility of developing AI-assisted neuroimaging tools that support rapid and accurate hemorrhage analysis. This framework establishes a foundation for future extensions toward volumetric analysis, uncertainty estimation, and integration into real-world clinical workflows.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

REFERENCES

- [1] PadmaPriya S. Babu & T. Brindha, Deep learning fusion model for ICH detection using DenseNet-121 and LSTM, 2021
- [2] S. Kaur & A. Singh, CNN framework for intracranial hemorrhage detection, 2020
- [3] C. Gamble et al., Conformal prediction for clinically trustworthy ICH detection, 2021
- [4] A. Sanner et al., Voxel Scene Graph for ICH detection, 2022
- [5] T. Spiegler et al., Weakly supervised ICH segmentation using YOLOv7 and SAM, 2023
- [6] Anonymous Authors, DenseNet-121 with Bayesian Optimization for ICH classification, 2021
- [7] J. Long et al., Fully Convolutional Networks for Semantic Segmentation, CVPR, 2015.
- [8] O. Ronneberger et al., U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation, MICCAI, 2015.
- [9] O. Oktay et al., Attention U-Net: Learning Where to Look, 2018.
- [10] F. Milletari et al., V-Net: Fully Convolutional Neural Networks for Volumetric Medical Image Segmentation, 2016.
- [11] Z. Zhou et al., UNet++: A Nested U-Net Architecture for Medical Image Segmentation, 2018.
- [12] H. Greenspan et al., Deep Learning in Medical Imaging: Overview and Future Promise, IEEE TMI, 2016.
- [13] S. Suzuki, Overview of Deep Learning in Medical Imaging, Radiological Physics and Technology, 2017.
- [14] A. Majumdar et al., Detecting Intracranial Hemorrhage with Deep Learning, IEEE EMBC, 2018.
- [15] W. Kuo et al., PatchFCN for Intracranial Hemorrhage Detection, 2018.
- [16] A. N. Md Sakib, N. Anjum and S. M. M. Ahsan, "Segmentation of Hemorrhagic Areas in Human Brain from CT Scan Images," 2022 4th International Conference on Sustainable Technologies for Industry 4.0 (STI), Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2022, pp. 1-5, IEEE
- [17] F. Kitamura, "Head CT Hemorrhage Dataset," Kaggle, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/felipekitamura/head-ct-hemorrhage>

RAINFALL INTELLIGENCE: MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES FOR FORECASTING AND ANOMALOUS PATTERN DETECTION

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Abstract—This project focuses on building a system for regional climate analysis, specifically targeting rainfall prediction and anomaly detection. We use a random forest algorithm on historical weather datasets to categorize rainfall intensity (low, medium, or high) and spot unusual weather patterns. This helps in identifying both long-term climate shifts and sudden deviations, which is highly useful for disaster management and environmental planning. The software relies on a Python backend with libraries like pandas, NumPy, scikit-learn, and Matplotlib handling the data processing and machine learning. We also decoupled the architecture, using React for the frontend to create interactive dashboards that make monitoring these weather patterns straightforward for users. Overall, our results show the system effectively predicts rainfall categories and flags anomalies across different timeframes.

Index Terms—Rainfall Prediction, Machine Learning, Random Forest, Anomaly Detection, React, Flask.

I. INTRODUCTION

Predicting rainfall accurately is a massive priority for agriculture, water management, and general public safety. It's a notoriously difficult problem because so many different climate variables impact the weather. Machine learning gives us a way to analyze huge amounts of historical meteorological data and find hidden patterns that traditional forecasting might miss [1]. Ultimately, better predictions mean better preparation.

When we looked at existing forecasting frameworks, we noticed a few major drawbacks:

- Most systems lack real-time anomaly detection, meaning they don't integrate multi-temporal data well.
- Current models often stick to simple binary classification (is it going to rain, yes or no?) rather than predicting the actual intensity.
- They struggle to adapt to specific regional geographies.
- There's a big gap when it comes to fusing historical datasets with live, real-time weather data.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

We reviewed several existing approaches to see how other teams handle weather forecasting. A. T. Williams et al. [2] built a multi-SARIMA model to break down time series data into trends and seasonal patterns. It works well and outperforms standard SARIMA, but it relies heavily on having the perfect dataset and requires a lot of manual parameter tuning.

A. Ali et al. [4] took a different route, applying Naive Bayes to predict rain. While they hit 100% accuracy in some specific test cases and it works well with limited data, Naive Bayes generally struggles to map out the more complex, non-linear relationships found in weather patterns.

Other teams have tried hybrid approaches. A. E. Abdishakur et al. [3] combined LSTM and GBM models. This definitely bumps up the accuracy and is great for disaster management, but it makes the system computationally heavy and much harder to maintain. Transfer learning using CNNs is another option we looked at, as it reduces the need for massive labeled datasets. The issue there is the risk of negative transfer—if the source data and target data are too different, the model's performance drops significantly.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

To bypass the limitations of basic binary predictions and avoid the heavy processing costs of deep learning, we built a dual-component engine based on Random Forest.

Our system does two main things:

- **Real-Time Data Collection:** We run a Flask backend that pulls live temperature, humidity, and wind speed via an API.
- **Forecasting and Anomaly Detection:** The Random Forest model processes this data to predict future conditions and immediately flags any anomalies to reduce warning delays.

We chose Random Forest because it gives us high accuracy with single-cycle training, meaning we don't have to waste computing power running through complex, multi-epoch training phases.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Architecture

Our architecture is designed as a sequential pipeline to merge historical data with live inputs seamlessly.

1. **Data Ingestion:** We start with a base of Historical Datasets which undergo feature engineering to create Pre-processed Data. Simultaneously, the OpenWeatherMAP API fetches Current weather data.
2. **Prediction Phase:** Both the Preprocessed Data and the live Current weather data are fed into the Rainfall Prediction Model.
3. **Anomaly Detection Phase:** Instead of running independently, the Anomaly Detection Model takes the *Prediction Results* generated by the first model, combining them with the Preprocessed Data to identify irregularities.
4. **Evaluation and Output:** The outputs from both models are routed through a Model Evaluation block. Finally, the evaluated data is pushed to the Visualization and Reporting interface

Fig. 2. System Architecture — Rainfall Intelligence Platform

B. Dashboard and Interface

For the user interface, we built an AI Weather Anomaly Intensity Detector. If a user searches for a city like Trivandrum, they get a live monitor showing a 5-Hour Forecast Trend graph (tracking temperature and humidity). We also built an Anomaly Logs panel that categorizes current conditions as No Anomaly, Normal Intensity, or Low Intensity Anomaly. Instead of just saying Rain, the radar visualization breaks it down into Light, Moderate, and Heavy.

C. Implementation Details

- **Frontend:** We used React to build the frontend. It makes the UI highly interactive and handles the state manage-

ment needed to update the forecast graphs and anomaly alerts in real time without refreshing the page.

- **Backend:** The core logic runs on a Flask server. Flask acts as the bridge, taking API requests from the React frontend, pushing the data through our scikit-learn Random Forest models, and returning the predictions.

V. RESULTS

The most significant result is that we successfully moved away from simple binary (rain/no rain) predictions. Our model actively classifies rainfall intensity into Low, Medium, and High categories. Integrating the OpenWeatherMap API means we are no longer reliant entirely on static historical data.

Overall, the model hit an 83.5% accuracy rate. Our performance diagnostics showed a Precision of 75.0%, a Recall of 37.5%, and a Temperature MAE of 29.4.

When we look at the specific confusion matrices, things get interesting:

- **Model A (Rain Anomaly Detection):** The model is very good at identifying normal weather. It correctly classified 55 No Rain events with only 2 false positives. It correctly caught 6 actual rain events, but it misclassified 10 rain events as No Rain. This explains our lower recall score and shows that sudden anomalies are still tricky to catch.
- **Model B (Intensity Classification):** For intensity, the model is highly accurate when there is no rain (56 correct predictions). However, the boundary between Low and Normal intensity is a bit blurred for the algorithm, as it misclassified a handful of these lighter events as None.

VI. CONCLUSION

We successfully built a Dual-Component Engine that handles both live weather classification and future trend forecasting. By hooking the system up to the OpenWeatherMap API, we brought real-time data into the mix. Ultimately, the Random Forest model gave us a solid 83.5% accuracy with very low processing overhead, and we successfully achieved granular, multi-class intensity outputs.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

There are a few clear ways to improve this system down the road:

- We want to integrate actual satellite and radar imagery to make the regional intelligence much sharper.
- Adding physics-aware logic to calculate things like soil saturation would make the predictions more realistic.
- We plan to expand the API connections so the model works well across wildly different terrains.
- Finally, we want to train the system on datasets from different global regions to see if that improves local accuracy.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. M. Hassan, M. A. T. Rony, M. A. R. Khan, M. M. Hassan, F. Yasmin, A. Nag, T. H. Zarin, A. K. Bairagi, S. Alshathri, and W. El-Shafai, Machine Learning-Based Rainfall Prediction: Unveiling Insights and Forecasting for Improved Preparedness, *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 132196–132222, 2023.
- [2] A. T. Williams, R. E. Sperl, and S. M. Chung, Anomaly Detection in Multi-Seasonal Time-Series Data, 2023.

- [3] A. E. Abdishakur, A. M. Tahlil, and A. A. Aden, Hybrid Machine Learning Model for Rainfall Prediction Using Time-Series Data, 2025.
- [4] A. Ali, A. Khairan, F. Tempola, and A. Fuad, Application of Naïve Bayes to Predict the Potential of Rain in Temate City, 2021.

An AI-Driven Real-Time Environmental Health Monitoring System

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Abstract— Rapid urbanization and climate change have significantly increased exposure to environmental health risks such as elevated particulate matter, poor air quality, and extreme temperatures. BioClima is a full-stack, AI-powered environmental health monitoring platform designed to transform raw environmental sensor data into personalized, real-time health guidance. The system integrates a Raspberry Pi 4-based IoT network consisting of DHT11 (temperature and humidity), MQ-135 (CO₂), MQ-8 (hydrogen gas), and PM2.5 particulate sensors, connected to a cloud-enabled Python Fast API backend and a responsive React dashboard. Sensor data is sampled every five seconds and transmitted via a structured REST API to a central server, where multiple AI modules operate concurrently. At the core of BioClima's intelligence is a Smart-Weighted Averaging (SWA) algorithm that computes a personalized environmental risk score (0–100). The score incorporates real-time sensor values along with user-specific health parameters such as age, asthma, skin sensitivity, and a configurable sensitivity factor. This risk estimate is further enhanced by a machine learning health predictor trained on historical environmental data. BioClima also includes a Predictive Scenario Simulator that models the impact of practical interventions such as opening windows, activating a HEPA air purifier, or increasing hydration before implementation. The system delivers ranked recommendations with quantified projected risk reductions. Additionally, a Q Learning reinforcement learning feedback loop adapts recommendations over time based on user ratings. The frontend provides interactive 24-hour, 7-day, and 30-day analytics for temperature, AQI, and risk scores, alongside an admin broadcast alert system. BioClima presents a scalable, modular framework for community-level environmental health monitoring in smart cities, schools, hospitals, and vulnerable populations.

Keywords— Environmental Health Monitoring, IoT, Air Quality, Reinforcement Learning, Predictive Simulation, Personalized AI, Smart Systems, Real-Time Analytics

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era of escalating environmental challenges rising temperatures, deteriorating air quality, and increasing ultraviolet radiation individuals face growing health risks that

are often invisible and poorly understood. Vulnerable populations, including those with respiratory conditions like asthma, cardiovascular diseases, and skin sensitivities, are disproportionately affected by fluctuating environmental conditions. Despite the abundance of generic weather and air quality data, there remains a critical gap in translating raw environmental measurements into actionable, personalized health guidance tailored to an individual's unique medical profile.

BioClima AI addresses this gap by delivering a personalized environmental health intelligence platform that bridges the divide between real-time sensor data and individualized health risk assessment. Designed for deployment on a Raspberry Pi 4, the system integrates an array of environmental sensors including the DHT11 for temperature and humidity, the MQ-135 for air quality and CO₂ levels, the MQ-8 for hydrogen gas detection, and a PM2.5 particulate matter sensor to continuously monitor ambient conditions. These raw readings are ingested into a robust Fast API backend, where a custom Smart Weighted Averaging algorithm computes a composite environmental health score by evaluating multiple parameters against established safety thresholds.

What distinguishes BioClima from conventional monitoring solutions is its AI-driven personalization engine. The platform maintains detailed user health profiles encompassing age, BMI, pre-existing medical conditions, medication usage, activity levels, and lifestyle factors such as smoking status and daily outdoor exposure. Advanced machine learning models, including a Health Twin simulator, a reinforcement learning feedback loop, and an intervention recommendation engine, work in concert to generate dynamic, context-aware health advisories. These advisories are not static warnings but evolve based on trend analysis, predictive modelling, and continuous learning from user feedback.

The frontend, built with React and Vite, presents this intelligence through an intuitive, visually rich dashboard featuring real-time sensor gauges, historical trend analytics, and personalized risk indicators. An administrative module enables broadcast alerts during critical environmental events, while optional Firebase cloud synchronization supports remote monitoring and data aggregation across multiple deployment locations. BioClima AI represents a convergence of IoT sensing, artificial intelligence, and preventive healthcare empowering individuals to make informed decisions about

their daily activities based on how their unique health profile interacts with their immediate environment.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

F.A. Samiul Islam [1] proposed an AI-based environmental monitoring framework that uses satellite imagery, IoT sensors, predictive modelling, and data analytics to monitor air and water quality, predict disasters, protect wildlife, and support sustainable development through intelligent, data-driven environmental management solutions.

Jesus Rosa-Bilbao et al. [2], proposed an IoT-based indoor air quality management system integrating self-manufactured sensor nodes, complex event processing, machine/deep learning (LSTM and decision tree), and blockchain to monitor, predict, and securely manage IAQ conditions in intelligent educational environments.

Asst. Prof. V. HariKrishna et al. [3] proposed a Raspberry Pi-based Smart Environment Monitoring System that tracks temperature, humidity, CO, smoke, LPG, and noise using DHT11, MQ7, MQ135, and LM393 sensors, providing LCD display alerts, buzzer indications, and GSM-based SMS notifications when thresholds are exceeded.

Jhansi Bharathi Madavarapu et al. [4] proposed an IoT-based wearable health monitoring system named HOT Watch that tracks ECG, body temperature, and oxygen levels using MLX90614, AD8232, and MAX30100 sensors, applying the Pan-Tompkins algorithm for heart rate detection and delivering real-time alerts via a mobile application.

Emran Alotaibi and Nadia Nassif [5] conducted a comprehensive bibliometric and in-depth analysis of 4,762 publications, highlighting AI/ML applications in air and water quality monitoring, climate modelling, biodiversity assessment, disaster management, IoT integration, and explainable AI for sustainable environmental management.

Kalyan Chatterjee et al. [6] proposed an AI-driven predictive indoor air quality model named “Indoor Air Wellness,” integrating Kalman Filtering and Artificial Neural Networks (Kal-ANN) to forecast pollutants, optimize pollution control, and enhance energy efficiency in green buildings with 96.55% predictive accuracy.

Taufiqur Rahaman [7] proposed Smart Environmental Monitoring Systems integrating IoT sensors, AI/ML analytics, cloud and edge computing, and blockchain to enable real-time air and water quality monitoring, predictive pollution modelling, regulatory compliance, and sustainable environmental governance through case-based analysis.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

BioClima AI is a personalized environmental health monitoring system deployed on a Raspberry Pi 4. The hardware layer integrates DHT11, MQ-135, MQ-8, and PM2.5 sensors to continuously capture temperature, humidity, air quality, CO₂, and particulate matter readings. Sensor data is transmitted to a Fast API backend, which validates inputs, computes a

composite Smart Weighted Averaging (SWA) score, and stores readings in an SQLite database. AI modules including a Health Twin, ML predictor, reinforcement learning feedback loop, and intervention engine analyse environmental trends against individual health profiles to generate personalized risk assessments and recommendations. The React frontend renders real-time dashboards, historical analytics, and adaptive health advisories. An admin module supports broadcast alerts, while optional Firebase integration enables cloud synchronization for remote monitoring across multiple locations.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: BioClima AI system architecture

Figure 1 illustrates The BioClima AI architecture comprises five interconnected layers. Environmental sensors (DHT11, MQ-135, MQ-8, PM2.5) interface with a Raspberry Pi 4, which transmits readings to the Fast API backend. The backend performs data validation, SWA score computation, and JWT-secured user management via SQLite. An AI engine featuring a Health Twin, ML predictor, and intervention engine generates personalized advisories. The React frontend displays real-time dashboards, while Firebase enables optional cloud synchronization.

C. Modules

- Sensor Data Acquisition Module

Interfaces with environmental sensors (DHT11, MQ-135, MQ-8, PM2.5) connected to a Raspberry Pi 4 to continuously collect real-time readings for temperature, humidity, air quality, CO₂, hydrogen gas, and particulate matter, with built-in data validation and error handling.

- User Authentication and Profile Module

Manages user registration, JWT-based login, and role-based access control (User/Admin). Maintains detailed health profiles including age, BMI, medical conditions, medications, activity level, and lifestyle factors to enable personalized risk assessments.

supporting seamless migration to Firebase Real-time Database integration for remote monitoring.

V. RESULTS

The BioClima AI system was successfully developed and tested on a Raspberry Pi 4, demonstrating real-time environmental monitoring with sensor data collection at five-minute intervals. The SWA algorithm accurately computed composite health scores by integrating temperature, humidity, PM2.5, CO₂, and H₂ readings. Personalized risk assessments showed meaningful variation across user profiles, users with respiratory conditions received sensitivity-adjusted scores up to 1.45× higher than baseline users. The AI modules, including the Health Digital Twin and ML predictor, generated context-aware health advisories. The React dashboard rendered live data with sub-second response times, while Firebase cloud synchronization enabled remote access with aggregated, anonymized data uploads every 30 minutes.

VI. CONCLUSION

BioClima AI successfully demonstrates the convergence of IoT sensing, artificial intelligence, and preventive healthcare into a unified, affordable platform. By considering real-time environmental data from multiple sensors with individualized health profiles, the system transforms raw measurements into personalized, actionable health guidance. Deployed on a Raspberry Pi 4, BioClima offers a scalable, cost-effective solution that empowers users to proactively safeguard their well-being against environmental health risks. Watch: IoT-Based Wearable Health Monitoring System” ,2024.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

Future enhancements include integrating wearable devices (smartwatches, SpO₂ sensors) for real-time physiological correlation, deploying multi-node sensor mesh networks for community-level environmental mapping, and implementing deep learning models for 24-48 hour risk forecasting. Additional goals include multilingual voice-based advisories, healthcare EHR integration, geospatial pollution heatmaps, and smart city dashboard partnerships for public health policy support.

REFERENCES

- [1] F.A. Samiul Islam, “The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Environmental Monitoring for Sustainable Development and Future Perspectives”,2025.
- [2] Jesús Rosa-Bilbao; David Merkl; Matthias F. Wagner; Juan Boubeta-Puig, “IoT-Based Indoor Air Quality Management System for Intelligent Education Environments”, 2025.
- [3] Asst. Prof. V. HariKrishna; D. Harshita; P. Likitha; P. Chandu; N. RamRishik, “Smart Environment Monitoring System”,2024.
- [4] Jhansi Bharathi Madavarapu; S. Nachiyappan; S. Rajarajeswari; N. Anusha; Nirmala Venkatachalam;

Rahul Charan Bose Madavarapu; A. Ahilan. “HOT Watch: IoT-Based Wearable Health Monitoring System” ,2024.

[5] Emran Alotaibi; Nadia Nassif; “Artificial intelligence in environment monitoring: in-depth Analysis”,2024.

[6] Kalyan Chatterjee; Muntha Raju1; Bhoomeshwar Balal; U. Nikitha1; Gampala Prabhas; Naim Ahmad; Aymanqahmash, Wade Ghribi; Bernardolemos and Saurav Mallik; “Indoor Air Wellness: A Predictive Model for pollution control using Advanced AI Techniques”,2025.

[7] Taufiqur Rahaman; “Smart Environmental Monitoring Systems for Air and Water Quality Management” ,2025.

Voice assistive vision glass

Real-Time Obstacle Detection and Intelligent Navigation Assistance

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Abstract— *Visual impairment significantly limits independent mobility and safe navigation in daily life. Traditional mobility aids such as white canes provide limited obstacle detection and do not offer real-time environmental awareness. This paper presents the design and development of a Voice Assistive Vision Glass system that enables real-time obstacle detection using ultrasonic sensing technology and provides immediate audio feedback to the user. The proposed system is lightweight, wearable, cost-effective, and designed for indoor and semi-outdoor environments. The system continuously measures obstacle distance, processes sensor data using a microcontroller, and generates voice alerts when obstacles are detected within a predefined threshold. Experimental evaluation demonstrates reliable performance with minimal response delay. The system enhances user independence and improves safety through intelligent assistive technology.*

Keywords—*Assistive technology; Obstacle detection; Ultrasonic sensor; Wearable system; Voice feedback; Embedded system.*

I. INTRODUCTION

According to global health statistics, millions of individuals worldwide suffer from partial or complete visual impairment. Navigation in unfamiliar environments remains one of the most significant challenges faced by visually impaired individuals. Safe mobility is essential for independence, education, employment, and social interaction.

Traditional assistive devices such as white canes detect obstacles only upon physical contact and offer limited range

detection. Guide dogs provide effective support but involve high maintenance costs and limited accessibility. Modern smart assistive systems based on camera vision and artificial intelligence exist; however, they are often expensive, complex, and computationally intensive.

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a Voice Assistive Vision Glass system that provides real-time obstacle detection and immediate voice guidance using a compact wearable design. The proposed system focuses on affordability, simplicity, and user comfort while maintaining effective obstacle detection performance.

II. RELATED WORK

Several research works have been conducted in the area of assistive navigation systems. Camera-based systems utilize image processing and deep learning algorithms for object recognition. While these systems offer advanced detection capabilities, they require high computational power and are sensitive to lighting conditions.

LiDAR-based systems provide high precision distance measurement but significantly increase system cost. Some wearable devices use vibration alerts for obstacle warning; however, vibration signals may not provide sufficient directional information or clarity in noisy environments.

In contrast, ultrasonic sensor-based systems are cost-effective, reliable, and suitable for short to medium-range obstacle detection. The proposed system combines ultrasonic sensing with real-time voice feedback, improving usability and response clarity.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Before beginning hardware implementation, the system design was first developed as a structured concept document. The sensing logic, processing algorithm, and output strategy were defined clearly before circuit integration. Hardware and software modules were planned separately to ensure smooth system integration.

Proper documentation and design validation were completed prior to final assembly. All hardware connections and program logic were tested in simulation and prototype stages before final deployment.

A. Abbreviations and Acronyms

All abbreviations and acronyms used in this paper are defined at their first occurrence.

The main abbreviations include:

- VAVG – Voice Assistive Vision Glass
- MCU – Microcontroller Unit
- GPS – Global Positioning System
- AI – Artificial Intelligence

B. Units

All measurements in this system follow the International System of Units (SI).

- Distance is measured in centimeters (cm) and meters (m).
- Time is measured in seconds (s).
- Frequency of ultrasonic waves is measured in kilohertz (kHz).
- Voltage and current are measured in volts (V) and amperes (A).

Unit consistency is maintained throughout the system design to avoid dimensional errors in calculations.

C. Architecture

The system consists of three primary modules:

- Sensing Module
- Processing Module
- Output Module

The sensing module includes ultrasonic sensors mounted on the spectacle frame to detect obstacles in the user's path. The processing module consists of a microcontroller responsible for distance calculation and decision-making based on predefined safety thresholds. It continuously analyzes the sensor data to determine the proximity of obstacles in real time. The output module generates voice alerts through earphones or a small

speaker, providing immediate and clear feedback to the user. The coordinated functioning of these modules ensures reliable obstacle detection and timely assistance during navigation.

IV. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

The hardware section of the proposed system includes the sensing unit, processing unit, audio output unit, and power supply. Each component is selected based on reliability, low cost, and real-time performance requirements.

A. Ultrasonic Sensor

The ultrasonic sensor is used for obstacle detection. It operates at a frequency of 40 kHz and measures distances typically between 2 cm and 400 cm using the time-of-flight principle.

The sensor emits ultrasonic waves and receives the reflected echo signal from obstacles. The distance is calculated based on the echo return time.

The sensor is selected due to its low cost, ease of interfacing, low power consumption, and ability to function independently of lighting conditions.

B. Microcontroller

The microcontroller acts as the central processing unit of the system. It triggers the ultrasonic sensor, measures the echo duration, calculates the distance, and compares it with a predefined threshold value.

If the measured distance is below the safety limit, the controller activates the audio alert module. The system is programmed using embedded C to ensure real-time processing and minimal delay.

C. Audio Output Module

The audio module provides voice-based alerts to the user when obstacles are detected. Pre-recorded messages such as "Obstacle Ahead" and "Object Very Close" are used to indicate proximity levels.

Audio feedback is preferred over vibration alerts as it provides clearer and more informative guidance to visually impaired users.

D. Power Supply

The system is powered using a rechargeable lithium-ion battery. A regulated supply ensures stable voltage for all components. The low power design improves portability and extends operating time.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed system can be further enhanced by integrating a camera module for object classification and implementing

Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based object recognition to improve environmental awareness. The addition of a Global Positioning System (GPS) module can support outdoor navigation assistance and route guidance. Machine learning algorithms may be incorporated to enable adaptive obstacle detection based on user behavior and environmental conditions. Furthermore, smartphone connectivity can be introduced to provide emergency alerts and real-time location sharing. These enhancements can significantly improve the functionality of the system and transform it into a comprehensive intelligent navigation assistant for visually impaired individuals.

VI. CONCLUSION

The **Voice Assistive Vision Glass** system provides an efficient, affordable, and practical assistive solution for visually impaired individuals. The primary objective of the system is to enhance the mobility and independence of visually challenged users by helping them detect obstacles in their surroundings. By integrating **ultrasonic sensing technology**, the system is capable of identifying obstacles at different distances in real time. When an obstacle is detected, the system provides **instant voice alerts**, allowing the user to take immediate action and avoid potential collisions.

The wearable design of the device in the form of a **lightweight smart glass** ensures user comfort and ease of use in daily life. Unlike traditional mobility aids that may require continuous physical interaction, this system operates automatically and provides guidance through audio feedback. This makes navigation more convenient and reduces the physical effort required by the user.

Another important advantage of the proposed system is its **low cost and simplicity**, which makes it accessible to a larger population of visually impaired individuals. The use of widely available electronic components also makes the system easy to develop, maintain, and upgrade.

In the future, the system can be further improved by integrating **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** for object recognition, **GPS modules for location tracking and navigation**, and **smartphone connectivity** for enhanced user interaction. These advancements can transform the system into a more intelligent assistive device capable of providing comprehensive environmental awareness.

Overall, the Voice Assistive Vision Glass has strong potential for **real-world implementation and commercialization**, contributing significantly to improving the safety, independence, and quality of life of visually impaired individuals.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Ikram, I. S. Bajwa, A. Ikram, I. De La Torre Díez, C. E. Uc Ríos, and Á. K. Castilla, "Obstacle detection and warning system for the visually impaired using IoT sensors," *IEEE Access*, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3250196. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3250196>
- [2] K. Guravaiah and T. Ramesh, "Third eye: Object recognition and speech generation for visually impaired," *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJET)*, vol. 9, no. 3, 2022. Available: <https://www.ijert.org/third-eye-object-recognition-and-speech-generation-for-visually-impaired>
- [3] B. Kuriakose and R. Raj, "DeepNAVI: A deep learning-based smartphone navigation assistant for the visually impaired," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET)*, 2022. Available: <https://ijarcet.org/deepnavi-a-deep-learning-based-smartphone-navigation-assistant>
- [4] P. Hedge and C. S., "Smart glasses for visually disabled person using IoT," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, vol. 8, no. 7, 2021. Available: <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V8/i7/IRJET-V8I725.pdf>
- [5] M. Young, *The Technical Writer's Handbook*. Mill Valley, CA: University Science, 1989. <https://archive.org/details/technicalwriters00youun>
- [1] S. Ikram, I. S. Bajwa, A. Ikram, I. De La Torre Díez, C. E. Uc Ríos, and Á. K. Castilla, "Obstacle detection and

CurrencyXplain for the Visually Impaired Using Deep Learning

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Abstract-The rise of counterfeit currency poses a serious threat to both economic stability and individual financial security. Current detection methods are often inaccessible to vulnerable groups such as the elderly and visually impaired. To overcome these limitations, this project presents “Currencyxplain for the Visually Impaired Using Deep Learning” a real-time mobile application that leverages artificial intelligence to instantly identify fake Indian currency notes. Using an optimized YOLOv11 deep learning model integrated with TensorFlow Lite, the system can detect and verify all major Indian denominations from ₹10 to ₹500 directly through a smartphone camera. The app, built with Flutter and powered by OpenCV for live video processing, delivers immediate results with clear visual indicators and real-time voice feedback, ensuring usability for the visually impaired. A standout feature is the built-in Elderly Helper Mode, which not only simplifies the interface with large buttons and clear instructions but also automatically triggers an emergency call or alert to a trusted contact if multiple counterfeit notes are detected in a row offering an extra layer of safety for senior users. Additional functionalities include multi-note detection, automatic value calculation, audio feedback and seamless cross-platform operation. This project delivers a practical and inclusive solution that empowers all

individuals, especially the elderly and visually impaired, to conduct transactions with confidence and independence.

Keywords- YOLOv11, Fake Currency Detection, Visually Impaired, Elderly Helper Mode, TensorFlow Lite.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currency recognition and authentication remain fundamental challenges for visually impaired individuals in their daily lives. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 2.2 billion people worldwide have vision impairment, with 36 million classified as blind. These individuals face considerable difficulties in identifying banknote denominations and verifying their authenticity during financial transactions, making them disproportionately vulnerable to counterfeit currency fraud .

Traditional assistive solutions have included tactile markings, currency readers, and specialized mobile applications. However, many existing solutions are limited in their capabilities, often requiring specialized hardware, lacking real-time processing, or failing to address the critical aspect of fake currency detection alongside denomination recognition. The proliferation of counterfeit currency in circulation further

compounds this problem, necessitating robust authentication mechanisms accessible to visually impaired users.

Recent advances in deep learning, particularly in object detection architectures, have opened new possibilities for assistive technology applications. The YOLO (You Only Look Once) family of models has demonstrated exceptional performance in real-time object detection tasks, making them particularly suitable for mobile deployment scenarios where low latency is crucial. YOLOv11, the latest iteration in this series, offers an optimal balance between detection accuracy and computational efficiency, enabling sophisticated computer vision applications on resource-constrained mobile devices.

This paper presents CurrencyXplain, a comprehensive solution that addresses the dual challenges of currency denomination identification and authenticity verification through a unified deep learning approach. The key contributions of this work include:

- Development of a YOLOv11-based model capable of simultaneously detecting currency denominations and classifying notes as real or fake, trained on a diverse dataset of 3,515 images capturing real-world variations in lighting, angle, and contrast.
- Conversion of the trained model to TensorFlow Lite format for efficient on-device inference, ensuring user privacy by eliminating the need for cloud-based processing and enabling operation without internet connectivity.
- Implementation of a Flutter-based mobile application with accessibility-first design principles, featuring large touch targets, high-contrast visual elements, and comprehensive English voice output with adjustable speech rate and volume controls.
- Integration of multi-modal feedback mechanisms including text-to-speech announcements for detected denominations, authenticity status, confidence scores, and cumulative totals, complemented by haptic feedback for non-visual confirmation.
- Development of an Elderly Help Mode incorporating emergency communication features through gesture-based triggers (double-tap, long-press, shake) for one-touch calling of predefined contacts.
- Support for simultaneous detection of multiple currency notes with automatic counting and summation of total monetary value, providing comprehensive transaction assistance.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work in assistive currency recognition systems. Section III details the system architecture and design considerations. Section IV describes the dataset creation methodology and training process. Section V presents the mobile application implementation. Section VI discusses experimental results and performance evaluation. Section VII concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Deep learning-based approaches have been extensively explored for currency detection and authentication tasks in recent years. Pham et al. developed a deep learning-based fake banknote detection method using visible-light images captured by smartphone cameras, specifically designed for visually impaired users. Their approach utilized convolutional neural networks to classify genuine and fake banknotes of US dollar, Euro, Korean won, and Jordanian dinar currencies. Using a self-collected dataset and four-fold cross-validation, they achieved high classification accuracy with various CNN architectures including AlexNet, ResNet-18, and GoogleNet, demonstrating the feasibility of using standard smartphone cameras for counterfeit detection without specialized sensors.

Jaman et al. developed a CNN-based approach for Bangladeshi currency detection, utilizing a dataset of 50,334 images across 10 denominations. Their model achieved 98.5% accuracy and was converted to TensorFlow Lite format for mobile deployment, demonstrating the effectiveness of deep learning for regional currency recognition systems and establishing a methodology for on-device inference that informs our approach.

Pachón et al. conducted a comprehensive comparison of custom CNN models versus transfer learning approaches for fake banknote recognition using Colombian currency. Their study evaluated sequential, residual, and Inception architectures, identifying that ResNet18 achieved 100% accuracy while their proposed custom model delivered significantly faster inference times up to 6.48 times faster on CPU and 16.29 times faster on GPU. This research highlighted the critical trade-off between accuracy and inference speed for real-time applications and informed our selection of YOLOv11-nano for mobile deployment.

Bhushanm et al. presented a comparative analysis of Simple Neural Network and Convolutional Neural Network approaches specifically for Indian 500 rupee note counterfeit detection. Their results demonstrated the superiority of CNN-based methods, achieving 100% accuracy compared to 97.7% for simple neural networks, with superior precision, recall, and F1-scores. This work established the effectiveness of deep learning for Indian currency authentication and provided a benchmark for our system's performance on Indian denominations.

Choudhary et al. conducted an extensive literature survey on CNN-based approaches for Indian rupee note counterfeit detection, reviewing multiple studies that employed various architectures including VGG16, AlexNet, and MobileNet, with reported accuracies ranging from 92% to 98%. Their survey identified key security features including security threads, RBI logos, and identifying marks that are essential for accurate counterfeit detection.

Nair et al. developed Verinote, a fake currency detection system using CNN architecture integrated with TensorFlow and OpenCV. Their system achieved 92.75% accuracy with 93.6% precision, demonstrating the practical applicability of deep learning for real-world counterfeit detection systems and establishing a foundation for mobile-based detection approaches.

Khanam and Hussain provided a comprehensive overview of YOLOv11 architectural enhancements, detailing the CSPDarknet backbone, PANet neck for multi-scale feature fusion, and anchor-free detection head that enable efficient real-time object detection on resource-constrained devices. Their work informed our selection of YOLOv11-nano as the optimal

balance between detection accuracy and computational efficiency for mobile deployment.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The proposed system is a smart mobile application designed to assist visually impaired users in currency detection and authentication. It applies YOLOv11 deep learning model to detect and classify currency notes in real-time. The system processes live camera feed, identifies denominations, verifies authenticity, and provides voice output of results. An Elderly Help Mode provides emergency assistance through gesture-based activation.

B. System Architecture

The system architecture consists of five primary layers:

1. **User Device Layer:** Includes hardware components (camera, speaker, haptic engine, microphone) and local storage.
2. **Flutter Application Layer:** Implements the user interface with accessibility-focused design featuring large buttons and high contrast.
3. **Services Layer:** Provides camera management, text-to-speech, detection orchestration, and emergency calling.
4. **Machine Learning Layer:** Handles model loading, inference execution using TensorFlow Lite, and result post-processing.
5. **Data Layer:** Manages persistent storage of user settings and emergency contacts.

C. Modules

1) User Interface Layer

- **Home Screen:** Features a prominent "SCAN CURRENCY" button, along with "Settings" and "HELP" buttons, and "Manage Contacts" option.
- **Scanning Interface:** Displays live camera feed with detection overlay showing denomination, confidence percentage, authenticity status, note count, and total amount. Control buttons include "Pause" and "Repeat" for voice output.
- **Settings Screen:** Provides accessibility configuration including Elderly Mode toggle, High Contrast option, Large Buttons toggle, Text Size adjustment, Haptic Feedback toggle, Voice Guidance toggle, Auto Announce Results toggle, Speech Rate selection, and Volume control.
- **Emergency Contacts Screen:** Manages emergency contact information with clear empty state messaging.

2) Machine Learning Layer

- **YOLOv11 Model:** Implements single-stage object detection with CSPDarknet backbone, PANet neck for multi-scale feature fusion, and anchor-free detection head.
- **TensorFlow Lite Inference:** Optimized for on-device execution with minimal memory footprint.
- **Post-Processing:** Applies Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) with IoU threshold of 0.5 and confidence thresholding at 0.70.

3) Voice Output Layer

- **Text-to-Speech Engine:** Provides English voice output with configurable speech rate and volume.
- **Announcement Structure:** "₹100 note detected. Genuine. Confidence 86 percent. Total amount ₹100."
- **Control Functions:** Pause and Repeat buttons for managing voice output.

4) Elderly Help Mode

- **SOS Activation:** Double-tap, long press (>2 seconds), and shake gesture detection.
- **Emergency Communication:** Direct calling to predefined contacts with auto-retry functionality.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. Dataset Creation

The dataset was built by collecting images of Indian currency notes under different real-world conditions. Genuine notes of ₹10, ₹20, ₹50, ₹100, ₹200, and ₹500 were obtained and photographed in various settings including different angles from 0 to 75 degrees, different lighting conditions like daylight and indoor light, and different distances from 10 to 50 centimeters.

Fake currency samples were created for training by modifying genuine note images through contrast changes, adding noise, altering colors, and printing genuine note images and recapturing them with smartphone cameras to simulate counterfeit notes.

The final dataset contains 3,515 training images and 336 validation images with a total of 8,791 labeled notes across seven categories including fake notes and six real denominations. Each image was manually annotated using the LabelImg tool, drawing boxes around each currency note and labeling them with their denomination and authenticity status.

To make the model more robust, data augmentation techniques were applied including rotation, scaling, brightness adjustment, contrast modification, and noise addition to simulate various real-world conditions. All counterfeit samples used in this research were digitally simulated for academic purposes only, and no actual counterfeit currency was produced or circulated.

B. Model Architecture

The system uses YOLOv11, a modern deep learning model designed for real-time object detection. The YOLOv11-nano version was selected specifically for mobile deployment because it offers a good balance between accuracy and speed. It has 2.58 million parameters and a model size of only 5.4 MB, making

it suitable to run on smartphones without compromising performance.

C. Training Configuration

The model was trained for 100 epochs on an NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU using the Ultralytics YOLO framework. The training used a batch size of 16 and image size of 640 by 640 pixels. The AdamW optimizer was used with a learning rate of 0.001667. During training, the model's loss values consistently decreased, indicating effective learning.

D. Model Conversion for Mobile Deployment

After training, the PyTorch model was converted to TensorFlow Lite format for mobile deployment. This conversion process involved exporting to ONNX format first, then converting to TensorFlow SavedModel, and finally to TensorFlow Lite. The converted model is 10.1 MB in size and achieves inference speed of 1.9 milliseconds on GPU, with minimal loss in accuracy.

E. Mobile Application Implementation

The mobile app is built using Flutter, which allows it to run on both Android and iOS devices. Key features include:

Camera Integration: The app continuously captures live video using the device camera and processes each frame for currency detection.

Real-time Detection: The TensorFlow Lite model runs on-device to detect and classify currency notes in real-time, displaying bounding boxes and labels around each detected note.

Voice Output: Text-to-speech functionality announces detection results in the format "₹100 note detected as Genuine. Confidence 86 percent. Total amount ₹100" making it accessible for visually impaired users.

Haptic Feedback: The app vibrates with different patterns for successful detection, errors, and emergency alerts, providing tactile confirmation.

Voice Commands: Users can control the app hands-free with commands like "start detection", "stop detection", "what is this", and "call help".

Elderly Helper Mode: A special mode with larger buttons, simplified interface, and automatic emergency calling when multiple counterfeit notes are detected.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Model Performance

The YOLOv11 model was trained for 100 epochs on a dataset of 3,515 images and validated on 336 images. The model achieved exceptional performance with 99.5% mean Average Precision (mAP50) and 94.4% mAP50-95. Fake currency detection achieved perfect precision and recall (100%), meaning every counterfeit note in the validation set was correctly identified with no false alarms. All real currency denominations (₹10 through ₹500) maintained consistent performance above 99% accuracy.

These results compare favorably with existing systems. Jaman et al. achieved 98.5% accuracy on Bangladeshi currency, while Bhushanm et al. reported 100% accuracy specifically for Indian ₹500 notes. Pachón et al. achieved 100% accuracy with ResNet18 on Colombian currency, though with slower inference times than our YOLOv11 implementation.

B. Real-World Performance

The system was tested on various mobile devices to evaluate real-world usability. On flagship devices like the iPhone 13 and Samsung S22, the app achieves 30-35 frames per second with inference times under 35 milliseconds, providing smooth real-time detection. Mid-range devices maintain 20-25 FPS, still sufficient for practical use. GPU acceleration provides significant speedup, with Metal on iOS delivering 7.7× faster performance than CPU-only execution.

Multi-note detection performs reliably, with 99.2% accuracy for 2-3 notes simultaneously and 97.8% for 4-5 notes. Performance degrades gracefully to 94.3% for six or more notes, making the app suitable for counting small stacks of currency.

Environmental testing showed robust performance across conditions: 99.2% accuracy in bright daylight,

98.7% under indoor fluorescent lighting, and 94.5% in low-light conditions. The model handles worn notes well (99.1% accuracy for slightly worn, 96.2% for heavily wrinkled) and maintains 92.5% accuracy even on torn or stained notes.

C. User Testing with Visually Impaired Participants. Fifteen visually impaired participants (8 completely blind, 7 with severe low vision) tested the application. Task completion rates were excellent: 100% for single note detection and fake note identification, 93.3% for multiple note counting, and 100% for SOS activation. Average detection time was 3.2 seconds per note.

Usability ratings on a 5-point scale were highly positive: ease of use (4.8), button size accessibility (4.9), voice output clarity (4.7), detection speed (4.6), confidence in results (4.8), and overall satisfaction (4.8).

Participants provided encouraging feedback: "I can finally check money independently without asking strangers," "The large buttons make it easy to use without sight," and "I feel more confident accepting cash payments now." These results demonstrate that CurrencyXplain effectively addresses the real-world needs of visually impaired users in financial transactions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented CurrencyXplain, a comprehensive deep learning-based mobile application for real-time currency detection and authentication designed specifically for visually impaired users. The system leverages YOLOv11 object detection to simultaneously identify currency denominations from ₹10 to ₹500 and verify note authenticity, achieving 99.5 percent mAP50 on validation data.

The application implements accessibility-first design principles including large touch targets, high-contrast visual elements, comprehensive English text-to-speech output, and haptic feedback. An Elderly Help Mode provides emergency communication through gesture-based SOS activation including double-tap, long-press, and shake gestures for one-touch calling of predefined contacts.

Through TensorFlow Lite optimization, the model achieves real-time inference with less than 100 millisecond latency and above 30 frames per second on modern mobile devices while maintaining accuracy. User testing with visually impaired participants demonstrated high satisfaction ratings at 4.8 out of 5 and successful task completion rates from 93 to 100 percent.

Compared to existing solutions, CurrencyXplain offers unique advantages including unified denomination and fake detection in a single model, multi-note support with automatic counting and summation, comprehensive accessibility features including voice output and haptic feedback, and integrated emergency assistance for elderly users. These features collectively address the research gap identified in the literature survey, providing a solution that combines accurate recognition, reliable authentication, and thoughtful accessibility design.

CurrencyXplain empowers visually impaired individuals with financial independence and security, reducing their vulnerability to counterfeit currency fraud while enabling confident participation in cash-based transactions.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of this project focuses on enhancing system performance, scalability, and real-world adaptability. Accuracy can be further improved by training the model with larger, more diverse datasets collected from different environments, lighting conditions, and note variations to enhance generalization across real-world scenarios.

Incorporating UV spectrum sensors to detect security features not visible in normal RGB light would significantly enhance counterfeit detection capabilities, as many security features on Indian currency notes are designed to be visible only under ultraviolet light. This multi-spectral approach would provide an additional layer of authentication beyond visible-light analysis.

Integration with cloud computing and mobile applications can enable remote monitoring, data storage, and real-time accessibility, allowing for centralized updates of counterfeit detection patterns and enabling community-based reporting of new

counterfeit variants. The system can also be upgraded with more advanced algorithms to increase processing speed and prediction precision.

Audio and physical property analysis including "flick" detection can be incorporated to analyze the physical properties of currency notes such as texture, thickness, and sound characteristics, providing multi-modal authentication that complements visual analysis. This would be particularly valuable for visually impaired users who rely on tactile and auditory cues.

Adding multilingual voice assistance beyond English, including Hindi, Tamil, Bengali, and Telugu, along with an improved user interface, will enhance usability and inclusiveness for diverse user populations across India. The elderly helper mode can be further developed with simplified interfaces, voice-guided verification, and large-display fraud warnings tailored to older adults.

Expanding the system to support additional currencies and denominations, including ₹2000 notes and international currencies, would broaden its applicability for travelers and businesses dealing with multiple currency types. Quantization optimization will implement int8 quantization for further model size reduction targeting below 3 megabytes without significant accuracy loss, building on established optimization strategies.

Wearable integration will be explored for smart glasses and smartwatches to provide heads-up display and wrist-based haptic feedback, further enhancing accessibility for visually impaired users in diverse environments. Clinical validation will include long-term usability studies to assess real-world adoption and identify usage patterns, cognitive load assessment to evaluate the system's impact during financial transactions, and comparative effectiveness studies against traditional assistive methods in controlled settings.

REFERENCES

[1] T. D. Pham, C. Park, D. T. Nguyen, G. Batchuluun, and K. R. Park, "Deep learning-based fake-banknote detection for the visually impaired people using visible-light images captured by smartphone

cameras," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 63144-63161, 2020.

[2] S. J. Jaman, M. Z. Haque, M. R. Islam, and U. A. Noor, "BD currency detection: A CNN-based approach with mobile app integration," unpublished.

[3] C. G. Pachón, D. M. Ballesteros, and D. Renza, "Fake banknote recognition using deep learning," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 1281, 2021.

[4] K. Bhushanm, M. Asritha, P. R. Sultana, P. A. Kumar, and S. M. Babu, "Fake currency detection using deep learning," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1-9, March 2024.

[5] R. K. Choudhary, P. Borate, P. Jaiswal, S. Gupta, and V. Mandaoade, "Literature survey on revolutionizing fake currency detection: CNN-based approach for Indian rupee notes," *Journal of Image Processing and Intelligent Remote Sensing*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 15-24, Aug-Sept 2024.

[6] S. Nair, F. Shaikh, M. Shaikh, E. Thomas, and P. Sherkhane, "Verinote - Fake currency detection using convolutional neural network," unpublished.

AI-Powered Text to Sign Translator

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Abstract— Sign language serves as a primary mode of communication for individuals with hearing and speech impairments. However, the lack of accessible translation tools creates communication barriers in education, healthcare, and social environments. This paper presents an AI-powered Text-to-Sign translation system supporting both American Sign Language (ASL) and Indian Sign Language (ISL). The proposed system performs deterministic alphabet-level translation by mapping each input character to its corresponding sign representation. A lightweight 3D avatar module is integrated to visually demonstrate selected gestures for improved user engagement. Additionally, an interactive Learning Hub module enhances sign language literacy through quizzes and feedback mechanisms. The system is implemented using Python-based web technologies to ensure portability and accessibility. The system achieves 100% mapping accuracy at the alphabet level and demonstrates potential for scalable future development toward word-level and grammar-aware translation systems.

Keywords—Assistive Technology, Text to Sign Translation, ASL, ISL, Educational Interface, Avatar Visualization

I. INTRODUCTION

Sign language is a primary communication medium for individuals with hearing and speech impairments. However, interaction between sign language users and non-sign users remains challenging in educational institutions, workplaces, and public services. Although several AI-based translation systems exist, many require high computational resources and extensive datasets, limiting their accessibility and deployment in lightweight environments.

This project proposes a web-based AI-powered Text-to-Sign translation system supporting both American Sign Language (ASL) and Indian Sign Language (ISL). Unlike probabilistic deep learning models, the proposed system performs deterministic alphabet-level translation, ensuring consistent and accurate output.

The key objectives of this work include, developing a web-based text-to-sign translator, supporting dual sign languages (ASL and ISL), integrating a lightweight avatar for gesture visualization and implementing an interactive Learning Hub module

II. RELATED WORK

Existing sign language translation systems can be categorized into three major approaches:

A. Vision-Based Recognition Systems

With the advancement of deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) became widely adopted for static hand gesture recognition. CNN-based architectures automatically extract spatial features from hand images through convolution operations. These systems significantly improved recognition accuracy compared to traditional image processing methods. However, they require large annotated datasets and substantial computational resources for training and inference.

B. Sequence-Based Neural Translation

For dynamic sign language translation, sequence-based neural models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, and more recently Transformer architectures have been employed. These models attempt to learn temporal dependencies between gestures and generate sentence-level translations using probabilistic modeling. Although these approaches enable continuous sign language translation, they are computationally intensive and require extensive labeled video datasets, which are often limited for regional sign languages such as Indian Sign Language (ISL).

C. Avatar-Based Systems

In addition to recognition-based systems, avatar-driven sign language visualization has gained attention as an alternative communication approach. Avatar-based systems utilize skeletal animation frameworks and motion capture datasets to render sign gestures through 3D models. While these systems improve visual clarity and user engagement, many lack linguistic precision in finger articulation and grammar modeling. Moreover, real-time gesture synthesis demands sophisticated animation engines and optimized rendering pipelines.

III. RESEARCH GAP

Sign language translation has been an active research area within assistive technology, computer vision, and natural language processing domains. Early systems primarily focused on gesture recognition using image processing techniques, where handcrafted features such as skin color segmentation, contour extraction, and edge detection were used to identify hand shapes. However, these approaches were sensitive to lighting variations and

background noise, resulting in limited robustness and scalability.

Recent research has also explored web-based assistive tools to improve accessibility and portability. However, many of these systems either focus solely on American Sign Language (ASL) or require backend AI services that limit offline deployment. Furthermore, most existing systems emphasize translation functionality without integrating educational reinforcement modules that help users learn and practice sign language..

Despite significant advancements, challenges remain in terms of computational efficiency, multilingual support, deployment simplicity, and integration of educational components. The need for lightweight, browser-accessible systems that can operate without heavy neural inference remains an open area for practical implementation. The proposed work addresses this gap by implementing a deterministic alphabet-level text-to-sign translation system with dual language support and an integrated interactive learning module, ensuring reliability, accessibility, and scalability.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The proposed system is a web-based AI-powered Text-to-Sign translation platform designed to assist communication and promote sign language awareness. The system focuses on alphabet-level translation of textual input into corresponding sign representations in both American Sign Language (ASL) and Indian Sign Language (ISL).³³ Unlike probabilistic deep learning models that rely on trained datasets and inference mechanisms, the proposed approach adopts a deterministic mapping strategy to ensure consistent and error-free translation at the character level.

The system is implemented using Python-based web technologies, enabling lightweight deployment and browser accessibility without requiring specialized hardware or GPU acceleration. The primary objective is to provide an accessible, scalable, and user-friendly platform that supports dual-language sign translation along with an integrated educational module for learning reinforcement.

The system operates by accepting textual input from the user, preprocessing the input string, and mapping each character to its corresponding sign representation. For an input string:

$$S = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots, c_n\}$$

where each c_i belongs to the English alphabet set $A = \{A, B, \dots, Z\}$ the output sequence is generated using a mapping function:

$$f: A \rightarrow G$$

where G represents the corresponding gesture representation. The final translated output is expressed as:

$$O = \{f(c_1), f(c_2), \dots, f(c_n)\}$$

In addition to translation, the system incorporates a basic 3D avatar module for visual demonstration of selected common gestures and an interactive Learning Hub to enhance user engagement and sign literacy.

B. System Architecture

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of System Architecture

Fig.1 illustrates the system architecture that follows a modular and layered architecture to ensure maintainability and scalability. The overall architecture consists of the following major components:

- User Interface Layer
- Input Processing Layer
- Language Selection Layer
- Alphabet Mapping Engine
- Output Rendering Layer
- Avatar Module
- Learning Hub Module

C. Modules

1) Text Input Module

This module provides an interface for users to enter textual content. It ensures that only valid alphabetical characters are processed. Special symbols and unsupported characters are filtered during preprocessing.

2) Preprocessing Module

The preprocessing module performs normalization operations including:

- Case conversion to uppercase
- Removal of non-alphabetical characters
- Tokenization of input string into individual characters

This ensures consistent mapping and avoids processing errors.

3) Language Selection Module

This module allows users to switch between ASL and ISL datasets dynamically. The system stores separate alphabet gesture repositories for each language. Conditional logic ensures that translation output corresponds to the selected language dataset.

4) Alphabet Mapping Engine

The core of the system, this engine maps each character to its corresponding sign representation using deterministic lookup.

5) Output Rendering Module

This module sequentially displays gesture representations corresponding to the input characters. The display mechanism ensures visual clarity and ordered presentation.

6) Avatar Module

The avatar module integrates a lightweight 3D model capable of demonstrating selected predefined gestures such as "Hi", "Yes", "No", and "Thank You". The animations are preprogrammed and triggered based on keyword selection. Although not linguistically complete, the avatar enhances visual engagement and user interaction

7) Learning Hub Module

The Learning Hub module provides an educational interface for sign language learning through interactive quizzes. The quiz mechanism randomly selects alphabet gestures and evaluates user responses.

V. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The proposed AI-powered Text-to-Sign Translation System is implemented as a lightweight web-based application using Python. The system is designed with modular architecture to ensure scalability, maintainability, and efficient execution. This section describes the software environment, data organization, processing workflow, and module-level implementation.

A. Technologies

The development of the system is carried out using Python along with a web framework Streamlit. The user interface is designed to provide a clean and interactive experience where users can input text and select the desired sign language. The backend handles processing and retrieval operations, while the frontend ensures clear visualization of gesture outputs. Since the system does not rely on deep learning inference or GPU-based processing, it remains lightweight and responsive.

B. Text preprocessing

When the user enters text, the system performs preprocessing before translation. The preprocessing stage includes converting all characters to uppercase to maintain uniformity, removing unsupported symbols and special characters, and splitting the input text into individual characters. This ensures that only valid alphabet letters are passed to the mapping engine. For example, if the user inputs the word "hello," it is converted to "HELLO" and then separated into the characters H, E, L, L, and O for further processing.

C. Alphabet mapping and Language Selector

The core functionality of the system lies in the Alphabet Mapping Engine. This module retrieves the corresponding sign gesture for each character from a structured dataset. Two separate datasets are maintained for ASL and ISL alphabets. Each dataset contains gesture images stored and indexed according to the English alphabet from A to Z. When a character is received, the system performs a direct lookup in the selected dataset and retrieves the corresponding gesture representation. Since deterministic mapping is used, the translation process ensures consistent and accurate output for every valid input.

Language selection is handled through a dedicated module that allows users to choose between ASL and ISL before performing translation. Based on the selected option, the system dynamically switches to the appropriate gesture dataset. This separation ensures that the correct sign representation is displayed according to the selected language while maintaining a unified system interface.

D. Avatar and Learning Hub

A simple 3D avatar module is integrated into the system to enhance visual engagement. The avatar is programmed with predefined animations representing common gestures such as "Hi," "Yes," "No," and "Thank You." When a supported keyword is selected, the corresponding animation is triggered. However, the avatar does not generate full linguistic sign language sentences and currently serves as a demonstrative visual component rather than a complete sign language synthesis engine.

The Learning Hub module is implemented as an interactive quiz system to support sign language education. This module randomly displays alphabet gestures and prompts the user to identify the correct corresponding letter. The system evaluates the response and calculates the score based on the number of correct answers. Immediate feedback is provided to improve user engagement and reinforce learning. This feature transforms the application from a simple translation tool into an educational platform.

VI. RESULTS

The developed AI-Powered Text-to-Sign Translator was successfully implemented as a web-based application supporting ASL and ISL alphabets. The system accurately converts input text into corresponding sign gestures using alphabet-level mapping. The gesture retrieval process is fast because it uses direct database lookup without complex computations. The output is displayed sequentially, ensuring clarity and correctness in representation. The avatar module successfully demonstrates a few predefined common gestures, improving visual understanding. The Learning Hub module enhances user engagement by allowing interactive practice. Overall, the system performs reliably for alphabet-based translation and educational purposes.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, a simple and efficient AI-Powered Text-to-Sign Translator was designed and implemented. The system

converts text input into sign language gestures using a structured alphabet mapping approach. Dual language support for ASL and ISL makes the system more flexible and useful. The integration of an avatar and learning module improves user interaction and educational value. The system is lightweight, easy to use, and suitable for assisting communication and basic sign language learning. Thus, the proposed system contributes toward bridging communication gaps between hearing and speech-impaired individuals and the general public.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

In the future, the system can be enhanced to support word-level and sentence-level translation instead of only alphabet-level mapping. Advanced natural language processing techniques can be integrated to improve grammatical structure in sign language output. The avatar module can be upgraded to generate dynamic sign animations rather than predefined gestures. Speech-to-text integration can be fully implemented to allow real-time voice-based translation. Additionally, mobile application deployment and cloud-based storage can improve accessibility and scalability of the system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jacky Li et al., "Sign Language Recognition and Translation: A Multi-Modal Approach Using Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing," in Proc. of the 14th Int. Conf. on Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing (RANLP), Varna, Bulgaria, 2023. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.ranlp-1.71/>
- [2] Umang Rastogi et al., "Advanced Gesture Recognition in Indian Sign Language using YOLOv10 with Swin Transformer Model," Scientific Reports, vol. 15, Article 32894, 2025. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-18496-8>
- [3] B. N. Madhukar et al., "Real-Time Sign Language Recognition and Translation: A Survey of Deep Learning Techniques," IJRASET, 2025. <https://www.ijraset.com/research-paper/real-time-sign-language-recognition-and-translation>
- [4] Esraa Hassan et al., "A Novel Model for Expanding Horizons in Sign Language Recognition," Scientific Reports, vol. 15, Article 24358, 2025. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-09643-2>
- [5] K. T. Govindharajalu et al., "A Deep Neural Network Framework for Dynamic Two-Handed Indian Sign Language Recognition," Sensors, vol. 25, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25123652>
- [6] Zeyu Liang et al., "Sign Language Translation: A Survey of Approaches and Techniques," Electronics, vol. 12, no. 12, 2023. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/12/12/2678>
- [7] Bader Alsharif et al., "Deep Learning Technology to Recognize American Sign Language Alphabet," Sensors (Basel), vol. 23, no. 18, 2023. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37766026/>

REAL-TIME MICROPLASTIC DETECTION IN HOUSEHOLD WATER USING UV-INDUCED FLUORESCENCE AND IoT MONITORING

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Abstract-- Microplastic contamination in domestic water systems has emerged as a critical environmental and public health concern. Existing detection methods such as Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy (FLIM), and hyperspectral imaging provide high accuracy but require expensive laboratory infrastructure, complex preprocessing, and significant computational resources. These constraints limit real-time and in-situ deployment, particularly in household environments. This paper presents a low-cost, portable, and real-time microplastic detection system based on UV-induced fluorescence sensing integrated with a lightweight edge-based AI classifier. Microplastics stained using Nile Red dye are excited using a UV LED source, and emitted fluorescence is captured via an optical photodiode. The signal is processed on an ESP32 microcontroller using a Decision Tree classifier optimized for low-power embedded execution. The system performs on-device noise filtering, feature extraction, and contaminant discrimination before transmitting processed data to a cloud dashboard via WiFi. Experimental validation demonstrates reliable detection of sub-millimeter particles with low latency and minimal power consumption. The proposed architecture eliminates dependency on bulky spectroscopy equipment and provides a scalable framework for real-time domestic water monitoring.

Keywords—Microplastic Detection, UV Fluorescence, Edge AI, ESP32, IoT Monitoring, Decision Tree Classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

Microplastics, defined as plastic particles smaller than 5 mm, are increasingly detected in freshwater ecosystems and domestic water supplies. These particles originate from degraded plastic waste, textile fibers, and industrial discharge. Due to their small size and hydrophobic properties, microplastics can accumulate in biological systems and potentially enter the human food chain.

Traditional detection methods such as FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, and FLIM provide polymer-level classification accuracy but require controlled laboratory environments, expensive instrumentation, and extensive sample preparation. While these approaches are scientifically robust, they are impractical for continuous household water monitoring.

Recent advances in AI-driven detection and edge computing have enabled portable sensing systems; however, most implementations rely on vision-based deep learning architectures requiring high computational power. Furthermore, many approaches remain sensitive to environmental noise and struggle to detect particles smaller than 1 mm.

The key research gap lies in developing a low-cost, real-time, and edge-deployable detection system that:

- Eliminates reliance on high-end spectroscopy
- Operates in real-world household conditions
- Detects sub-millimeter particles
- Requires minimal preprocessing
- Runs on low-power embedded hardware

To address these limitations, this work proposes a UV-induced fluorescence detection system integrated with an ESP32-based lightweight Decision Tree classifier for real-time microplastic monitoring in domestic water tanks.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Recent methodologies for microplastic detection span spectroscopy-based, imaging-based, and AI-driven approaches. Spectroscopy methods such as FTIR and Raman spectroscopy provide high chemical specificity but require expensive optical systems and controlled laboratory settings. FLIM-based detection techniques achieve polymer differentiation through fluorescence lifetime signatures but depend on confocal microscopy

and precise calibration. Hyperspectral imaging combined with machine learning classifiers has shown improved detection accuracy but involves bulky imaging equipment and computationally intensive processing. Deep learning-based object detection models such as YOLO architectures have been applied for real-time microplastic tracking in aqueous environments. While these approaches enable automated detection, they rely heavily on image clarity, lighting stability, and GPU-based computation, making them unsuitable for low-power embedded systems. TinyML-based approaches have demonstrated potential for edge deployment; however, many still depend on spectral feature extraction from expensive optical sensors. A comprehensive review of existing systems reveals the following common limitations:

- High hardware cost
- Computational complexity
- Environmental sensitivity
- Manual preprocessing steps
- Limited edge-device compatibility

The proposed system addresses these challenges by integrating UV fluorescence sensing with lightweight embedded AI classification.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The proposed system consists of a side-channel sampling chamber integrated into a domestic water tank. Water continuously flows through a controlled optical chamber where UV excitation and fluorescence detection occur. The system comprises:

- UV LED excitation source (365–395 nm)
- Nile Red staining for microplastic enhancement
- Optical photodiode fluorescence sensor
- ESP32 microcontroller
- WiFi communication module
- Cloud dashboard interface

The architecture enables continuous monitoring without manual intervention.

B. System Architecture

The operational workflow begins with continuous water diversion into the optical chamber. Upon UV excitation, fluorescence signals are captured and digitized using the ESP32 ADC module. Extracted features such as peak intensity and signal variance are processed by the embedded Decision Tree classifier. If contamination is detected, the system triggers an alert and transmits diagnostic data to the cloud dashboard. Otherwise, normal monitoring continues with periodic data logging.

Figure 1: BioClimate AI system architecture

The system architecture is organized into five layers:

1. **Sampling Layer** – Controlled water flow through optical chamber
2. **Optical Detection Layer** – UV excitation and fluorescence emission capture
3. **Signal Processing Layer** – ADC conversion and noise filtering
4. **AI Classification Layer** – Decision Tree-based contaminant detection
5. **IoT Communication Layer** – WiFi data transmission to dashboard

The ESP32 performs all inference operations locally, minimizing latency and power consumption.

C. Detection Principle

Nile Red dye selectively binds to hydrophobic polymer surfaces. Upon UV excitation, stained microplastics emit fluorescence in the visible spectrum. The photodiode sensor captures fluorescence intensity, which varies depending on particle presence and concentration. This intensity-based detection eliminates the need for spectral scanning or high-resolution imaging.

D. AI Classification Module

Instead of using computationally expensive CNN architectures, a Decision Tree classifier was selected due to:

- Low memory footprint
- Minimal computational overhead
- Fast inference time
- Compatibility with ESP32 architecture

Input features include:

- Fluorescence intensity amplitude
- Signal variance
- Flow rate compensation factor
- Temperature correction factor

The model performs binary classification: Microplastic Detected / Not Detected.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Design

□ Use Case Diagram

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

Figure II represents the use case diagram illustrates three actors User, Admin, and Raspberry Pi Sensors interacting with the BioClima AI system. Users register, manage health profiles, view dashboards, and receive personalized advisories. Admins manage users and broadcast alerts. Sensors autonomously collect and transmit environmental readings for real-time processing.

B. Hardware Configuration

- ESP32 microcontroller (240 MHz dual-core)
- UV LED (395 nm)
- Optical photodiode sensor
- Analog signal conditioning circuit
- Flow rate sensor

- Temperature sensor

ADC sampling frequency: 1 kHz Data window size: 500 samples

C. Signal Processing

Raw photodiode signals undergo:

- Moving average filtering
- Baseline normalization
- Peak detection
- Feature extraction

Noise sources such as ambient light and flow turbulence are compensated through threshold calibration

C. Embedded AI Deployment

The Decision Tree model was trained offline using labeled fluorescence datasets and exported as C-compatible logic for embedded inference.

Memory usage: < 50 KB Inference latency: < 200 ms

V. RESULTS

Experimental evaluation was conducted using controlled microplastic samples with varying concentrations.

Parameter	Observed Value
Detection Accuracy	88–92%
Inference Time	180 ms
Power Consumption	< 4W
Minimum Particle Size	< 1 mm
False Positive Rate	< 8%

The system demonstrated stable operation under moderate lighting variations and water flow rates up to 30 cm/s.

Compared to spectroscopy-based systems, the proposed architecture achieved significant cost reduction while maintaining acceptable detection reliability.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a portable, low-cost, and edge-deployable microplastic detection system based on UV-induced fluorescence sensing and lightweight AI classification. By eliminating reliance on expensive spectroscopy equipment and leveraging embedded Decision Tree inference on ESP32, the system enables real-time domestic water monitoring with minimal power consumption.

The proposed architecture provides a scalable framework for household, community-level, and rural water quality surveillance.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

Future enhancements include:

- Dye-free autofluorescence detection
- Polymer-type classification
- Adaptive TinyML model updates
- Multi-pollutant sensing integration
- Long-term field validation studies

REFERENCES

[1] A. Cerioli et al., “Efficient Detection of Microplastics on Edge Devices With Tailored Compiler for TinyML Applications,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 90970–90983, 2025.

[2] F. Zhou, X. Wang, G. Wang, and Y. Zuo, “A Rapid Method for Detecting Microplastics Based on Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Technology (FLIM),” *Toxics*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 118, 2022.

[3] H. Zhang et al., “Applications of Fluorescence Technology for Rapid Identification of Marine Plastic Pollution,” *Polymers*, vol. 17, no. 12, pp. 1679, 2025.

[4] M. A. B. Sarker, U. Butt, M. H. Imtiaz, and A. B. Baki, “Automatic Detection of Microplastics in the Aqueous Environment,” in *Proc. IEEE 13th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.

[5] R. C. Thompson et al., “Lost at Sea: Where Is All the Plastic?,” *Science*, vol. 304, no. 5672, pp. 838, 2004.

[6] J. A. Ivar do Sul and M. F. Costa, “The Present and Future of Microplastic Pollution in the Marine Environment,” *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 185, pp. 352–364, 2014.

[7] L. Cózar et al., “Plastic Debris in the Open Ocean,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS)*, vol. 111, no. 28, pp. 10239–10244, 2014.

[8] A. L. Andrady, “Microplastics in the Marine Environment,” *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, vol. 62, no. 8, pp. 1596–1605, 2011.

[9] J. Redmon et al., “You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection,” in *Proc. IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2016, pp. 779–788.

[10] D. Han et al., “TinyML: Enabling Machine Learning on Ultra-Low-Power Edge Devices,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 8899–8912, 2020.

[11] G. Erni-Cassola, M. Gibson, R. Thompson, and J. Christie-Oleza, “Lost, But Found with Nile Red: A Novel Method to Detect and Quantify Small Microplastics,”

Environmental Science & Technology, vol. 51, no. 23, pp. 13641–13648, 2017.

[12] A. Turner and K. L. Holmes, “X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometry for Analysis of Microplastics in Environmental Samples,” *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 631–632, pp. 1222–1230, 2018.

FLUENT AI - AI POWERED VIRTUAL COMMUNICATION TUTOR USING VIDEO CALL INTERFACE

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Abstract— Effective communication skills are essential in academic, professional, and social environments. Many learners struggle with spoken English due to hesitation, lack of confidence, and limited opportunities for real-time practice. Although artificial intelligence and conversational models have shown strong potential in language learning applications, many systems remain limited to basic grammar correction or text-based interactions without addressing behavioral aspects of communication. This study presents FluentAI, an AI-powered English communication tutor that integrates real-time speech recognition, behavioral confidence analysis, and large language model-based conversational interaction. The system analyzes speech characteristics such as filler word frequency, hesitation delay, speech pace, and vocabulary diversity to compute a dynamic confidence score. Based on this score, the AI tutor adapts its response complexity and feedback style to support gradual confidence improvement. The platform combines speech-to-text processing, conversational AI response generation, and avatar-based interaction within an interactive web application. By bridging the gap between language learning tools and real-time communication training, the proposed system demonstrates the potential of artificial intelligence to enhance speaking fluency, engagement, and confidence development.

Keywords— Artificial Intelligence, Conversational AI, Speech Recognition, Confidence Detection, Large Language Models, Adaptive Learning, Communication Training, Educational Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

English communication proficiency has become an essential skill in the modern globalized world. It plays a vital role in higher education, professional growth, international collaboration, and digital communication. In academic institutions, students are often evaluated not only on their technical knowledge but also on their ability to present ideas clearly and confidently. Similarly, in professional environments, effective spoken communication influences interviews, workplace performance, leadership potential, and career advancement. Despite its importance, a significant number of learners struggle with real-time spoken

communication due to hesitation, anxiety, and lack of confidence.

Traditional language learning methods primarily focus on grammar rules, vocabulary acquisition, reading comprehension, and written exercises. While these components are fundamental, they do not fully address the challenges associated with spontaneous verbal expression. Many learners understand grammatical structures theoretically but experience difficulty when asked to speak in real-time situations such as interviews, presentations, or discussions. This gap highlights a critical limitation in conventional language education systems: the absence of structured confidence development mechanisms.

With the advancement of digital learning platforms, several online applications have emerged to support language acquisition. These platforms often provide interactive exercises, automated grammar correction, and speech-based pronunciation evaluation. However, most existing systems evaluate language performance mainly in terms of correctness rather than behavioral indicators such as hesitation time, filler word usage, speech pace, or lexical diversity. As a result, they improve linguistic accuracy but do not significantly enhance communication confidence.

Recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly in the domain of Large Language Models (LLMs), have enabled highly contextual and human-like conversational systems. Transformer-based architectures have demonstrated remarkable performance in generating coherent multi-turn dialogues. These advancements have opened opportunities for AI-driven tutoring systems capable of providing personalized and scalable learning experiences. Nevertheless, most AI conversational tutors operate using static prompt strategies and generalized response generation, without incorporating measurable behavioral signals from the learner.

Confidence in communication is not solely determined by grammatical correctness. Psychological and behavioral research suggests that perceived confidence is influenced by factors such as response latency, speech continuity,

vocabulary variety, and reduced filler usage. A speaker who responds promptly, uses diverse vocabulary, and maintains steady speech pace is often perceived as more confident, even if minor grammatical errors exist. Therefore, an effective communication tutoring system should integrate both linguistic correction and behavioral confidence modeling.

To address this gap, this research introduces FluentAI, a real-time confidence-aware AI communication tutor designed to enhance both fluency and self-confidence in spoken English. The system integrates live speech recognition, behavioral speech analytics, adaptive large language model responses, and immersive conversational interaction. Unlike conventional systems, FluentAI computes a quantitative confidence score based on measurable speech parameters such as filler frequency, hesitation delay, response length adequacy, speech pace normalization, and vocabulary diversity ratio. This score dynamically influences the AI tutor’s tone, complexity, and feedback strategy.

By incorporating real-time behavioral analytics into conversational AI, FluentAI aims to bridge the gap between language correctness and communication confidence. The primary contribution of this work lies in the development of a measurable confidence modeling framework that adapts instructional interaction based on user behavior. This approach promotes a more personalized and psychologically supportive learning environment.

II. RELATED WORKS

Cuicui Zhu et al. [1] proposed a pronunciation error detection model based on feature fusion. The methodology combines CNN and Bi-LSTM encoders with multi-attention mechanisms to improve classification performance. The model achieved significant performance gains and effectively handled class imbalance. However, it requires accurately labeled datasets, has high computational complexity, and was not validated in real-time environments.

Xing Wei et al. [2] introduced an end-to-end speech model enhanced with articulatory feature integration for L2 mispronunciation detection and diagnosis. Their approach improved detection accuracy and provided better diagnosis of pronunciation errors. Nevertheless, the system depends on articulatory data, increases model complexity, and has limited cross-language validation.

Anwar Hussen et al. [3] developed a non-autoregressive end-to-end neural modeling approach for automatic pronunciation error detection. The system utilized NAR E2E LASO dictation with Bi-LSTM attention and FBANK/wav2vec features. It achieved faster inference and lower phoneme error rate compared to baseline models. However, it requires labeled L2 datasets, has higher model complexity, and struggles with persistent vowel and consonant errors.

Linkai Peng et al. [4] proposed an end-to-end mispronunciation detection and diagnosis framework using transfer learning in speech models. The approach demonstrated higher accuracy and improved generalization capability. Despite these advantages, the model depends on pre-trained source models, shows accent sensitivity, and requires high computational resources.

Haifa Alaqel et al. [5] presented a transformer-based speech recognition model with transfer learning and hybrid data augmentation for improving diacritical Arabic speech recognition. The system achieved better recognition accuracy and robustness to diacritical variations. However, it demands large datasets, involves high computational cost, and has limited testing in noisy environments.

Anurag Das et al. [6] proposed a mispronunciation detection method using speech reconstruction before error detection. Their approach improved accuracy and demonstrated noise robustness. However, it introduces additional computational overhead, requires high-quality data, and is dependent on the reconstruction model’s performance.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The FluentAI system is an intelligent and adaptive communication training platform designed to improve English speaking fluency, confidence, and conversational skills through real-time AI interaction. It provides an immersive learning environment where users can practice speaking, receive instant feedback, and track their progress securely. The system integrates speech recognition, behavioral confidence analysis, large language model-based response generation, and avatar-based interaction within a unified architecture.

Users interact with the system through live microphone input, which is transcribed in real time. The platform analyzes speech characteristics such as filler words, hesitation delay, speech pace, and vocabulary diversity to compute a dynamic confidence score. Based on this score, the AI tutor adjusts its teaching style, difficulty level, and feedback tone to suit the learner’s confidence level. In addition to speaking practice, the system offers structured challenges, writing evaluation, session recording, and performance tracking. By enhancing adaptability, engagement, and personalization, FluentAI promotes continuous improvement in communication skills while maintaining secure user data management.

The modular architecture of the system ensures scalability and smooth integration of future AI enhancements. This design allows the platform to evolve continuously while maintaining performance efficiency and user-centric adaptability.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: FluentAI System Architecture

The System Architecture illustrates the multi-layer architecture of the FluentAI system, ensuring real-time interaction and scalable AI processing. The architecture consists of an External Services layer, Frontend layer, and Backend layer connected through HTTP APIs and WebSocket communication.

The External Services layer includes speech-to-text processing, large language model integration, text-to-speech synthesis, and AI avatar rendering. The Frontend manages user interaction, transcript display, state management, and confidence analysis. The Backend handles real-time request processing, AI response generation, session management, and database storage. The system uses bidirectional WebSocket communication to ensure low latency and smooth conversational flow. Session data, confidence metrics, and progress information are securely stored in a structured database for future analysis and tracking. This modular architecture improves system scalability and allows easy integration of additional AI services in the future. It also ensures reliable data flow between different components of the system while maintaining real-time responsiveness. The layered design helps maintain system stability and simplifies maintenance and further development.

C. Modules

- **User Module:** Manages user authentication, session tracking, profile management, and progress monitoring. It ensures secure login and maintains individual performance history, including confidence scores and completed practice sessions.
- **Speech Recognition Module:** Captures live microphone input and converts speech to text in real time using an external speech-to-text service. It ensures high transcription accuracy and minimal latency to maintain natural conversation flow.
- **Confidence Detection Module:** Analyzes behavioral speech indicators such as filler word frequency, hesitation time, speech pace, and vocabulary diversity. It computes a confidence score between predefined levels to adapt the AI tutor's response strategy.
- **Conversational AI Module:** Generates context-aware responses using a large language model. It dynamically modifies feedback complexity and questioning style based on the user's detected confidence level.
- **Avatar Interaction Module:** Provides immersive AI communication through text-to-speech synthesis and WebRTC-based avatar interaction with lip synchronization support.
- **Database Management Module :** Securely stores user profiles, transcripts, session records, confidence metrics, and performance analytics, ensuring controlled access and data integrity.
- **Writing Analysis Module :** Evaluates user-written essays and paragraphs by analyzing grammar, coherence, vocabulary usage, and sentence structure. It provides detailed corrective feedback and scoring to help users improve their written communication skills alongside speaking proficiency.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Design

• Use Case Diagram

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

Use Case Diagram represents the workflow of interactions in the FluentAI system, where users engage with the AI tutor for speaking practice, writing evaluation, and confidence tracking. The user initiates a session through login or guest access and selects a speaking challenge or free conversation mode. The system processes live speech input, computes confidence metrics, generates AI responses, and stores session data for progress monitoring. The backend manages AI processing, session storage, and performance analytics, ensuring smooth coordination between frontend interaction and AI services. The design enables seamless real-time communication between the user, speech recognition engine, confidence analyzer, and conversational AI module.

B. Implementation Details

• Frontend Technologies

The frontend of the FluentAI system is developed using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, providing a responsive and interactive user interface. HTML ensures structured content organization, while CSS enhances visual presentation and user experience. JavaScript enables dynamic interaction, real-time transcript updates, confidence gauge visualization, and WebSocket communication. Socket.IO is used for bidirectional communication between the frontend and backend, enabling low-latency real-time conversation flow. WebRTC integration supports webcam and microphone access for avatar-based communication. These technologies collectively provide a user-friendly, scalable, and performance-optimized interface. The modular frontend design also ensures easy maintainability and future feature expansion.

- Backend Technologies

The backend is implemented using Python Flask and Flask-SocketIO, ensuring efficient real-time communication and API handling. Flask provides a lightweight and flexible framework for managing routes and server-side logic. Flask-SocketIO enables continuous bidirectional communication for transmitting transcripts and receiving AI responses without delay.

The conversational intelligence module integrates Groq LLaMA 3.1 8B for generating adaptive responses based on user input and confidence level. Deepgram Nova-2 is used for real-time speech-to-text transcription. These technologies ensure accurate speech processing, contextual response generation, and smooth conversational interaction within the system architecture.

- Security Mechanisms

Security is implemented through controlled API access, secure environment variable management for API keys, and HTTPS-based encrypted communication. User authentication mechanisms ensure session isolation and prevent unauthorized access. Input validation and server-side filtering protect against common vulnerabilities such as SQL injection and Cross-Site Scripting (XSS). Secure WebSocket communication further safeguards real-time data transmission between client and server.

- Database Management

Data is managed using SQLite integrated with SQLAlchemy ORM for structured storage and efficient query handling. The database stores user profiles, session transcripts, confidence scores, performance metrics, and progress statistics. Efficient indexing and optimized query execution ensure minimal latency during data retrieval. Session data is persistently stored for analytics, enabling users to track improvement over time. The database architecture is designed to support scalability and maintain data integrity across multiple concurrent sessions.

V. RESULT

The FluentAI system overcomes limitations of traditional language learning platforms by introducing real-time confidence-aware adaptive interaction. Unlike conventional applications that focus primarily on grammar correction and static exercises, FluentAI integrates speech recognition, behavioral confidence analysis, and large language model-based conversational intelligence within a unified framework.

The system enables users to engage in live speaking sessions where their speech characteristics are continuously analyzed to compute a confidence score. Based on this score, the AI tutor dynamically adjusts its feedback tone, complexity level, and questioning strategy. Experimental evaluation involving 12 undergraduate students demonstrated measurable improvements in communication confidence, with an average increase of 18.6 percent across three sessions. The system achieved 95.2 percent speech recognition accuracy and maintained an average response latency of 1.84 seconds, ensuring smooth conversational flow.

The integration of avatar-based interaction enhanced user engagement, with the majority of participants preferring immersive communication over text-based chat systems. Secure session storage and structured database management allow users to track progress over time. These results indicate that FluentAI provides an efficient, adaptive, and scalable solution for improving spoken communication skills in real-world learning environments.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The FluentAI system can be further enhanced by integrating advanced emotion recognition and prosodic analysis to detect user stress, anxiety, and engagement levels during conversation. By incorporating voice tone and sentiment analysis, the system can provide more personalized and psychologically adaptive feedback.

Future development may include phoneme-level pronunciation scoring to provide detailed articulation feedback alongside confidence evaluation. The integration of reinforcement learning techniques could enable the AI tutor to continuously improve its adaptive strategies based on long-term user interaction patterns.

Expanding the platform to support multilingual communication training would increase accessibility and usability across diverse user groups. Additionally, deploying the system on a cloud-based scalable infrastructure would enable large-scale real-time usage while maintaining performance efficiency.

Mobile application development and offline session recording features can further enhance accessibility and convenience.

VII. CONCLUSION

FluentAI presents an intelligent and adaptive AI-powered communication tutoring system designed to enhance English speaking fluency and confidence through real-time interaction. By integrating speech recognition, behavioral confidence analysis, and large language model-based conversational intelligence, the system addresses both linguistic accuracy and psychological aspects of communication.

Unlike conventional language learning platforms that primarily focus on grammar correction, FluentAI introduces a measurable confidence detection mechanism that evaluates speech patterns such as hesitation delay, filler word frequency, speech pace, and vocabulary diversity. The dynamic adaptation of AI responses based on confidence levels creates a personalized and supportive learning environment.

Experimental evaluation demonstrated measurable improvement in user confidence, high speech recognition accuracy, and low response latency, validating the system's effectiveness and scalability. By combining technological innovation with behavioral modeling, FluentAI provides a practical and efficient solution for improving real-time communication skills in academic and professional contexts.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Litman and S. Forbes-Riley, "Spoken Dialogue Systems for Intelligent Tutoring," *AI Magazine*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 63–74, 2006.
- [2] J. Bernstein, A. Van Moere, and J. Cheng, "Validating Automated Speech Recognition for Language Learning," *Language Testing*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 355–377, 2010.
- [3] Y. Kim and A. Baylor, "Pedagogical Agents as Learning Companions," *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 569–596, 2006.
- [4] M. Graesser, A. Olney, B. Haynes, and A. Chipman, "AutoTutor: A Tutor with Dialogue in Natural Language," *Behavior Research Methods*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 180–192, 2005.
- [5] S. D'Mello and A. Graesser, "AutoTutor and Affective Autotutor: Learning by Talking with Emotionally Intelligent Computers," *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 1–39, 2012.
- [6] T. Wang, J. Yang, and H. Chen, "Adaptive Learning Systems Based on Artificial Intelligence for Personalized Education," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 112000–112012, 2020.
- [7] A. Fadhil, "A Conversational Interface to Improve Medication Adherence: Towards AI Support in Patient Treatment," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1803.09844*, 2018.
- [8] T. Brown et al., "Language Models are Few-Shot Learners," in *Proc. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2020.
- [9] J. Devlin, M. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding," in *Proc. NAACL-HLT*, 2019.
- [10] OpenAI, "GPT-4 Technical Report," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.08774*, 2023.
- [11] D. Amodei et al., "Deep Speech 2: End-to-End Speech Recognition in English and Mandarin," in *Proc. ICML*, 2016.
- [12] Deepgram Inc., "Deepgram Speech-to-Text API Documentation," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://deepgram.com>
- [13] Groq Inc., "Groq LLaMA 3.1 Model Documentation," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://groq.com>
- [14] Simli AI, "Real-Time AI Avatar Platform Documentation," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://simli.ai>

BLITZGO: INTELLIGENT ON- DEMAND BIKE TAXI PLATFORM

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Abstract-- Conventional urban transportation systems, including traditional taxis and app-based ride hailing, often present significant drawbacks for daily commuters. These systems are frequently inefficient in congested traffic, leading to prolonged travel times, and can be cost-prohibitive for short-distance or last-mile journeys. Existing platforms lack the agility to navigate dense urban environments effectively, creating a gap in accessible, affordable, and real-time transportation solutions. This limits a commuter's ability to travel efficiently and adds to urban congestion and pollution. To overcome these challenges, the proposed system, blitzgo, is an intelligent, on demand bike taxi platform designed to provide a low-cost, real-time solution for urban mobility. The system architecture is built around two core mobile applications: one for passengers and another for registered drivers (captains). Blitzgo leverages IoT principles by utilizing smartphone GPS for precise, real-time location tracking of both passengers and the fleet. An intelligent algorithm processes ride requests, matching passengers with the nearest available captain and providing instant fare estimations based on distance and demand. Communication between the passenger, captain, and backend server is handled via real-time protocols to ensure seamless data synchronization for live tracking and status updates. All ride data is transmitted over a secure connection to a cloud-based backend, which is processed and made available to both users through a user-friendly mobile dashboard. This dashboard displays ride details, route navigation, and estimated time of arrival, and includes safety features such as an in-app SOS button and ridesharing capabilities. This system provides an automated, efficient, and scalable alternative to traditional transport, making rapid urban travel accessible to all. The future scope for Blitzgo includes the integration of electric vehicles (EVs) to promote sustainable travel, the implementation of dynamic pricing models using machine learning to optimize for traffic and demand, and integration with public transport APIs to offer a truly multimodal, end-to-end transit solution.
Keywords— Bike Taxi Platform, Intelligent Ride Matching, Real-Time GPS Tracking, Urban Mobility, Cloud-Based Transportation System, Smart Transportation Architecture, Dynamic Pricing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban transportation has emerged as one of the most critical challenges in rapidly growing metropolitan cities. Increasing population density, expanding commercial zones, and limited road infrastructure have led to severe traffic congestion, longer commute times, increased fuel consumption, and rising levels of air pollution. Conventional transportation systems such as buses, auto-rickshaws, taxis, and private vehicles often struggle to provide efficient and affordable mobility, particularly for short-distance and last-mile travel. Although app-based ride-hailing platforms have improved accessibility and convenience, most of these systems are car-centric, which contributes further to road congestion and higher operational costs.

In cities like Thiruvananthapuram and other urban regions, commuters frequently experience delays during peak hours due to heavy traffic and limited route flexibility. Four-wheeler vehicles are often inefficient in navigating narrow roads, densely populated areas, and high-traffic corridors. As a result, passengers face increased waiting times, higher fares, and unreliable arrival estimates. This situation highlights the need for a more agile, cost-effective, and scalable urban mobility solution.

Two-wheeler transportation, particularly bike taxi services, provides a practical alternative to traditional ride-hailing systems. Motorbikes require less road space, consume less fuel, emit fewer greenhouse gases, and can maneuver efficiently through congested traffic. These advantages make bike taxis an ideal solution for last-mile connectivity, daily commuting, and short urban trips.

BLITZGO is developed as an intelligent, on-demand bike taxi platform designed to address these urban mobility challenges. The system focuses on providing affordable, fast, and reliable transportation through real-time tracking, intelligent ride allocation, and cloud-based infrastructure. The platform consists of two primary mobile applications—one for passengers and one for registered drivers (referred to as captains). By leveraging smartphone GPS sensors and IoT-enabled location monitoring, BLITZGO enables precise realtime tracking of users and vehicles.

An intelligent ride-matching algorithm processes ride requests and assigns the nearest available captain based on geospatial distance calculations. The system also provides instant fare estimation using distance-based pricing models and dynamic demand adjustments. Real-time communication between passenger, captain, and backend server ensures seamless ride tracking, status updates, and navigation support. The platform incorporates safety mechanisms including an in-app SOS

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Meshkani and Farooq [1] proposed a generalized ride-matching framework for sustainable shared mobility. Their approach focuses on optimizing passenger–driver matching to reduce authentication to enhance user trust and reliability. the waiting time and vehicle idle distance. Although effective for shared mobility, the model is primarily designed for car-based systems rather than lightweight bike taxi platforms..

Cao et al. [2] presented an optimization model for ride-sharing route planning that balances system efficiency and user fairness. The study improves routing decisions using mathematical optimization techniques. However, the proposed model is computationally intensive and better suited for structured ride-hailing environments than agile, short-distance bike taxi services.

Masoud and Jayakrishnan [3] developed a real-time peer-to-peer ride-matching algorithm for flexible ridesharing systems. Their solution dynamically matches riders using spatial and temporal constraints, reducing passenger wait times. The work focuses on multi-passenger carpooling and does not address two-wheelerspecific mobility requirements.

Schreieck et al. [4] proposed a dynamic ridesharing matching algorithm that adapts to continuously changing ride requests. The system improves scalability through geospatial clustering. While effective for urban ridesharing, it lacks safety integration and optimization for bike-based transportation in congested city environments..

A data-driven study published in EPJ Data Science [5] analyzed biking safety in urban areas using traffic and accident datasets. The research highlights the importance of route safety analysis for two-wheelers. However, it does not provide a complete ridehailing system architecture or real-time booking implementation.

Chaudhary [6] evaluated service quality in ride-hailing bike services, focusing on user satisfaction, affordability, and safety perception. The study emphasizes transparent pricing and ride tracking. Although insightful, it does not propose an intelligent backend architecture or automated ride allocation mechanisms.

A recent study by Zhang et al. [7] proposed an AI-based dynamic pricing and demand prediction model for ride-hailing platforms. The system uses machine learning techniques to forecast ride demand based on traffic density and time patterns. While effective for large-scale taxi systems, it lacks optimization for lightweight bike taxi mobility solutions.

button, ride-sharing functionality, trip recording, and secure BLITZGO is an intelligent on-demand bike taxi platform designed to provide efficient, affordable, and real-time urban transportation. The system consists of two primary mobile applications: a Passenger App and a Rider App, integrated through a centralized cloud-based backend. When a passenger initiates a ride request, the Ride Allocation Engine processes the

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

nearest available rider. The system ensures seamless communication between users through real-time request using GPS-based geospatial calculations to identify

synchronization protocols. A Safety and Alert System continuously monitors ride status and enables emergency support features such as SOS alerts and ride-sharing functionality. Integrated payment gateways facilitate secure digital transactions, while administrative dashboards manage ride records, analytics, and system monitoring. The architecture ensures scalability, security, and efficient ride lifecycle management within congested urban environments.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: BioClima AI system architecture

Figure 1 The BLITZGO architecture comprises Passenger and Rider application interfaces connected to a centralized Ride Allocation Engine. The engine communicates with the Safety and Alert System and GPS–IoT module for real-time tracking and monitoring. Payment Gateway integration ensures secure transactions. The Admin Dashboard manages ride data, system analytics, and operational control. This modular architecture enables efficient ride matching, safety supervision, and scalable cloud-based management.

C. Modules

- Passenger Application Module

This module provides the user interface for passengers to register, log in, book rides, track captains in real time, view fare estimates, and make digital payments. It integrates GPS services

for location selection and communicates with the backend for ride status updates and notifications.

- Rider (Captain) Application Module

The Rider module allows captains to accept or reject ride requests, navigate to pickup and drop locations, monitor earnings, and manage availability status. It ensures real-time synchronization with the Ride Allocation Engine and supports secure authentication mechanisms

- Ride Allocation Engine

The Ride Allocation Engine is the core processing unit of the system. It uses geospatial distance calculations to identify the nearest available rider based on GPS coordinates. The engine minimizes passenger waiting time and optimizes rider utilization through intelligent matching logic.

- GPS and IoT Tracking Module

This module enables continuous real-time tracking of both passenger and rider locations. It updates ride progress, calculates Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), and ensures route monitoring. The module enhances transparency and improves system reliability.

- Safety and Alert System

The Safety module provides emergency support features including an in-app SOS button, ride-sharing functionality, and trip recording. It continuously monitors ride activity and allows quick alert transmission to predefined contacts or administrators.

- Payment Gateway Module

This module handles secure digital transactions between passengers and riders. It supports online payment methods and wallet integration. All transactions are encrypted and processed through secure communication protocols.

- Admin Dashboard Module

The Admin Dashboard enables system monitoring, user management, ride analytics, and performance evaluation. It stores ride records, monitors active trips, and ensures smooth operational control of the platform.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Design

Use Case Diagram

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

Figure II The use case diagram of **BLITZGO** illustrates the interaction between passengers, drivers, and administrators within the intelligent bike taxi platform. It represents core functionalities such as ride booking, real-time tracking, payment processing, and safety features, along with external systems like GPS and payment gateways for seamless operation.

B. Implementation Details

- Frontend Technologies

The BLITZGO frontend is developed as two dedicated mobile applications for **Passenger** and **Driver**, built using modern cross-platform mobile development frameworks (Android/iOS). The user interface is designed with a simple and intuitive booking workflow, enabling users to request rides, track drivers in real time, and complete payments seamlessly. The frontend integrates real-time GPS tracking for live ride monitoring and route visualization. Features such as ride history, fare estimation, rating and review system, wallet integration, and SOS emergency alerts are implemented to enhance usability and safety. API communication with the backend is handled through secure RESTful services.

- Backend Technologies

The backend of BLITZGO is implemented using a cloudbased architecture to ensure scalability and high availability. It manages ride requests, driver allocation, fare calculation, payment processing, and user authentication. An intelligent ride allocation algorithm is incorporated to match passengers with nearby available drivers efficiently. Real-time GPS data is processed for tracking and route optimization. The system supports data synchronization, ride status updates, and trip recording through centralized cloud storage and server-side processing.

- Security Mechanisms

Blitzgo implements a multi-layered security framework to ensure safe and reliable operations. User authentication is enforced through secure login mechanisms, and sensitive data such as passwords are encrypted before storage. Role-based access

control distinguishes Passenger, Driver, and Admin functionalities. Secure payment transactions are handled through integrated payment gateways with transaction verification protocols.

Additionally, safety features such as SOS alerts, emergency contact sharing, trip recording, and real-time ride monitoring enhance passenger and driver security.

- Database Management

The system utilizes a cloud-based database for storing user profiles, ride details, payment records, ratings, and trip history. Structured data models are maintained for passengers, drivers, rides, and transactions.

Real-time synchronization ensures that ride status updates and GPS tracking data are accurately reflected across both applications. The database architecture is designed to support scalability for increasing user volume and future expansion into new urban regions.

V. RESULTS

The BLITZGO system was successfully designed and evaluated as an intelligent on-demand bike taxi platform. The application demonstrated efficient real-time ride booking and driver allocation with minimal response delay. GPS-based live tracking accurately displayed rider and driver locations, ensuring transparency and route optimization throughout the trip. The intelligent ride-matching algorithm effectively connected passengers with nearby available drivers, reducing waiting time and improving operational efficiency. The fare estimation module generated accurate cost predictions based on distance and route conditions. Secure payment gateway integration ensured reliable digital transactions with proper verification mechanisms. Safety features such as SOS alerts, trip sharing, and ride monitoring were tested and functioned effectively, enhancing user trust and reliability. The cloud-based backend maintained stable performance under multiple concurrent ride requests, demonstrating scalability potential. Overall, BLITZGO achieved its objective of providing a fast, affordable, and technology-driven urban mobility solution.

VI. CONCLUSION

BLITZGO successfully demonstrates an intelligent, scalable, and efficient solution for on-demand bike taxi services in urban environments. By integrating real-time GPS tracking, intelligent ride allocation algorithms, secure digital payments, and enhanced safety mechanisms, the system ensures convenience, affordability, and reliability for both passengers and drivers. The cloud-based backend architecture supports data synchronization and scalability, enabling the platform to handle increasing user demand. Furthermore, features such as SOS alerts, ride monitoring, and rating systems improve overall user trust and service quality. BLITZGO contributes toward reducing traffic congestion, minimizing travel time, and promoting sustainable urban mobility through technology-driven transportation solutions.

VII. FUTURESCOPE

Future enhancements of BLITZGO include integration of electric bikes to promote sustainable transportation and reduce carbon emissions. The system can incorporate AI-driven traffic prediction models for optimized routing and reduced delays. Advanced safety analytics, automated emergency response mechanisms, and expansion into multi-city deployments with improved cloud scalability can further strengthen platform reliability and global adaptability. Future development can also include facial recognition or biometric verification for improved rider and driver authentication. Integration with government transport systems and smart city infrastructure could enable better regulatory compliance and traffic coordination.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. M. Meshkani and B. Farooq, "A Generalized RideMatching Approach for Sustainable Shared Mobility," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 2021.
- [2] Y. Cao, S. Wang, and J. Li, "Optimization Model of RideSharing Route for Ride Hailing Considering System Optimization and User Fairness," *IEEE Access*, 2021.
- [3] N. Masoud and R. Jayakrishnan, "A Real-Time Algorithm for Peer-to-Peer Ride Matching in Flexible Ridesharing Systems," *Transportation Research Record*, 2017.
- [4] M. Schreieck, H. Safetli, S. A. Siddiqui, and C. Pflügler, "A Matching Algorithm for Dynamic Ridesharing," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Mobility Services*, 2016.
- [5] EPJ Data Science, "A Data-Driven Approach for Assessing Biking Safety in Cities," *EPJ Data Science Journal*, 2021.
- [6] A. Chaudhary, "Assessing Service Quality of Ride-Hailing Bike Service within Kathmandu Valley," *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology*, 2024.
- [7] S. K. Ma, O. Wolfson, and P. Santi, "Real-Time City-Scale Ridesharing via Linear Assignment Problems," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2019.

Smart Electric Line Damage Detection System

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Abstract—Overhead electric distribution lines are highly vulnerable to environmental disturbances such as vegetation interference, conductor sagging, mechanical stress, and unexpected line breakage. Traditional monitoring systems mainly focus on electrical fault detection and often fail to identify physical threats before they lead to outages. This project presents a fully implemented smart monitoring system that integrates sensor-based detection, camera-based visual monitoring, edge computing, and a Digital Twin dashboard for real-time fault identification and preventive maintenance. The system utilizes ultrasonic sensing for sag detection, continuity monitoring for line break identification, vibration sensing for impact detection, and OpenCV-based camera analysis for vegetation proximity monitoring. All data processing is performed locally using Raspberry Pi to ensure low latency and reliability even in limited connectivity environments. The Digital Twin dashboard provides live system visualization, status alerts, and fault location indication. The implemented prototype demonstrates accurate real-time detection, automatic alert generation, and relay-based disconnection during critical conditions, offering a scalable solution for smart grid monitoring.

Keywords— Overhead Line Monitoring, Edge Computing, Vegetation Detection, Line Break Detection, Digital Twin, Predictive Maintenance.

INTRODUCTION

Power distribution networks rely heavily on overhead transmission and distribution lines. These lines are vulnerable to environmental factors including □ Tree branch growth near conductors ,Wind-induced mechanical oscillations ,Thermal expansion causing conductor sag ,Accidental breakage due to external impact. These problems can result in power interruptions, equipment damage, fire hazards, and safety risks to the public. In many cases, faults are detected only after service disruption occurs, leading to increased downtime and maintenance costs. Traditional fault detection systems mainly focus on monitoring electrical parameters such as current, voltage, and frequency. While these systems are effective in detecting short circuits, overcurrent conditions, and ground faults, they are limited in identifying mechanical and environmental threats such as sagging conductors or approaching tree branches. As a result, most existing systems operate reactively rather than predictively. Manual inspection is still widely used to

monitor physical conditions of overhead lines. However, this approach is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and inefficient, especially in remote or rural areas. Additionally, periodic inspections cannot provide continuous real-time monitoring, increasing the risk of unnoticed damage. By combining physical sensing and intelligent processing, the proposed system shifts the monitoring approach from reactive fault detection to proactive risk prevention. The overall objective of this work is to enhance power distribution reliability, improve operational safety, and reduce maintenance response time through intelligent monitoring and early warning mechanisms.

I. RELATED WORKS

Several research works have been carried out in the area of overhead power line monitoring to improve reliability and reduce outages. Traditional protection systems mainly detect electrical faults such as short circuits, overloads, and ground faults using relays and circuit breakers. In recent years, IoT-based monitoring solutions have been introduced, where sensors are deployed along transmission lines to measure parameters such as temperature, vibration, tilt, and sag. These systems enable remote monitoring and data collection but often rely heavily on centralized cloud platforms for processing and analysis. Some researchers have proposed ultrasonic-based sag detection systems to measure the vertical distance of conductors from a reference point, helping to identify excessive sag caused by thermal expansion or mechanical stress. Other studies have explored computer vision and drone-based inspection methods to detect vegetation encroachment near power lines. While these approaches improve detection accuracy, drone systems require manual operation and are not suitable for continuous monitoring. Additionally, vibration-based monitoring systems have been studied to detect abnormal oscillations due to wind or impact, but they are usually implemented as standalone solutions. Despite these advancements, most existing approaches focus on a single fault detection mechanism and lack integration into a unified architecture. This gap in integrated and predictive monitoring motivates the development of a comprehensive smart overhead line damage detection system as proposed in this project.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is a fully implemented Smart Overhead Electric Line Damage Detection and Predictive Monitoring System designed to continuously monitor the physical condition of overhead distribution lines and detect potential hazards before they lead to major failures

Fig1: Proposed Methodology Framework

The core idea of the system is to shift from reactive fault detection to predictive and preventive monitoring. Instead of identifying faults after power interruption occurs, the system continuously analyzes physical conditions and generates early warnings. The implemented prototype consists of: Vibration sensor for mechanical disturbance detection, Continuity monitoring circuit for breakage detection, Camera module for vegetation proximity monitoring, Raspberry Pi as edge processing unit, Web-based Digital Twin dashboard for visualization. All data processing and decision-making are performed locally using edge computing, ensuring low latency and minimal dependence on internet connectivity. The proposed system operates in continuous monitoring mode. Sensors collect real-time data from the physical environment, and the edge processor analyzes this data using predefined thresholds and algorithms. The system classifies operational states into three categories: Safe Condition, Warning Condition, Critical Condition. If a critical condition is detected, the system activates automatic protective actions and generates alerts through the dashboard. The integration of multiple sensing mechanisms ensures higher reliability and fault detection accuracy compared to single-parameter monitoring systems.

The architecture of the proposed system is organized into five structured layers to ensure clarity, scalability, and modular design. Physical layer, edge processing layer, communication layer, digital twin layer, ui layer.

Physical layer:

This is the real-world layer where the actual electric transmission line exists.

It includes: Overhead electric conductors, Transmission poles, Surrounding environment (trees, weather, wind conditions). Sensors used in this layer are tilt sensor (detects abnormal leaning of poles or line displacement), Vibration Sensor (Detects excessive mechanical vibrations caused by

wind, impact, or tree contact), Temperature Sensor (Monitors overheating of conductors, which may indicate overload or fault conditions), camera (Captures images of the overhead line to detect tree branches, sagging, or physical obstruction). This layer continuously senses the physical condition of the electric line.

Edge Processing Layer

The main purpose of this layer is local Data Processing and Fault Detection and the components used is Raspberry pi.

This layer receives raw data from sensors and process it locally and it performs threshold value comparison, image processing, fault detection, alert generation.

Communication Layer

The main purpose of this layer is to secure data transmission. This layer transfers processed data from the edge device to the cloud server. It ensures secure and reliable communication.

It does not analyze data — it only acts as a bridge between edge and cloud.

Digital Twin Layer

Virtual Representation of Physical System is the objective of this layer where this layer creates a real-time virtual copy of the physical electric line. It mirrors sensor data and system status dynamically and it helps in visualization, simulation, and predictive maintenance planning.

User Interface Layer

This is the top layer where users interact with the system. It includes monitoring dashboard, real time alerts, maintenance in sights. Monitoring dashboard displays line health, sensor readings, fault location, graphical representation, system performance and real time alerts ie when a fault occurs warning notification appears, alarm will be triggered and sms notification will be provided.

The workflow of the architecture is

- Sensors collect physical data.
- Edge device processes and analyzes data.
- Fault detection algorithm classifies condition.
- Alerts are generated locally.
- Data is transmitted through IoT gateway.
- Cloud stores and analyzes data.
- Digital twin updates in real time.
- Dashboard displays system status to user.

This layered architecture ensures efficient data flow from physical sensing to intelligent visualization, enabling a reliable, scalable, and preventive monitoring solution for overhead electric distribution systems.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the implementation and testing of the Smart Overhead Electric Line Damage Detection System using Edge Computing and Digital Twin demonstrate that the proposed architecture is capable of accurately detecting multiple fault conditions in real time and providing reliable monitoring support. During experimental evaluation, various fault scenarios such as wire sagging, excessive vibration, tree branch interference, and complete line breakage were artificially simulated on the prototype setup to assess system performance. The ultrasonic sensor successfully detected variations in conductor height and accurately classified normal, warning, and critical sag conditions based on predefined thresholds. The vibration sensor effectively captured abnormal mechanical disturbances caused by simulated impacts and continuous oscillations, and the edge processing unit filtered noise to avoid false alarms. The camera module, integrated with OpenCV-based image processing, successfully identified the intrusion of objects into predefined safety zones, demonstrating the system's ability to predict hazardous tree branch contact before physical damage occurs. In the case of line breakage, the continuity monitoring mechanism immediately detected circuit interruption and triggered a critical alert with minimal delay. Since data processing and fault classification were performed locally at the edge device, response time was significantly reduced compared to cloud-dependent systems, ensuring near-instantaneous alert generation. The digital twin dashboard accurately mirrored real-time physical changes, displaying sensor readings, fault status, and alert notifications without noticeable lag, thereby enhancing situational awareness and remote monitoring capability. The system also maintained operational reliability during temporary network interruptions due to local data storage and processing. Overall, the experimental results confirm that integrating multi-sensor monitoring, edge computing, secure communication, and digital twin visualization provides a robust, scalable, and preventive solution for overhead electric line monitoring. Compared to conventional systems that primarily detect faults after power interruption, the proposed system enables early warning, predictive maintenance, and automated alert mechanisms, thereby improving safety, reducing manual inspection requirements, and enhancing overall grid reliability.

Fig 2: The live dashboard

IV. FUTURE WORK

The future scope of the Smart Overhead Electric Line Damage Detection System includes enhancing detection accuracy using advanced AI and deep learning models for improved vegetation and fault identification. GPS integration can enable precise fault location tracking, while cloud-based analytics can support predictive maintenance using historical data. The system can also be expanded with solar-powered edge units for remote deployment and a mobile application for real-time alerts. In large-scale implementation, multiple monitoring nodes can be connected to create a distributed smart grid monitoring network, making the system more scalable, intelligent, and suitable for modern power distribution infrastructure.

V. CONCLUSION

The Smart Overhead Electric Line Damage Detection System using Edge Computing and Digital Twin successfully demonstrates an intelligent and preventive approach to monitoring power distribution lines. By integrating multi-sensor technology, computer vision, local edge processing, and real-time dashboard visualization, the system is capable of detecting sagging wires, vegetation interference, vibration disturbances, and line breakage efficiently. The use of edge computing reduces response time and minimizes dependency on continuous internet connectivity, ensuring reliable operation even in remote areas. The Digital Twin dashboard enhances situational awareness by providing a real-time virtual representation of the physical system. Overall, the implemented prototype proves that combining sensing, intelligent processing, and automated alert mechanisms can significantly improve safety, reliability, and maintenance efficiency in overhead electric line monitoring systems.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

REFERENCES

- [1] Yogita Raut, Aditi Shinde and Purva Pokale, Smart monitoring & fault detection system for power transmission lines, 2025
- [2] Ashvini N. Jadhav, Sneha M. More, Sushma S. Pawar, Tushar P. Pandhi, IoT based electric pole safety system, 2021
- [3] Vijay R. Patil et al., "IoT Based Transmission Line Fault Detection", IJERT, 2024A.
- [4] Yuting Wu, Tianjian Liao, Fan Chen et al., "Overhead Power Line Damage Detection: An Innovative Approach Using Enhanced YOLOv8", MDPI Sensors, 2023
- [5] V. N. Kuryanov et al., "Detection of Damage Sites on Overhead Power Lines with a Voltage of 110 kV or Higher", IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 2022.
- [6] Bhanuprasad Nuthalapati & Umesh Kumar Sinha., "Detection of downed or Broken power line Fault not touching the ground".
- [7] Arman Alahyari, Anton Hinneck, Rahim Tariverdi, David Pozo., "Segmentation and Defect Classification of the Power Line Insulators: A Deep Learning-based Approach".
- [8] Ahmed, Manam & Khan, Md Rabbi. "Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Digital Twins for Energy Efficiency in Smart Grids." Review of Applied Science and Technology, Vol. 4, No. 02, 2025.
- [9] Kumari, Namita; Sharma, Ankush; Tran, "A Comprehensive Review of Digital Twin Technology for Grid-Connected Microgrid Systems: State

of the Art, Potential and Challenges Faced.” Energies, Vol. 16, Issue 14, 2023.

- [10] S. K. Satyanarayana and S. N. Chandra Shekhar, Underground cable fault detection using iot,2024
- [11] A. Firos ,N. Prakash ,M. Soni ,Fault detection in power transmission lines using AI Model,2023
- [12] L. Goswami and P. Agrawal , IOT based Diagnosing of fault detection in power tansmission through Google firebase Database,2020

Smart Fishing System

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Abstract-- Fishing is a vital source of livelihood for millions, especially in coastal regions. However, traditional fishing methods often lead to the unintentional capture of poisonous or endangered fish, posing health risks, economic loss, and environmental damage. To address this socially relevant issue, this project proposes a smart underwater fish detection and classification system that assists fishermen in identifying fish species in real time before capture. The system uses a waterproof ultrasonic sensor to detect fish presence and a camera module to capture underwater images. These images are analyzed using a pre-trained machine learning model running on a Raspberry Pi, which classifies the fish based on known species data. The output, including the fish name and a warning if it is poisonous or endangered, is displayed as plain text on a compact OLED screen for easy understanding. Key components of this system include Raspberry Pi, Endoscopic-CAM, JSN-SR04T waterproof ultrasonic sensor, and a 0.96" I2C OLED display. The device is powered using a laptop, making it simple to operate and cost-effective for small-scale fishermen. In addition to ensuring safe and informed fishing, the system also spreads awareness about protected species, helps reduce accidental by-catch, and supports sustainable marine practices. The proposed device thus combines the power of AI, embedded systems, and marine safety, offering a technically sound and socially impactful solution.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fishing plays a vital role in global food security, economic stability, and employment, particularly in coastal and rural communities. Millions of people depend directly or indirectly on fishing for their livelihood and daily nutrition. Traditionally, fishermen rely on experience, environmental cues, and manual observation to determine suitable fishing locations. However, these conventional methods are highly uncertain and often inefficient, leading to excessive fuel consumption, time wastage, and inconsistent catch outcomes. Moreover, the increasing pressure on marine ecosystems due to overfishing and accidental by-catch has created serious ecological concerns. The need for intelligent, technology-driven fishing solutions has therefore become more important than ever in order to improve efficiency while preserving marine biodiversity.

Although modern fish-finding devices such as sonar systems are available in the market, they primarily detect underwater objects based on echo signals and cannot differentiate between fish species. This limitation prevents fishermen from identifying whether the detected fish are commercially valuable, poisonous, or endangered. The absence of species-level identification increases the risk of unintentional capture of protected marine life, leading to legal penalties, environmental degradation, and economic losses. Furthermore, most advanced marine monitoring systems are expensive, bulky, and require specialized training, making them inaccessible to small-scale fishermen and beginners. Hence, there is a significant demand for a low-cost, portable, and intelligent system capable of real-time fish detection and classification to support safer and more sustainable fishing practices.

To address these challenges, this project proposes a Smart Fishing System that integrates ultrasonic sensing, embedded computing, and artificial intelligence for underwater fish detection and species classification. The system employs a waterproof ultrasonic sensor to detect the presence and approximate distance of fish underwater. Upon detection, a camera module captures real-time underwater images, which are processed using a lightweight machine learning model deployed on a Raspberry Pi platform. The model classifies fish species based on trained image datasets and retrieves associated information such as nutritional value, toxicity level, and conservation status from a local database. The results are displayed on an OLED interface in a clear and user-friendly format, along with actionable recommendations on whether to proceed with casting the fishing net or rod.

The proposed system is designed to be compact, energy-efficient, and cost-effective, ensuring accessibility for small-scale fishermen. It operates as a standalone embedded device without requiring continuous internet connectivity, making it suitable for remote fishing locations. In addition to improving catch efficiency, the system contributes to sustainable fishing by reducing accidental by-catch and promoting awareness of endangered species. The modular design also allows future enhancements such as integration with environmental sensors (temperature, pH, turbidity), GPS tagging, and cloud-based data storage. By combining AI-driven image processing with real-time sensing technology, the Smart Fishing System offers

a socially impactful and technologically advanced solution for modernizing traditional fishing practices.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1

Vrushali Pagire *et al.* (2022) presented a comparative study of three deep learning object detection architectures—YOLOv3, SSD MobileNet v2, and Faster R-CNN ResNet50—for underwater fish detection using the Fish4Knowledge dataset containing over 25,000 annotated images. The study addressed underwater imaging challenges such as color distortion, low contrast, and noise through preprocessing techniques including histogram equalization, color correction, and noise filtering. The models were trained using TensorFlow on NVIDIA GPUs and evaluated using precision, recall, and mean Average Precision (mAP). Among the tested models, SSD MobileNet v2 achieved the highest performance with 98.21% mAP and faster inference speed compared to the others, demonstrating an effective balance between computational efficiency and detection accuracy. However, the system required GPU-based computation and focused only on fish detection rather than species classification. This work provides a strong foundation for selecting lightweight models suitable for adaptation into embedded systems such as Raspberry Pi using TensorFlow Lite.

Paper 2

S. Andrades *et al.* (2020) proposed a two-stage deep learning framework for temperate fish detection and classification. The approach employed YOLOv3 for object detection and a separate Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) blocks for species classification. The dataset consisted of approximately 7,000 annotated images representing 15 fish species captured under varying underwater lighting and environmental conditions. YOLO first generated bounding boxes around detected fish, after which the cropped images were passed to the CNN for classification. This separation of detection and classification tasks improved species identification accuracy, particularly in low-visibility environments. Although the dual-stage architecture enhanced accuracy and robustness, it increased computational complexity, memory usage, and inference latency, making it less suitable for low-power embedded deployment. The study highlights the trade-off between accuracy and system complexity in real-time underwater applications.

Paper 3

Z. Li *et al.* (2023) introduced a lightweight deep learning model for marine fish detection by improving YOLOv5s through the integration of GhostNet modules and attention mechanisms to reduce computational redundancy. Using the Fish9 dataset containing nine coral reef fish species, the researchers applied pruning and quantization techniques to minimize floating-point operations (FLOPs) while maintaining detection performance. The enhanced model achieved a 19% reduction in size and a 3% increase in accuracy compared to standard YOLOv5s, with real-time inference speed reaching 52.7 frames per second on a mid-tier GPU. Although training required GPU resources and the dataset scope was limited, the study demonstrated that

optimized lightweight architectures can achieve high accuracy with reduced computational demands. This research strongly supports the feasibility of deploying compressed deep learning models on resource-constrained embedded platforms.

Paper 4

J. Zhang *et al.* (2021) conducted a comprehensive review of deep learning-based object detection techniques applied in fish aquaculture, analyzing over 50 research studies. The review compared commonly used architectures such as YOLO, SSD, and Faster R-CNN in terms of accuracy, inference speed, and practical applicability. It highlighted key environmental challenges affecting underwater detection systems, including turbidity, light scattering, occlusion, and dynamic backgrounds. Furthermore, the study emphasized the transition from cloud-based processing toward edge-AI deployment for real-time field applications. While the paper did not present experimental validation or hardware implementation, it provided critical insights into existing research gaps, particularly the need for energy-efficient, portable systems capable of operating in real-world marine environments. This review establishes the theoretical background and identifies the importance of embedded AI solutions for practical fishing systems.

Paper 5

Kandimalla *et al.* (2021) developed a deep learning-based multi-task framework for automated detection, classification, and counting of fish in river passages using underwater camera systems. The system utilized a CNN-based object detector combined with a tracking algorithm to prevent duplicate counting of fish across frames. The dataset comprised approximately 80,000 real-world underwater images, enabling the model to achieve over 90% detection accuracy with a counting error below 5%. The integration of detection, classification, and tracking provided a comprehensive ecological monitoring solution. However, the implementation required GPU-based hardware and continuous power supply, limiting its portability and suitability for small-scale field applications. Despite these limitations, the study demonstrates the potential of integrating multiple AI tasks into a unified framework for advanced aquatic monitoring.

Paper 6

Dhruv Rathi *et al.* (2018) proposed an underwater fish species classification system using a Convolutional Neural Network trained on the Fish Recognition Ground Truth Dataset. The preprocessing pipeline included color correction, noise reduction, and edge enhancement to improve image clarity under underwater conditions. The CNN architecture consisted of three convolutional layers, two fully connected layers, and a softmax classifier, achieving an overall classification accuracy of 96.29%. While the system demonstrated the effectiveness of CNNs for marine species identification, it focused solely on classification and did not incorporate object detection or real-time embedded deployment. Additionally, model training required significant computational resources. This work laid the foundational understanding of AI-driven fish classification, which can be extended to real-time detection systems integrated with embedded hardware platforms.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The Smart Fishing System is an intelligent and embedded decision-support platform designed to assist fishermen in identifying fish presence, species type, and capture suitability in real time. The system integrates ultrasonic sensing, underwater image acquisition, deep learning-based fish detection, and rule-based decision logic into a Raspberry Pi-based portable device. It ensures efficient and sustainable fishing by reducing manual effort and minimizing unnecessary casting attempts.

The system provides role-independent usage, meaning it is designed to be beginner-friendly while also beneficial for professional fishermen. The ultrasonic sensor detects fish presence, and upon detection, the camera captures underwater images for processing. AI models identify fish species and count their number, while a structured database provides nutritional information such as protein, fat, and calorie values. Based on predefined sustainability rules, the system outputs a final recommendation: CAST or DO NOT CAST. By combining embedded systems, artificial intelligence, and real-time decision logic, the Smart Fishing System enhances fishing efficiency while promoting responsible fishing practices.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: Smart Fishing System Architecture

Figure 1 illustrates the multi-layer architecture of the Smart Fishing System, designed for efficient real-time processing on Raspberry Pi 4. The system consists of a hardware layer, image processing layer, AI inference layer, database layer, and decision support layer.

The hardware layer includes the Raspberry Pi 4, JSN-SR04T waterproof ultrasonic sensor, underwater USB camera, and 3.5-inch SPI TFT display. The sensor continuously monitors underwater distance and triggers the image capture process when fish are detected within a predefined threshold. The captured frames are processed through image enhancement techniques before being passed to the AI models. YOLOv8 Nano performs fish detection, while MobileNetV2 classifies species. The database module stores nutritional and sustainability-related information. Finally, the decision engine evaluates all parameters and displays the output through the graphical user interface.

C. Modules

• Sensor and Detection Module

This module continuously monitors underwater conditions using the JSN-SR04T ultrasonic sensor. When the measured distance falls below a defined threshold, it triggers the image acquisition process. This event-driven approach minimizes unnecessary computation and optimizes power usage.

• Image Acquisition and Processing Module

The underwater USB camera captures multiple frames when activated. These frames undergo preprocessing techniques such as RGB color correction, Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE), and gamma correction to improve clarity under low-light and turbid water conditions.

• Fish Detection Module

This module utilizes YOLOv8 Nano, a lightweight object detection model optimized for edge devices. It detects fish within frames, generates bounding boxes, calculates confidence scores, and determines fish count in real time.

• Species Classification Module

After detection, cropped fish regions are passed to a MobileNetV2 convolutional neural network that identifies fish species. The model is fine-tuned using a custom fish dataset to ensure classification accuracy while maintaining low computational overhead.

• Decision Support Module

This module implements rule-based conditional logic. It evaluates fish count, edibility, poisonous status, and endangered classification to generate a final recommendation of CAST or DO NOT CAST. The logic ensures explainability and supports sustainable fishing practices.

• Database Management Module

The SQLite database securely stores species details, including protein, fat, calories per 100g, edible status, poisonous indication, and endangered classification. The database is queried after classification to retrieve relevant information for final decision-making and display.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Design

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

Figure 2 represents the interaction between the fisherman and the Smart Fishing System. The fisherman activates the system, and the ultrasonic sensor monitors underwater activity. When fish presence is detected, the camera captures images and initiates AI-based detection and classification. The system processes data, retrieves nutritional information,

and displays the final recommendation. The use case highlights automated sensing, intelligent processing, and real-time feedback within a single embedded platform.

B. Implementation Details

• Frontend Technologies

The user interface of the Smart Fishing System is developed using Python-based GUI frameworks such as Tkinter. The interface displays fish count, species name, nutritional values, and the final CAST or DO NOT CAST recommendation. OpenCV is used for image capture and frame handling, while graphical elements are designed to ensure clarity and usability even in outdoor fishing environments. The interface is lightweight to ensure smooth operation on Raspberry Pi hardware.

• Backend Technologies

The backend is implemented using Python and optimized for Raspberry Pi OS (64-bit). The system integrates OpenCV for image processing, Ultralytics YOLOv8 for fish detection, TensorFlow/Keras for MobileNetV2-based classification, NumPy for numerical computations, and SQLite3 for local database management. Threading is implemented to allow simultaneous sensor monitoring and image processing without blocking system performance. The modular structure ensures scalability and maintainability.

• Security Mechanisms

Although the system operates as a standalone embedded device, security measures are implemented at both hardware and software levels. GPIO voltage protection is ensured through a voltage divider on the ultrasonic sensor's Echo pin to prevent damage to the Raspberry Pi. Software-level exception handling manages camera failures, model loading errors, and sensor misreads. Local database access is restricted within the application environment to prevent unauthorized modifications.

• Database Management

The system uses SQLite as a lightweight and embedded database solution suitable for Raspberry Pi deployment. The database stores fish species details, nutritional information, and sustainability indicators. Efficient indexing and optimized queries are implemented to ensure minimal latency during data retrieval. Since SQLite operates locally within the device, it eliminates network dependency and ensures reliable offline functionality during fishing operations. medicine expiry tracking and user interactions while ensuring minimal latency in data retrieval.

V. RESULTS

The proposed Smart Fishing System was successfully implemented using Raspberry Pi 5 integrated with an underwater camera, ultrasonic sensor, and OLED display

module. Experimental evaluation was conducted in controlled water tank and semi-natural pond environments to assess detection accuracy, processing speed, and system reliability. The underwater camera captured real-time frames which were enhanced through preprocessing techniques to reduce underwater noise and improve clarity before being passed to the pretrained AI model for classification. The system achieved an average fish species identification accuracy of approximately 88–92% under moderate lighting and clear water conditions. The ultrasonic sensor effectively assisted in detecting object proximity, reducing unnecessary image processing and improving computational efficiency.

The decision logic module analyzed classification results using stored database information and generated appropriate outputs including fish name, nutritional information, sustainability warnings, and casting recommendations, which were displayed on the OLED screen with an average response time of 1.8–2.5 seconds. The system operated within acceptable power limits, making it suitable for portable deployment. Although performance slightly decreased in highly turbid water conditions, overall results demonstrate that the Smart Fishing System effectively supports intelligent fish detection and decision-making, thereby enhancing fishing efficiency while promoting sustainable practices.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Smart Fishing System presented in this work successfully integrates underwater imaging, ultrasonic sensing, and artificial intelligence to provide an intelligent and real-time fish detection and identification solution. By combining hardware components such as Raspberry Pi 5, underwater camera, and OLED display with a pretrained AI model and decision logic module, the system is capable of detecting fish presence, identifying species, and delivering useful recommendations to fishermen. The experimental results confirm that the system achieves reliable accuracy and responsive performance under practical conditions, demonstrating its feasibility for real-world deployment.

Furthermore, the proposed system contributes toward promoting sustainable fishing practices by providing warnings for protected species and offering informed casting instructions based on detected data. Although environmental factors such as low visibility may affect accuracy, the overall system performance validates the effectiveness of integrating embedded systems with artificial intelligence for smart aquatic monitoring. Future enhancements can focus on improving image processing under extreme conditions, optimizing model efficiency, and incorporating additional environmental sensors to further strengthen system robustness and applicability.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The Smart Fishing System can be further improved by integrating advanced deep learning models optimized for underwater environments to enhance classification accuracy under low-light and turbid conditions. Future enhancements may include the addition of environmental sensors such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and salinity sensors for comprehensive aquatic monitoring, as well as GPS integration for location-based fish tracking and yield prediction. Incorporating IoT-based cloud connectivity and mobile application support can enable remote monitoring and data analytics. Expanding the training dataset to include more fish species, implementing real-time fish size estimation and population counting, and optimizing the system for lower power consumption and faster edge processing will further strengthen the system's reliability, scalability, and practical deployment in sustainable fisheries management.

REFERENCES

1. S. Li, L. Wang, and J. Chen, "Underwater Fish Detection Using Deep Learning Techniques," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 123456–123467, 2020.
2. R. Girshick, "Fast R-CNN," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, Santiago, Chile, 2015, pp. 1440–1448.
3. J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi, "You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016, pp. 779–788.
4. M. Boom, P. X. Huang, J. He, and R. B. Fisher, "Supporting Ground-Truth Annotation of Image Datasets Using Clustering," in *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR)*, Tsukuba, Japan, 2012, pp. 1542–1545.
5. A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, "ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS)*, 2012, pp. 1097–1105.
6. K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016, pp. 770–778.

Portable Eye Controlled Mouse System

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Abstract-- In today's rapidly evolving digital world, ensuring technology is inclusive and accessible to all is more important than ever—especially for individuals with physical disabilities who are often limited in their ability to interact with conventional computer systems. This project proposes a novel solution in the form of an offline, portable eye controlled cursor system that allows users to seamlessly navigate and interact with a computer using just their eye movements, eliminating the need for a traditional mouse or keyboard. The core of this system relies on a camera-based eye-tracking mechanism that accurately detects and maps the user's gaze to control the position of the on-screen cursor. In addition to gaze based navigation, the system incorporates intuitive click functionalities such as blink-to-click, continues blink for scrolling down. To further enhance usability, especially in scenarios involving text input, an on-screen keyboard has been integrated, enabling users to type efficiently using gaze focus alone. The inclusion of offline voice command support adds an extra layer of flexibility, allowing users to perform actions through spoken instructions without the need for an internet connection. This system especially unique is its fully offline operation and portable design using Raspberry Pi 4 and other essential languages and libraries such as Python, OpenCV, MediaPipe, making it suitable for use in remote environments, homes, and educational institutions. By eliminating the dependency on external infrastructure or cloud processing, the solution ensures privacy, speed, and reliability while promoting digital independence for differently-abled users. This project stands at the intersection of human computer interaction (HCI), computer vision, and assistive technology, and showcases how simple, low-cost hardware paired with intelligent design can bring meaningful change to people's lives.

Keywords— Eye tracking, assistive technology, human computer interaction, computer vision, gaze control, portable system, accessibility

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of digital technology has transformed nearly every aspect of modern life, including education, healthcare, communication, governance, and employment. Computers and smart devices have become essential tools for productivity and social interaction. However, despite these advancements, accessibility remains a significant challenge for individuals with physical disabilities. Traditional input devices such as keyboards and mice require fine motor control and coordinated hand movements, which are not feasible for users suffering from paralysis, spinal cord injuries, muscular dystrophy, cerebral palsy, or other neuromuscular disorders. This limitation creates a digital divide that restricts their ability to independently access information, communicate effectively, and participate fully in society. Ensuring inclusive and barrier free access to computing systems is therefore both a technological necessity and a social responsibility.

Assistive technologies have emerged as powerful solutions to bridge this accessibility gap. Among various alternative interaction methods—such as speech recognition, gesture control, and brain-computer interfaces—eye-tracking systems have gained significant attention due to their non-invasive nature and reliability. Eye movement is one of the few motor functions that remains unaffected in many individuals with severe physical impairments. By detecting and interpreting gaze direction, it becomes possible to translate eye movements into meaningful computer commands. Over the past decade, advances in computer vision, machine learning, and embedded systems have enabled the development of camera-based gaze tracking solutions that eliminate the need for expensive infrared sensors or specialized hardware. However, many existing systems remain costly, complex, or dependent on continuous internet connectivity, limiting their practicality in low-resource or remote environments.

Another major concern with existing gaze-based systems is their reliance on cloud processing and high-end computing platforms. Internet-dependent systems introduce latency issues, privacy risks, and operational instability in areas with poor connectivity.

For assistive devices, reliability and real-time responsiveness are critical factors because users depend on them for daily communication and interaction. Moreover, commercially available eye-tracking devices are often expensive, making them inaccessible to economically disadvantaged users. There is therefore a strong need for a portable, low-cost, and fully offline eye-controlled system that ensures privacy, affordability, and ease of deployment without compromising performance or accuracy.

In response to these challenges, this paper presents a Portable Eye-Controlled Mouse System designed to enable complete computer interaction through gaze tracking, blink detection, and offline voice commands. The system utilizes a camera-based eye detection mechanism integrated with embedded hardware to provide real-time cursor control, click functionality, scrolling operations, and text input via a virtual keyboard. By operating entirely offline, the proposed solution ensures data privacy, reduces latency, and enhances reliability. The portable design makes it suitable for use in homes, hospitals, educational institutions, and remote areas. Through the integration of human-computer interaction principles, computer vision techniques, and assistive system design, this work aims to promote digital independence and significantly improve the quality of life for differently-abled individuals.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Soukupova T et al.[1] proposed a real-time eye blink detection method using facial landmarks and Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR). Their work focused on detecting eye closure using geometric relationships between eye landmarks extracted from facial images. The proposed method demonstrated high accuracy and low computational cost, making it suitable for real-time applications. This research laid the foundation for blink-based click detection systems in assistive technologies.

Zhang X et al.[2] introduced an appearance-based gaze estimation model using convolutional neural networks trained on large-scale datasets. Their system was capable of estimating gaze direction under varying lighting conditions and head poses. The research contributed significantly to robust gaze-tracking techniques without requiring specialized hardware. However, the approach required high computational power, limiting portability.

Kanan C et al. [3] This study presented a real-time eye tracking framework using computer vision techniques for detecting pupil movement and blinking patterns. The system utilized facial landmark detection and threshold-based blink recognition. It demonstrated improved responsiveness and was applicable in assistive communication systems. The research emphasized low-latency implementation for practical use.

Betke M et al. [4] developed one of the early camera-based eye tracking systems designed specifically for individuals with severe disabilities. Their system allowed users to control a computer cursor using eye gaze without requiring wearable sensors. This work proved that low-cost camera systems could

be used as effective assistive devices, influencing future gaze-controlled interaction systems.

Hansen D W et al. [5] Their research discussed different gaze estimation methods, including feature-based approaches, appearance-based models, and 3D model-based tracking systems. The paper also analyzed system challenges such as head pose variation, illumination changes, calibration requirements, and computational complexity. This work provided a structured overview of gaze-tracking technologies and highlighted the importance of developing accurate, real-time, and user-friendly systems for assistive applications.

Krafka K. et al. [6] The authors developed a large-scale dataset and trained a convolutional neural network to predict gaze position under varying head poses, lighting conditions, and device types. Their work demonstrated that accurate gaze estimation could be achieved without specialized infrared hardware, making eye tracking more accessible to the general public.. This research significantly contributed to appearance-based gaze estimation techniques and inspired the development of software-driven, camera-based eye tracking systems suitable for assistive applications.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The proposed Portable Eye-Controlled Mouse System is a compact, offline assistive platform that enables complete computer control using eye movements, blinking gestures, and voice commands. The system eliminates the need for traditional input devices by providing real-time cursor movement, clicking, scrolling, and text entry through computer vision-based gaze tracking. A modular architecture ensures reliability, scalability, and ease of implementation. The hardware is centered on the Raspberry Pi, integrated with a USB camera for continuous face and eye capture, and a microphone for offline voice recognition. All processing is performed locally, ensuring privacy and independence from internet connectivity. The portable design allows operation using standard power banks, making it suitable for diverse environments. The software is developed in Python using OpenCV for real-time image processing and MediaPipe for facial landmark and eye tracking. The processing pipeline includes frame capture, face detection, gaze estimation, cursor mapping, and action triggering with optimized latency. The system supports three interaction modes: gaze-based cursor navigation, blink-based click and scrolling operations, and offline voice commands. Gaze direction is mapped to screen coordinates, short blinks trigger clicks, prolonged blinks enable scrolling, and a virtual keyboard supports dwell-time-based text entry. By integrating these multimodal controls into a single embedded platform, the system ensures accessibility, portability, affordability, and digital independence for physically challenged users. Furthermore, the system is designed to maintain stable performance under moderate lighting variations and minor head movements by incorporating smoothing and filtering techniques during gaze estimation. These optimization strategies reduce jitter in cursor motion and enhance user comfort during prolonged usage. By combining embedded computing, real-time

vision processing, and multimodal interaction, the proposed system delivers an efficient, secure, and user-centric assistive solution that promotes digital inclusion and independence.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: Portable Eye controlled system architecture

C. Working

The Portable Eye-Controlled Mouse System operates through a structured real-time processing pipeline that begins with visual data acquisition using a USB camera connected to the Raspberry Pi 4. The camera continuously captures live video frames of the user’s face, which are processed using OpenCV for frame extraction, resizing, grayscale conversion, and noise reduction to ensure stable input quality. These preprocessed frames are then passed to the MediaPipe Face Mesh module, which detects and extracts high-precision facial landmarks. From these landmarks, the eye regions are isolated, and specific key points around the eyelids and iris are identified. Using geometric relationships between these landmarks, the system computes the gaze direction and estimates the pupil position relative to the screen. The calculated gaze vector is then mapped to corresponding screen coordinates through a coordinate transformation algorithm, enabling real-time cursor positioning.

To enable interaction beyond cursor movement, the system incorporates blink detection and gesture interpretation mechanisms. The Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) is continuously calculated using selected eyelid landmark points to determine whether the eyes are open or closed. When the EAR value falls below a predefined threshold for a short duration, it is classified as a voluntary blink and interpreted as a left-click command. A prolonged blink exceeding a specified time threshold triggers scrolling functionality, while optional patterns such as double blinks can be mapped to right-click actions. The processed gaze coordinates and gesture signals are passed to the Cursor Control Engine, where smoothing techniques such as moving average filtering are applied to reduce jitter and ensure stable cursor movement. Finally, PyAutoGUI is used to convert these processed signals into operating system-level actions, including cursor movement, clicking, and scrolling, thereby enabling seamless control without traditional input devices.

In addition to vision-based interaction, the system integrates a gaze-based virtual keyboard and an offline voice command module to enhance usability. The on-screen keyboard allows users to select characters by focusing their gaze on specific

keys for a defined dwell time, after which the selected character is appended to a text buffer and rendered on the screen. For hands-free command execution, the microphone captures voice input, which is processed using an offline speech recognition engine to identify predefined commands such as open application, scroll, or close window. All processing, including video analysis, gaze estimation, blink detection, cursor control, virtual typing, and speech recognition, is performed locally on the Raspberry Pi 4 without cloud dependency. This fully offline architecture ensures low latency, enhanced privacy, and reliable operation, making the system suitable for assistive applications in homes, educational institutions, and remote environments.

IV CONCLUSION

This paper presented the design and implementation of a Portable Offline Eye-Controlled Mouse System aimed at enhancing digital accessibility for individuals with physical disabilities. The proposed system demonstrates how low-cost embedded hardware, specifically Raspberry Pi 4, combined with intelligent computer vision algorithms can enable seamless human-computer interaction without relying on traditional input devices such as a mouse or keyboard. By leveraging OpenCV for real-time video acquisition and preprocessing, MediaPipe Face Mesh for accurate facial landmark detection, and Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR)-based blink analysis for gesture interpretation, the system successfully translates natural eye movements into precise cursor navigation and click operations.

A key strength of the proposed architecture lies in its fully offline processing capability. All gaze estimation, blink detection, coordinate mapping, and speech recognition processes are executed locally on the Raspberry Pi platform without cloud dependency. This ensures enhanced privacy, reduced latency, improved reliability, and suitability for deployment in remote or resource-constrained environments. The integration of PyAutoGUI enables seamless interaction with the operating system by converting processed gaze coordinates and blink events into real-time cursor movement, clicking, scrolling, and automated text input operations. Furthermore, the incorporation of a gaze-based virtual keyboard and offline voice command module significantly improves usability, particularly in text-entry scenarios.

Experimental observations indicate that the system achieves stable cursor control under controlled lighting conditions with minimal computational overhead, making it practical for everyday usage in homes, educational institutions, and assistive care environments. The modular layered architecture ensures scalability and maintainability, allowing future integration of advanced filtering techniques, adaptive calibration mechanisms, or AI-based gaze prediction models to further enhance accuracy and user comfort.

The proposed portable eye-controlled cursor system successfully bridges the gap between assistive technology and affordable embedded computing. It demonstrates that meaningful accessibility solutions can be developed using cost-effective hardware and open-source software frameworks. By promoting independence, inclusivity, and digital empowerment, this system contributes significantly to the field of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), computer vision-

based assistive systems, and embedded intelligent interfaces. Future work may focus on improving robustness under dynamic lighting conditions, multi-user calibration support, and integration with IoT-enabled smart environments to further expand its real-world applicability.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

One major direction for future work involves improving gaze estimation accuracy through advanced machine learning and deep learning models. While the current system utilizes facial landmark detection and geometric gaze mapping techniques, integrating convolutional neural networks (CNNs) or lightweight transformer-based vision models optimized for edge devices can significantly enhance robustness under varying lighting conditions, head poses, and occlusions. Implementing adaptive calibration mechanisms that automatically adjust to individual eye characteristics would further improve personalization and long-term usability.

Another important enhancement lies in dynamic environmental adaptation. Future versions can incorporate automatic brightness normalization, infrared camera modules for low-light environments, and head pose compensation algorithms to maintain stability even when the user moves slightly. Multi-camera fusion techniques may also be explored to improve tracking precision and reduce gaze drift.

From a hardware perspective, optimization for lower-power embedded systems or custom AI accelerators (such as edge TPUs or neural compute sticks) can reduce latency and increase computational efficiency. The system could also be miniaturized into a wearable form factor such as smart glasses, making it more portable and discreet for daily use.

In terms of user interaction, future developments may include predictive text integration, adaptive dwell-time control, and context-aware gesture recognition to reduce cognitive load. The addition of emotion detection or fatigue monitoring using eye behaviour analytics could provide intelligent assistance and improve user comfort. Expanding the offline voice command module with natural language understanding capabilities would allow more conversational interaction with the system.

Integration with Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystems represents another promising extension. The system could be expanded to control smart home devices, wheelchairs, or assistive robotics platforms through gaze-based commands. This would transform the solution from a computer interaction tool into a comprehensive assistive control interface for smart environments.

For broader deployment, future research may focus on multi-language support, cross-platform compatibility (Linux, Windows, and macOS), and integration with accessibility APIs to ensure seamless operation across different operating systems. Cloud-assisted optional modes could also be explored for users who require advanced AI features while still maintaining privacy-preserving offline functionality as the default.

Finally, clinical validation and large-scale user testing with differently-abled individuals would provide quantitative performance metrics such as accuracy, response time, user satisfaction index, and long-term reliability analysis. Such studies would strengthen the system's applicability in rehabilitation centers, educational institutions, and assistive technology programs.

The future scope of the Portable Eye-Controlled Mouse System extends toward enhanced intelligence, improved adaptability, hardware optimization, smart environment integration, and large-scale validation. Continued research and refinement can transform this prototype into a highly robust, commercially viable, and universally accessible assistive human-computer interaction platform.

VI. REFERENCE

- Vo Ngoc Mai Anh; Hoang Kim Ngoc Anh; Vo Nhat Huy; Huynh Gia Huy; Minh Ly. "Improve Productivity and Quality Using Lean Six Sigma: A Case Study". *International Research Journal on Advanced Science Hub*, 5, 03, 2023, 71-83. doi: 10.47392/irjash.2023.016
- Somu C, Karthi A, Sanjay S, Karthikeyan R, Dinesh S and Ganesh N 2017 Synthesis of various forms of carbon nanotubes by arc-discharge methods—comprehensive review *Int. J. Res. Eng. Technol.* 4 IRJET- V4I164
- R. Devi Priya, R. Sivaraj, Ajith Abraham, T. Pravin, P. Sivasankar and N. Anitha. "MultiObjective Particle Swarm Optimization Based Preprocessing of Multi-Class Extremely Imbalanced Datasets".
- Susanta Saha; Sohini Mondal. "An in-depth analysis of the Entertainment Preferences before and after Covid- 19 among Engineering Students of West Bengal". *International Research Journal on Advanced Science Hub*, 5, 03, 2023, 91-102. doi: 10.47392/irjash.2023.018
- Ayush Kumar Bar; Avijit Kumar Chaudhuri. "Emotica.AI - A Customer feedback system using AI". *International Research Journal on Advanced Science Hub*, 5, 03, 2023, 103-110. doi: 10.47392/irjash.2023.019

Career Valley

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Abstract-The Smart Placement Assistance System is designed to automate and enhance campus placements. Placement preparation requires more than just academic performance; it demands structured skill tracking and personalized guidance. This proposed system utilizes the K-Means clustering machine learning algorithm to group students according to their readiness levels and skills. To bridge identified skill gaps, it provides targeted role matching, resume-building support, and personalized training recommendations. By offering an interactive student portal and an admin dashboard, the data-driven system streamlines the recruitment workflow, ensures objective candidate classification, and adapts dynamically to student progress to improve overall employability.

Keywords: Smart Placement, K-Means Clustering, Machine Learning, Recommendation Engine, Employability.

I INTRODUCTION

Placement preparation requires more than academic performance; it needs structured skill tracking and personalized guidance. Existing placement systems are primarily designed to manage student information, placement activities, and recruitment processes through web or mobile-based platforms. Current solutions focus on the centralized storage of student academic details, resumes, skills, and

placement records. These systems aim to streamline the overall placement workflow, reduce paperwork, and improve efficiency by adopting web-based architectures and cloud deployment. Furthermore, most existing solutions include dashboards that allow placement officers to monitor student data and manage recruitment activities.

Despite these functionalities, existing systems face significant drawbacks, primarily focusing on basic automation while lacking AI-driven features like automated resume shortlisting and predictive placement analysis. There is limited integration of real-time communication tools such as live updates, chatbots, or alumni interaction. Existing architectures also suffer from a lack of scalability, as most are restricted to single institutions without multi-institution collaboration capabilities. Furthermore, there is an insufficient use of analytics dashboards to help students, recruiters, and placement officers track placement trends, alongside a weak emphasis on the privacy and security of company and student records. The proposed data-driven approach resolves these issues to enhance employability and ensure objective classification.

II LITERATURE SURVEY

Prof. Rupali Komatwar et al. [1] developed a placement support system utilizing the Apriori

algorithm. While this decision support system reduces paperwork, saves time, and allows for custom filtering, it is hindered by data redundancy and a communication gap between students, alumni, and training officers.

Naresh Patel K M et al. [2] proposed a web application for placement prediction using Random Forest Classifier and CatBoost algorithms. This approach achieves high prediction accuracy (up to 88%) by using historical data, but it struggles to adapt to frequent changes in company criteria and fails to provide detailed learning plans despite suggesting skills.

M Ilanchezhian and Ranjithkumar R [3] created a centralized web-based placement activity system capable of generating reports using filters. Though it organizes student data quickly, it requires significant manual work and is prone to delays in information.

Preksha Nigam et al. [4] introduced "Placement Hive," an AI-based portal built on a monolithic architecture using Django and PostgreSQL. It automates matching, screening, and job recommendations to save recruiter effort, but introduces privacy risks regarding sensitive applicant data and potential AI bias in candidate selection.

K Priyanga et al. [5] deployed a smart and automated college placement system on the cloud, featuring testing, validation, and real-time notifications. While fair and transparent, it currently lacks skill matching, resume analysis, and actual machine learning implementation.

Aakarsh M S et al. [6] designed a placement assistance system accessible via web and Android applications to provide direct access to information at any time. However, this system relies heavily on manual dependency, faces security concerns, and is strictly dependent on internet connectivity. Incorporating real-time job market and industry data will help align student recommendations directly

with current hiring trends. This system is heavily dependent on human assistance.

III PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. system overview

The proposed system is a smart platform designed to assist campus placements by leveraging student skills, career preferences, and academic performance. It applies K-Means clustering to logically group students based on their respective readiness levels. Personalized training recommendations are then generated for students according to their recognized readiness clusters and skill gaps. The platform facilitates data entry and progress updates through a student interface, while an admin dashboard empowers administrators to analyze clusters, monitor student performance, and plan activities effectively.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: Career valley system architecture

C. Modules

- User Interface Layer: Features a student portal that allows students to input details and view reports, alongside a recruiter dashboard that assists administrators in managing student data and monitoring overall progress.

- **Data Collection & Preprocessing:** Involves the continuous validation, normalization, and data entry processes to ensure consistency and accuracy. It successfully converts raw inputs into processed data that is ready for further analysis.
- **Data Storage:** Provides reliable access by maintaining a robust skills repository, recruiter data, and a student database.
- **Machine Learning Layer:** Utilizes the K-Means Clustering Algorithm to identify meaningful clusters that highlight individual weaknesses and strengths, effectively grouping students based on performance and skills.
- **Recommendation Engine:** Executes accurate role matching to align students with highly suitable career paths while suggesting personalized training programs to elevate their skills.
- **Reporting & Export Module:** Generates actionable insights for administrators and students through comprehensive analytics dashboards, training plans, and student reports.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

- Frontend and Backend Technologies based on the system implementations are:
- The frontend interface is developed using modern web technologies including React for building interactive user interfaces such as the Login and Register pages. It utilizes React Router for navigation and Axios to handle seamless HTTP requests to the server APIs.
- The backend operates on a Node.js environment using the Express.js framework. It relies on modules like cors for cross-origin resource sharing, dotenv for environment variable management, and implements structured routing for students, companies, jobs, and applications.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed system significantly simplifies and automates the campus placement process. By leveraging intelligent algorithms, it accurately matches students with suitable job opportunities while reducing manual workloads for placement officers and students. It improves precision in candidate shortlisting and ensures a transparent, data-driven recruitment pipeline. Ultimately, the system enhances communication between recruiters, students, and placement cells, helping institutions effectively analyse student performance and placement trends

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Future iterations aim to expand the system to support multiple institutions via scalable and centralized placement management. Incorporating real-time job market and industry data will help align student recommendations directly with current hiring trends. Furthermore, deeper readiness analysis will be achieved by integrating coding assessments, aptitude tests, and soft-skill evaluations. The platform's scope will also be broadened to support higher studies, certifications, and internship guidance, culminating in the development of a personalized, AI-based career guidance assistant.

REFERENCES

- [1] Prof. Rupali Komatwar, Swapnil Kamble, Mihir Khedekar, Kishor Walzade, "Placement support system", <https://ijarcce.com/wpcontent/uploads/2016/02/IJARCCCE-78>.
- [2] Naresh Patel K M, Goutham N M, Inzamam K A, Suraksha V Kandi, Vineet Sharan VR, "Placement prediction and analysis using machine learning", <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/11019060>.
- [3] M Ilanchezhian, Ranjithkumar R, "Placement activity system", <https://www.ijert.org/research/placement-activity-system-IJERTCONV4IS19030>.

[4] Preksha Nigam, Mohammad Ragib Ahmad, Dr. Ashok Kumar Yadav, "Placement hive – artificial intelligence Based placement portal", <https://ymerdigital.com/uploads/YMER220498>.

[5] K Priyanga, A Divakar, A S E Vyshnavee, S Ibrahim Basha, D Harsitha, "Smart and automated college placement system", <https://www.ijarsct.co.in/Paper23767>.

[6] Aakarsh M S, Anirudh R, Gagan K, Niranjana C A, Vanamala C K, "Placement assistance system", <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V3/i5/IRJET-V3I5160>.

AI POWERED HEATSTROKE PREDICTION SYSTEM

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Abstract- Heatstroke is a severe heat-related illness caused by prolonged exposure to high temperature, humidity, and physical exertion, posing significant health risks to vulnerable populations. Conventional heat alert systems rely mainly on environmental temperature thresholds and lack predictive capability and personalization. To address these limitations, this paper presents an AI-powered heatstroke prediction system that integrates real-time environmental and physiological data for early risk assessment. The system continuously monitors parameters such as ambient temperature, humidity, body temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation using interconnected sensing devices. By analyzing these parameters collectively, the system classifies heatstroke risk levels and generates timely alerts to support preventive intervention and emergency response. The proposed approach emphasizes proactive health monitoring and aims to enhance safety in extreme climatic conditions.

Keywords: Heatstroke prediction, Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, Health monitoring, Early warning system

I. INTRODUCTION

Heatstroke is a critical heat-related illness that occurs when the body's thermoregulation system fails due to prolonged exposure to high temperature, humidity, and physical exertion. The increasing frequency of extreme heat events caused by global climate change has significantly elevated the risk of heatstroke, particularly among outdoor workers, athletes, elderly individuals, and vulnerable populations. Without timely detection and intervention, heatstroke can lead to severe organ damage and life-threatening conditions.

Most existing heat alert and monitoring systems rely primarily on ambient temperature thresholds and provide generalized warnings. Such systems do not account for individual physiological responses, which play a crucial role in the onset of heatstroke. Additionally, conventional approaches often lack continuous monitoring, real-time analysis, and automated alert mechanisms, making them reactive rather than preventive in nature.

Recent advancements in Internet of Things (IoT) technology enable real-time collection of environmental physiological data through wearable and embedded sensors. When combined with Artificial Intelligence (AI), these systems can analyze multiple parameters simultaneously to assess heat stress more accurately. By integrating environmental conditions with physiological indicators, AI-based approaches support early risk assessment and timely alerts. This paper focuses on an AI-powered heatstroke prediction system designed to enhance preventive healthcare monitoring and improve safety under extreme climatic conditions.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Several research efforts have focused on the detection and prediction of heatstroke by analyzing physiological responses, environmental conditions, and wearable sensor data.

Fujiwara et al. [1] proposed a heat illness detection method based on heart rate variability analysis derived from ECG signals using a multivariate anomaly detection algorithm. The system demonstrated effectiveness in monitoring athletes and identifying early signs of heat illness. However, its sensitivity was limited, and performance variations were observed across different population groups, which affected overall reliability.

Momose et al. [2] developed a wearable heatstroke risk informing system that measured perspiration rate using a capacitive humidity sensor embedded in a ventilated capsule. The approach was non-invasive and suitable for continuous, real-time monitoring in environments such as schools and elderly care facilities. Despite these advantages, the system required additional real-world testing to improve detection accuracy and robustness.

Khan et al. [3] presented a wearable heatstroke detection and control system that integrated temperature sensors with a PID controller and a Peltier cooling module. The system not

only detected heat stress but also actively reduced body temperature, making it suitable for workers in hot environments. However, limited field testing and the bulky nature of the hardware design reduced its practicality for long-term wearable use.

Shafiq et al. [4] proposed an extreme heat prediction framework using deep learning and explainable artificial intelligence techniques based on historical meteorological data. The model effectively predicted extreme heat events and provided interpretability of results. Nevertheless, its applicability was geographically limited, and the approach required large datasets and significant computational resources.

Lim et al. [5] explored an Internet of Things-based heatstroke prediction approach integrated with machine learning techniques to enable real-time monitoring and early intervention. The system demonstrated potential in reducing heat-related hospital admissions through early warnings. However, the need for large training datasets and improvements in device comfort were identified as key challenges.

Silawarawet et al. [6] introduced a prototype heatstroke warning system for athletes using multiple environmental sensors integrated with a microcontroller and a web-based monitoring platform. The system supported outdoor sports monitoring and heat illness prevention. However, reliability issues with certain sensors and limited validation highlighted the need for further experimentation and refinement.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The proposed system is an AI-powered heatstroke prediction framework designed to continuously monitor environmental and physiological parameters in real time. The primary objective of the system is to assess heat stress risk and provide early warnings to prevent severe heat-related illnesses. By integrating multiple sensing devices with intelligent data analysis, the system enables timely identification of abnormal conditions that may lead to heatstroke.

The system monitors ambient temperature and humidity along with physiological indicators such as body temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation. These parameters provide a comprehensive understanding of both environmental exposure and individual physical response. The collected data is processed to classify heatstroke risk levels and trigger appropriate alerts.

B. System Architecture

The system architecture follows a layered design consisting of data acquisition, data processing, risk assessment, and alert generation units. Environmental and physiological sensors continuously collect real-time data, which is transmitted to a central processing unit for analysis. The processing unit prepares the data for intelligent evaluation to ensure accurate risk classification.

An AI-based analysis module evaluates the combined parameters to classify heatstroke risk into Low, Moderate, and High categories. Based on the identified risk level, the system activates appropriate alert mechanisms. The architecture supports real-time operation and reliable integration of sensing, analysis, and communication components.

Figure 1: AI Powered Heatstroke Prediction System Architecture

C. System Modules

The proposed system consists of the following modules:

- Sensing Module: Collects real-time environmental data such as temperature and humidity, along with physiological parameters including body temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation.
- Data Processing Module: Organizes and filters the collected sensor data to remove inconsistencies and ensure accuracy before analysis.
- Risk Assessment Module: Analyzes the processed data to evaluate heat stress severity and classify the risk level as Low, Moderate, or High.

- Alert and Notification Module: Generates warning alerts for moderate risk levels and emergency notifications for high-risk conditions to enable timely preventive action and medical assistance.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The design and implementation of the proposed heatstroke prediction system focus on reliable real-time monitoring, accurate risk assessment, and timely alert generation. A modular design approach is adopted to ensure seamless integration of sensing hardware, backend processing, and user interface components, while supporting scalability and ease of deployment.

The system implementation integrates embedded hardware with software-based processing platforms. Environmental and physiological sensors are interfaced with a microcontroller-based embedded platform that supports continuous data acquisition and transmission. The embedded layer is designed for low-power operation and real-time responsiveness, making it suitable for wearable and portable applications.

The backend of the system is implemented using Python and is responsible for data preprocessing, intelligent analysis, and heatstroke risk classification. The backend manages sensor data storage, processing, and decision-making logic, enabling continuous monitoring and real-time evaluation of heat stress conditions.

The frontend of the system is developed using web-based technologies, including HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, to provide a user-friendly interface for real-time data visualization and alert display. The frontend presents environmental readings, physiological parameters, and risk levels in an easily interpretable format. It communicates with the backend to retrieve processed results and display alert notifications to the user.

Embedded-side control and sensor interfacing are implemented using C/C++ to ensure efficient communication with hardware components and real-time performance. The interaction between the embedded platform, backend processing unit, and frontend interface ensures seamless data flow and timely alert generation.

The overall design and implementation support practical deployment in environments such as outdoor workplaces, sports activities, and elderly care monitoring.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an AI-powered heatstroke prediction system that integrates environmental and physiological monitoring for early detection of heat stress. By combining real-time sensor data with intelligent risk assessment, the system overcomes the limitations of conventional temperature-based alert methods.

The proposed design enables continuous monitoring and timely alert generation, supporting preventive action in high-risk conditions. The system is suitable for applications such as outdoor work, sports activities, and elderly care, contributing to improved safety under extreme heat exposure.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Future enhancements of the proposed heatstroke prediction system can include non-contact heatstroke detection using camera-based or thermal imaging techniques, enabling monitoring without the need for wearable sensors. Such approaches can improve user comfort and support large-scale surveillance in public spaces.

Prediction accuracy can be further improved by incorporating reinforcement learning techniques that allow the system to adapt automatically based on user data and environmental changes. Integration with hospital medical records can enable personalized heatstroke prediction by considering individual medical history and health profiles.

The system can also be extended to generate AI-based heatstroke risk maps for different geographical locations, supporting large-scale public health monitoring. Additionally, the incorporation of drone-based first aid delivery mechanisms can enhance emergency response, particularly in remote or hard-to-reach areas.

REFERENCES

- [1] Al-Bouwarthan M, Quinn MM, Kriebel D, Wegman DH. Risk of kidney injury among construction workers exposed to heat stress: a longitudinal study from Saudi Arabia. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(11):3775. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17113775> PMID: [32466510](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32466510/)
- [2] Matsueda M. Predictability of Euro-Russian blocking in summer of 2010. *Geophys Res Lett*. 2011;38(6):1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011GL046123>

[3] Abbas S, Waseem M, Yaseen M, Latif Y, Leta MK, Khan TH, et al. Spatial-temporal seasonal variability of extreme precipitation under warming climate in Pakistan. *Atmosphere*.2023;14(2):210.<https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos14020210>

[4] O'Brien-Delpesh C, Sinanan N, Martin H, Chadee A. Preserving fragile ecosystems from oil spills –an environmental sensitivity assessment of the east coast of Trinidad. *Ocean Coastal Manag.*2022 ;230 :106374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2022.106374>

[5] Somani R. Global warming in Pakistan and its impact on public health as viewed through a health equity lens. *Int J Soc Determinants Health Health Serv*2023;53(2):27551938231147. <https://doi.org/10.1177/27551938231154467>PMID: [36734041](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36734041/)

[6] Nguyen D, Ashraf S, Le M, Ali M. Projection of climate variables by general circulation and deep learning model for Lahore, Pakistan. *EcolInf.*2023;75:102077.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2023.102077>

[7] Zahid M, Rasul G. Changing trends of thermal extremes in Pakistan. *ClimaticChange.*2012;113(3–4):883–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0390-4>

Chatbot Supporting Mental Health

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Abstract-- Solitude is a mental health support chatbot developed with strong emphasis on a custom-built conversational AI model designed exclusively for mental health assistance. The system concentrates on domain-specific model design and behavioural optimization to ensure emotionally intelligent interactions. The customized chatbot model is engineered to prioritize emotional sensitivity, contextual relevance, and conversational continuity, enabling it to understand user intent, emotional tone, and mental state more accurately than generic chatbot systems. The model incorporates structured dialogue flows, sentiment-aware response generation, and controlled conversational behaviour to ensure supportive, non-judgmental, and ethically guided interactions. It adapts responses dynamically based on user mood patterns, prior interactions, and conversational context, promoting a sense of personalized and consistent support. Solitude operates in real time, providing confidential assistance for concerns such as stress, anxiety, and emotional distress, while embedding safety mechanisms including disclaimers, escalation guidance, and encouragement toward professional help when required. The frontend, developed using modern web technologies such as Next.js, HTML, and CSS, delivers a responsive, calming, and user-friendly interface, while integrated voice support enables speech-based interaction for improved accessibility and engagement. The backend, implemented using Python and JavaScript with Supabase as the database solution, supports secure data storage, scalable architecture, and efficient processing for continuous interactions. Additional features such as mood tracking, activity logging, and progress monitoring reinforce reflective self-awareness and long-term engagement. Overall, Solitude demonstrates how a purpose-built mental health chatbot model, combined with robust web technologies, can function as a reliable, scalable, and low-cost digital mental health companion that complements traditional care and extends psychological support to underserved populations

Keywords— Conversational Artificial Intelligence, NLP, Sentiment Analysis, Real-Time Interaction Systems, Supabase, Emotional Intelligence in AI, Digital Mental Health Support

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health disorders such as stress, anxiety, and depression have become increasingly prevalent in today's fast-paced and digitally connected world. Despite growing awareness, access to timely and affordable mental health care remains a significant challenge due to social stigma, limited availability of professionals, high consultation costs, and geographical constraints. As a result, many individuals hesitate to seek help or are unable to receive consistent psychological support. Recent advancements in AI and Natural Language Processing have enabled the development of intelligent conversational agents capable of offering preliminary emotional assistance. Solitude is designed to leverage these technologies to create a safe, accessible, and supportive digital environment for individuals experiencing emotional distress.

The chatbot is built using a customized conversational AI model specifically tailored for mental health interactions. Unlike generic chatbots that provide broad and often impersonal responses, this system emphasizes emotional sensitivity, contextual relevance, and conversational continuity. It integrates structured dialogue flows and sentiment-aware response generation to better interpret user intent, emotional tone, and psychological state. By analyzing conversation history and mood patterns, the chatbot adapts its responses dynamically to ensure personalized and empathetic communication. Ethical safeguards are embedded within the system, including non-judgmental response strategies, clear disclaimers, and escalation guidance that encourages users to seek professional assistance when critical situations are identified.

From a system architecture perspective, the chatbot employs a hybrid AI approach that combines transformer-based language understanding with intent classification and emotion detection mechanisms. The frontend is developed using modern web technologies to provide a responsive, calming, and user-friendly interface that promotes comfort and ease of interaction. Voice-based input and output capabilities are incorporated to enhance accessibility, especially for users who may prefer speech communication over text. The backend infrastructure supports real-time processing, secure session management, and encrypted data storage to maintain confidentiality and user trust.

In addition to conversational support, the platform includes features such as mood tracking, activity logging, and progress monitoring to encourage reflective self-awareness and long-term engagement. These features enable users to observe emotional trends over time and adopt healthier coping strategies. By integrating technological innovation with ethical responsibility and user centered design, the proposed chatbot demonstrates the potential of AI driven systems to complement traditional therapy. It serves as a scalable and cost-effective digital companion that can extend mental health support to underserved and remote populations while maintaining privacy, reliability, and compassionate interaction.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Jayabhaduri R et al. [1], developed an AI-powered mental health chatbot using a Keras sequential deep learning model with TensorFlow's Sequential API and text preprocessing techniques. The system improves accessibility and user engagement. However, it faces accuracy limitations, real-time response challenges, and significant privacy risks in handling sensitive mental health data.

Ishita Agarwal et al. [2], proposed an LLM-based multimodal chatbot using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture for preliminary diagnosis. The system supports underserved communities and scalable datasets. However, it remains limited to initial diagnostic guidance, requires medical validation, and raises security concerns when deployed in real-world healthcare environments.

Mohammad Amin Kuhail et al. [3], studied chatbot-human personality congruence using the Big-Five Inventory framework in an advising system. The approach enhances evidence-based personality design and user engagement. However, the research is limited to selected traits, involves a small sample size, and lacks long-term validation of behavioral outcomes.

Jenisha Samlin G et al. [4], introduced Strezzy, a deep learning chatbot using NLTK, SpaCy, BERT, and BiLSTM for depression detection and support. It enables early identification and lightweight deployment. However, it lacks human-like understanding, presents ethical and privacy concerns, and provides limited multimodal and speech input support.

R. Shanmukha Priya et al. [5], developed a mental health chatbot integrating sequential algorithms with SAT and CBT therapeutic techniques. The system offers evidence-based relaxation and motivational interventions. However, it requires improved accuracy, broader clinical validation, better emergency handling, and significant computational resources for efficient operation.

Christopher Obinna Okoro et al. [6], proposed an AI-based chatbot for student mental health using datasets from Kaggle and GitHub with PHQ-9 and GAD-7 scales. It ensures 24/7 accessibility and real-world therapy data integration. However, privacy risks, limited therapeutic

depth, and potential technical failures remain key limitations.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The system adopts a hybrid architecture that integrates deterministic logic with a locally hosted LLaMA 3 (8B) model deployed via Ollama to enable controlled, context-aware response generation for mental health support. Deterministic components enforce safety rules, domain restrictions, and structured workflows, while the language model delivers empathetic, natural, and context-sensitive interactions. The frontend, developed using Next.js and Tailwind CSS, provides a responsive and calming chat interface with optional voice input to enhance accessibility and user engagement. On the backend, dedicated modules handle intent detection, crisis severity monitoring, crisis detection, conversation state management, structured prompt construction, and output validation to ensure reliable and ethically guided responses. Supabase is integrated for secure authentication, encrypted data storage, and optional session history management, supporting privacy, scalability, and future extensibility. Together, these components create a robust, secure, and user-centered conversational system capable of delivering real-time, confidential, and responsible mental health assistance.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1: Solitude chatbot system architecture

Figure 1 illustrates the Solitude system architecture comprising four interconnected layers: Frontend, Backend, Data Layer, and LLM Layer. The user interacts with a responsive Next.js-based chat interface styled using Tailwind CSS, with optional voice input enabled through the Web Speech API. User inputs are transmitted securely to the backend conversation pipeline. The backend orchestrates multiple safety and intelligence modules, including intent classification, crisis detection, conversation memory management, domain guarding, and structured prompt construction. A locally hosted LLaMA 3 (8B) model deployed via Ollama performs controlled response generation. Supabase provides secure authentication, encrypted storage, and session logging. An output validation layer ensures responses comply with safety and domain policies before being delivered to the user.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

C. Modules

- Chat Interface and Voice Interaction Module

Implements a responsive chat UI using Next.js and Tailwind CSS, supporting both text and optional voice input through the Web Speech API. It manages user interaction flow, message rendering, and secure communication with the backend.

- Intent Classification Module

Analyzes incoming user messages to determine conversational intent, emotional tone, and contextual relevance. This module ensures appropriate routing within the conversation pipeline and activates safety mechanisms when necessary.

- Crisis Detection and Bypass Module

Continuously monitors user input for high-severity mental health indicators. In critical situations, the system triggers emergency response guidance and helpline routing, temporarily bypassing standard generation to prioritize user safety.

- Domain Guard and Conversation Memory Module

Restricts responses strictly to mental health support domains and prevents unsafe or irrelevant outputs. The conversation memory manager maintains contextual continuity across sessions, enabling coherent and personalized interactions.

- Prompt Construction and Controlled Generation Module

Builds structured prompts by combining user input, conversation history, and safety constraints before sending them to the locally hosted LLaMA 3 (8B) model via Ollama. Controlled generation ensures empathetic yet policy-compliant responses.

- Output Validation Layer

Performs final verification of generated responses to ensure compliance with safety, ethical, and domain-specific guidelines before delivering them to the user interface.

- Authentication and Secure Storage Module (Supabase)

Handles user authentication, encrypted data storage, and optional session history logging. This module ensures privacy, scalability, and secure management of sensitive mental health conversations.

Together, these modules create a secure, scalable, and ethically governed conversational AI system capable of delivering real-time, context-aware, and safety-focused mental health support.

A. System Design

□ Use Case Diagram

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

Figure II illustrates the Solitude use case diagram with two actors: User and Admin. Users register, log in, engage in chat (text/voice), track mood, and receive personalized support. The system performs intent classification and crisis detection. Admins manage users, review flagged cases, and monitor analytics securely.

B. Implementation Details

- Frontend Technologies

The Solitude frontend is developed using Next.js with Tailwind CSS to deliver a fast, responsive, and accessible user interface. The application is structured into modular pages such as Chat, Dashboard, Mood Tracker, Login, and Settings, supported by reusable UI components for messages, alerts, and analytics widgets. The interface follows a calming design approach with soft color palettes, minimal layouts, and smooth micro-interactions to enhance user comfort during sensitive conversations. Voice interaction is enabled through the Web Speech API, allowing optional speech-to-text input. API communication is managed through a centralized service layer that securely attaches authentication tokens to each request. The frontend is optimized for cross-device compatibility, ensuring seamless performance across desktop and mobile browsers.

- Backend Technologies

The backend is implemented using Python and Node.js components to manage AI orchestration and real-time communication. The core conversation pipeline includes modules for intent classification, crisis detection, conversation state management, domain restriction, prompt construction, and output validation. A locally hosted LLaMA 3 (8B) model is deployed via Ollama to enable controlled and context-aware response generation. The backend enforces deterministic safety rules before and after model inference to ensure ethical responses. Asynchronous processing is used to

maintain low-latency interactions. The system is structured modularly to allow future expansion, including additional AI models or monitoring services.

- Security Mechanisms

Solitude incorporates a multi-layered security framework to protect sensitive mental health data. Authentication is managed using Supabase with secure session handling and encrypted credential storage. All communication between frontend and backend is protected using HTTPS protocols. Role-based access control ensures restricted administrative access where required. Conversation data is encrypted at rest, and optional session logging can be enabled for users who choose to retain chat history. Crisis-related interactions are handled with strict validation layers to prevent unsafe outputs. Token-based authentication is enforced for protected endpoints, ensuring only authorized users can access personalized services.

- Database Management

Supabase serves as the primary database solution, providing scalable and secure cloud-based storage. The system stores user credentials, encrypted conversation logs, mood tracking records, and activity history in structured relational tables. A session-based management pattern ensures efficient connection handling and prevents resource leaks. The database architecture is designed for scalability, allowing future integration with analytics dashboards and extended mental health monitoring features while maintaining strict privacy and compliance standards.

V. RESULTS

The Solitude mental health support system was successfully developed and deployed using a hybrid architecture integrating deterministic safety logic with a locally hosted LLaMA 3 (8B) model. Real-time conversations were processed with low-latency responses, maintaining smooth interaction across text and voice inputs. The intent classification and crisis detection modules accurately identified high-risk emotional cues, triggering emergency guidance and helpline recommendations when required. Controlled prompt construction and output validation mechanisms ensured responses remained context-aware, empathetic, and domain-restricted. Personalized support improved over time through conversation memory and mood tracking features, enabling adaptive and consistent interactions. Secure authentication and encrypted session storage protected sensitive user data, while optional history logging enhanced continuity. Overall, Solitude demonstrated reliable performance, strong safety compliance, and scalable deployment capability, confirming its effectiveness as a secure and responsive AI-driven mental health support platform.

VI. CONCLUSION

Solitude successfully demonstrates how AI and NLP can be integrated into a secure, empathetic, and accessible

mental health support platform. By combining real-time conversational processing, crisis detection, personalized response generation, and strict privacy safeguards, the system delivers meaningful emotional assistance to users facing stress, anxiety, and depression. Its hybrid architecture ensures safe, context-aware interactions while maintaining confidentiality. Solitude provides a scalable, cost-effective digital companion that complements traditional therapy and expands mental health accessibility, especially for underserved communities.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

In the future, Solitude can be enhanced with advanced voice, facial expression, and sentiment analysis for more human-like conversations. Long-term user profiling and memory integration can improve personalization. Collaboration with mental health professionals will strengthen clinical validation. Integration with wearable devices and predictive AI models can enable proactive monitoring, early risk detection, and timely intervention support.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Jayabhaduri, A. Vijayaraghavan, R. Ajay Karthik, G. Ceralaathan and S. Sai Sailesh, "AI Powered Chatbot for Mental Health Treatment," in *Proc. 2024 1st Int. Conf. on Technological Innovations and Advance Computing (TIACOMP)*, Bali, Indonesia, 2024, pp. 168–172.
- [2] I. Agarwal, V. Sakthivel and P. Prakash, "Toward Inclusive Healthcare: An LLM-Based Multimodal Chatbot for Preliminary Diagnosis," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 136420–136432, 2025.
- [3] M. A. Kuhail, et al., "Assessing the Impact of Chatbot-Human Personality Congruence on User Behaviour: A Chatbot-Based Advising System Case," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. on Advanced Learning Technologies*, 2025.
- [4] J. Samlin G., et al., "Strezzy: A Deep Learning Based Conversational Chatbot for Depression Detection and Support," *Int. J. Sci. Res. Eng. Dev. (IJSRED)*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2025.
- [5] R. Shanmukha Priya, et al., "Chatbot for Mental Health Care," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Computing and Communication Systems*, 2025.
- [6] C. O. Okoro, et al., "Artificial Intelligence-Based Chatbot for Student Mental Health Support," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Artificial Intelligence and Applications*, 2025.
- [7] W. Pichowicz, M. Kotas and P. Piotrowski, "Performance of Mental Health Chatbot Agents in Detecting and Managing Suicidal Ideation," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, Art. no. 31652, pp. 1–14, Aug. 2025.
- [8] P. Rathnayaka, N. Mills, D. Burnett, D. De Silva, D. Alahakoon and R. Gray, "A Mental Health Chatbot with Cognitive Skills for Personalised Behavioural Activation

and Remote Health Monitoring,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 10, Art. no. 3653, 2022,

[9] E. Itelman, G. Golovchiner, A. Barsheshet, R. Kornowski, and A. Erez, “Balancing innovation and professionalism: The emerging role of AI-powered chatbots in medical consultation,” *Heart Rhythm*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 2037–2039, Oct. 2024.

[10] 6] S. H. Alqaidi, S. M. Albugami, W. S. Alzahrani, S. Badri, and A. Wali, “Network-integrated medical chatbot for enhanced healthcare services,” *Telematics Informat. Rep.*, vol. 15, Sep. 2024, Art. no. 100153.

[11] S. D. Bhavani Peri, S. Santhanalakshmi, and R. Radha, “Chatbot to chat with medical books using retrieval-augmented generation model,” in *Proc. IEEE North Karnataka Subsection Flagship Int. Conf. (NKCon)*, Bagalkote, India, Sep. 2024,

[12] A. R. George, J. E. Saji, J. Francis, L. Shibu, and H. Haritha, “Multiple disease prediction using machine learning with chatbot and doctor-patient appointment system,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Smart Power Control Renew. Energy (ICSPCRE)*, Rourkela, India, Jul. 2024

Indoor Mapping and Navigation System Using QR Codes for College Campus

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Abstract—Indoor navigation within large institutional campuses is a complex challenge due to multi-building layouts and lack of GPS availability indoors. This paper presents a QR code-based indoor navigation system integrated with web technology. The system includes surveying, AutoCAD drafting, digital mapping using Mappedin, website development, and QR code deployment. The solution improves navigation efficiency, reduces confusion, and enhances accessibility for users.

Keywords—Indoor navigation, QR codes, AutoCAD, Mappedin, campus mapping

I. INTRODUCTION

Indoor navigation is increasingly important in large institutions where multiple buildings and floors exist. Navigating such environments manually is inefficient. GPS-based systems fail indoors, necessitating alternative solutions such as QR codes. This project implements a QR-based navigation system that integrates surveying, mapping, and web technologies. The system ensures accurate indoor positioning and ease of access through smartphones without requiring additional applications. The proposed solution aims to improve user experience and support smart campus initiatives.

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technologies. The system ensures accurate indoor positioning and ease of access through smartphones without requiring additional applications. The proposed solution aims to improve user experience and support smart campus initiatives.

II. NEED FOR INDOOR NAVIGATION SYSTEM

Indoor navigation systems help users locate facilities easily within complex structures. They reduce time spent searching for rooms and improve accessibility for differently-abled individuals. These systems also assist during emergencies by guiding users to exits. In educational institutions, they enhance the experience of new students and visitors. The system reduces dependency on staff and promotes efficient movement across campus.

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III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Christian Perey and Tomoaki Miyashita (2011) introduced indoor navigation combined with augmented reality. Adam Satan (2018) developed a QR-based navigation system using smartphones. Kunhoth Jithin (2019) compared indoor navigation technologies. Kajal Kumbhar (2019) proposed a QR-based system for indoor use. János Erdélyi (2020) demonstrated QR-based positioning. Jianhua Liu and team (2020) introduced BIM-based indoor mapping. Mazhar F. Khan (2022) emphasized QR-based positioning accuracy. These studies highlight the importance of cost-effective and accurate indoor navigation solutions.

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IV. METHODOLOGY

The project methodology consists of surveying, drafting, mapping, and implementation. Physical surveys were conducted using measuring tools and Total Station. Rough sketches were prepared. AutoCAD was used to create floor plans. Mappedin was used to create interactive maps. A website was developed using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. QR codes were generated and deployed at strategic locations. Each stage was carefully executed to ensure accuracy and functionality.

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V. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation involved surveying multiple buildings including Polytechnic Block, Main Block, Block A, Block B, and Mechanical Workshop. Floor plans were drafted using AutoCAD. Digital maps were created using Mappedin. The website provided a user interface for navigation. QR codes

were placed at entrances and corridors. The system was tested for accuracy and usability.

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VI. RESULTS

The system successfully provides indoor navigation. Users can locate rooms easily. The system reduces confusion and saves time. QR codes enable accurate positioning. The website ensures easy access without additional apps. The solution is reliable and user-friendly.

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VII. DISCUSSION

The system demonstrates that QR-based navigation is effective and economical. Compared to Wi-Fi and Bluetooth systems, QR codes require minimal infrastructure. However, user interaction is required for scanning codes. Future improvements may include automation and AR integration. The system is scalable and can be applied to other environments.

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VIII. CONCLUSION

The indoor navigation system developed provides an efficient solution for navigating complex buildings. It integrates surveying, mapping, and web technologies. The system is cost-effective and easy to implement. It enhances user experience and supports smart campus initiatives. Future enhancements can further improve functionality.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Christian Perey and Tomoaki Miyashita, Indoor Positioning and Navigation for Mobile AR, 2011.
- [2] Adam Satan, QR Code-Based Indoor Navigation Mobile System, 2018.
- [3] Kunhoth Jithin, Comparative Analysis of Indoor Navigation Systems, 2019.
- [4] Kajal Kumbhar, Indoor Navigation Using QR Codes, 2019.
- [5] János Erdélyi, Positioning in Indoor Environment Using QR Codes, 2020.
- [6] Jianhua Liu et al., BIM-Based Indoor Map Model, 2020.
- [7] Mazhar F. Khan, Precise Indoor Positioning Using QR Codes, 2022.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON PALF CONCRETE WITH PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF COARSE AGGREGATE BY MARBLE CHIPS

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ABSTRACT

Concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials due to its high compressive strength and durability. However, it suffers from low tensile strength, poor ductility, and susceptibility to cracking. This study investigates the use of Pineapple Leaf Fibre (PALF) as a natural reinforcing material and marble chips as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates to improve the performance and sustainability of concrete. PALF was added in proportions of 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% by weight of cement, while marble chips replaced coarse aggregates at levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%. M25 grade concrete specimens were prepared and tested for compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength after 28 days of curing. The results indicate that PALF improves tensile and flexural strength by enhancing crack resistance, while marble chips contribute to maintaining or improving compressive strength. The optimum mix was found to be 1.5% PALF with 30% marble chip replacement. The study demonstrates that the combined use of agricultural and industrial waste materials can produce sustainable and high-performance concrete.

KEYWORDS

PALF, Marble Chips, Fibre Reinforce Concrete, Sustainable Concrete, Mechanical Properties

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a versatile and widely used material in the construction industry. Concrete is a versatile and widely used material in the construction industry due to its strength, durability, and cost-effectiveness. Despite its advantages, conventional concrete has inherent limitations such as low tensile strength, brittleness, and cracking under tensile stresses. To overcome these drawbacks, fibre reinforced concrete (FRC) has been developed by incorporating fibres into the concrete matrix. Natural fibres such as Pineapple Leaf Fibre (PALF) have gained attention due to their eco-friendly nature, high tensile strength, and availability as agricultural waste.

At the same time, the disposal of marble waste from industries poses environmental challenges. Using marble chips as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates helps reduce environmental impact and conserves natural resources.

This study focuses on combining PALF and marble chips to develop a sustainable concrete with improved mechanical properties.

II. NEED FOR THE STUDY

The rapid growth of the construction industry has led to excessive consumption of natural resources and increased environmental pollution. The need for this study arises from:

- Utilization of agricultural waste (PALF)
- Recycling industrial waste (marble chips)

- Reduction in environmental pollution
- Improvement in mechanical properties of concrete
- Development of sustainable construction materials

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Conventional concrete exhibits high compressive strength but poor tensile and flexural strength, leading to cracking and durability issues. Additionally, improper disposal of pineapple leaves and marble waste contributes to environmental degradation.

Hence, there is a need to develop an eco-friendly concrete mix that enhances strength while utilizing waste materials.

IV. OBJECTIVES

- To study the effect of PALF on concrete properties
- To investigate partial replacement of coarse aggregates with marble chips
- To compare results with conventional M25 concrete
- To determine the optimum mix proportion

V. MATERIALS USED

The materials used in this experimental study include cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, marble chips, Pineapple Leaf Fibre (PALF), and water. Cement is used as the primary binding material in concrete, providing strength through hydration. Fine aggregate is used to fill the voids between coarse aggregates and improve the workability of the mix. Coarse aggregate contributes to the bulk and load-bearing capacity of concrete. Marble chips, obtained as an industrial waste product, are used as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates to promote sustainability and reduce environmental impact. Pineapple Leaf Fibre (PALF), a natural fibre extracted from pineapple leaves, is incorporated into the concrete to enhance its tensile and flexural strength. Water is used for mixing and curing, ensuring proper hydration and strength development of the concrete.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The experimental methodology begins with the collection of all required raw materials, including cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, marble chips, and PALF. The Pineapple Leaf Fibre is prepared by extracting it from pineapple leaves, followed by cleaning, drying, and cutting it into suitable lengths for use in the concrete mix.

The concrete is prepared by initially mixing cement, fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate in dry condition until a uniform mixture is obtained. The PALF is then added gradually to the dry mix to ensure uniform distribution and to avoid fibre clustering. Water is added slowly to the mixture while continuous mixing is carried out to achieve a homogeneous and workable concrete mix.

The workability of the freshly prepared concrete is determined using the slump test. After assessing workability, the concrete is poured into moulds for casting specimens. Proper compaction is carried out during casting to eliminate air voids and ensure uniform density. The specimens are then left undisturbed for 24 hours before being demoulded.

After demoulding, the specimens are subjected to curing in water for a period of 28 days to achieve the required strength. Upon completion of curing, the hardened concrete specimens are tested for mechanical properties such as compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength. The results obtained from these tests are analyzed to evaluate the performance of the concrete and to determine the optimum mix proportion.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

A. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST

The compressive strength of concrete cubes was determined using a compression testing machine.

$$f_c = \frac{P}{A}$$

Where:

P = Load at failure

A = Cross sectional area

B. SPLIT TENSILE STRENGTH TEST

The tensile strength was determined using cylindrical specimens:

$$f_t = \frac{2P}{\pi LD}$$

C. FLEXURAL STRENGTH TEST

Flexural strength was calculated using beam specimens:

$$\sigma = \frac{PL}{bd^2}$$

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Compressive strength increased with marble chip replacement up to 30%
- PALF significantly improved tensile and flexural strength
- Workability slightly decreased with fibre addition
- Best performance observed at:
 - **1.5% PALF**
 - **30% marble chip replacement**

This combination provided improved crack resistance and overall strength.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The experimental study shows that:

- PALF enhances tensile and flexural strength
- Marble chips effectively replace natural aggregates
- Sustainable materials improve performance and reduce environmental impact
- The optimum mix is **1.5% PALF + 30% marble chips**

Thus, PALF and marble chips can be successfully used to produce eco-friendly and durable concrete.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Bharathi and A. Murugan, "Performance evaluation of pineapple leaf fibre reinforced concrete," *IJERT*, 2020.
- [2] R. Chaudhary and N. Patel, "Strength characteristics of fibre reinforced concrete using marblwaste," 2022.
- [3] K. Chotaliya et al., "Use of waste marble chips in concrete," 2016.
- [4] M. Kumar and V. Rao, "Partial replacement of coarse aggregates with marble chips," 2019.
- [5] S. Osmi et al., "Mechanical properties of PALF reinforced concrete," 2022

OBJECT DETECTION DRONE USING YOLOv10

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and implementation of an object detection drone using YOLOv10 for real time aerial surveillance and monitoring applications. The proposed system integrates a quadcopter platform with an onboard camera and embedded processing unit to detect and classify objects accurately. YOLOv10 provides high speed and improved detection performance compared to previous versions. The system is capable of detecting humans, vehicles, and other target objects in real time. The proposed model is suitable for surveillance, disaster management, agriculture monitoring, and security applications.

KEYWORDS

Drone; Object Detection; YOLOv10; Computer Vision; Surveillance; Deep Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), commonly known as drones, are widely used in surveillance, agriculture, disaster management, and defense applications. Integrating artificial intelligence with drones enhances their capability by enabling automatic object detection and tracking.

YOLOv10 (You Only Look Once version 10) is a real time object detection algorithm that improves detection accuracy and reduces computational complexity. This paper proposes a smart drone system integrated with YOLOv10 to perform efficient aerial object detection.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system architecture consists of multiple integrated hardware and software components working collaboratively to achieve real-time object detection. The drone frame supports brushless DC motors controlled by electronic speed controllers, which provide stable and efficient flight dynamics. A lithium polymer battery supplies high energy density power for extended flight duration. The onboard processor, such as NVIDIA Jetson Nano or Raspberry Pi 4, performs image preprocessing and executes the YOLOv10 neural network model. The high-resolution camera continuously captures video frames, which are converted into tensor format and fed into the detection model. The flight controller manages stabilization and navigation using GPS data, accelerometer, and gyroscope inputs. Processed detection outputs, including bounding boxes and class probabilities, are transmitted wirelessly to the ground control station for monitoring and further analysis. This modular architecture ensures scalability and adaptability for future AI enhancements

A. Hardware Components

The main hardware components include:

1. Quadcopter frame

2. Brushless DC motors with propellers
3. Electronic Speed Controllers (ESC)
4. Flight controller
5. Camera module
6. Li-Po battery

The drone captures aerial images using the onboard camera and processes them through the embedded processor.

B. Software Components

1. Python programming language
2. YOLOv10 deep learning model
3. OpenCV for image processing
4. PyTorch framework
5. Drone control software

The captured image frames are processed using YOLOv10 to detect objects with bounding boxes and confidence scores.

III. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The working of the proposed system is explained as follows:

1. The drone captures live video using the onboard camera.
2. The video frames are transmitted to the embedded processor.

3. YOLOv10 processes each frame in real time.
4. The model detects objects and classifies them.
5. Bounding boxes are drawn around detected objects.
6. The processed video is displayed or transmitted to a ground station.

YOLOv10 follows a single stage detection approach, where object localization and classification are performed simultaneously, improving speed and efficiency.

Fig 1: Flow Chart

IV. DESIGN

An Object Detection Drone using YOLOv10 is an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) integrated with a real-time object detection algorithm called YOLOv10 (You Only Look Once version 10).

This system captures aerial images or videos using an onboard camera and processes them through YOLOv10 to identify and classify objects such as vehicles, humans, animals, buildings, or obstacles in real time.

Fig 2: Design

V. ADVANTAGES

- * High detection speed
- * Improved accuracy compared to earlier YOLO versions
- * Real time monitoring capability
- * Reduced human intervention
- * Suitable for multiple applications

VI. APPLICATIONS

1. Border Surveillance

In border surveillance, the object detection drone using YOLOv10 plays a critical role in enhancing national security and monitoring sensitive regions. The drone can patrol large and remote border areas where continuous human surveillance is difficult and resource-intensive. By capturing real-time aerial footage, the system can automatically detect unauthorized human movement, suspicious vehicles, or illegal crossings. YOLOv10 enables accurate classification and localization of detected objects, allowing authorities to receive instant alerts with precise coordinates. This reduces response time and minimizes security risks. Additionally, the drone can operate during day and night conditions (with suitable cameras), making it a reliable solution for continuous border monitoring.

2. Traffic Monitoring

For traffic monitoring applications, the drone provides a dynamic and wide-area view of road networks compared to traditional fixed CCTV cameras. It can detect and classify vehicles such as cars, buses, trucks, and motorcycles while analyzing traffic density in real time. The YOLOv10 model helps in identifying congestion patterns, accidents, road blockages, and traffic rule violations. The

collected data can be transmitted to traffic management centers for effective planning and control. This improves road safety, reduces congestion, and supports the development of smart city infrastructure by enabling intelligent transportation systems.

3. Disaster Management

During disaster situations such as floods, earthquakes, landslides, or fires, the object detection drone becomes a valuable tool for emergency response and rescue operations. It can access dangerous or inaccessible areas without risking human lives. The system detects stranded individuals, damaged buildings, vehicles, and other critical objects in real time. YOLOv10 ensures fast and accurate detection even in complex environments. The drone provides live video and location data to rescue teams, helping them prioritize affected areas and allocate resources efficiently. This enhances situational awareness and significantly improves disaster response effectiveness.

4. Crowd Monitoring

Crowd monitoring is another important application of the object detection drone using YOLOv10. During public gatherings, festivals, rallies, or large events, managing

crowd safety becomes essential. The drone can estimate crowd density, track movement patterns, and detect abnormal activities in real time. YOLOv10 enables the detection of multiple individuals simultaneously, even in dense environments. Authorities can use this information to prevent overcrowding, manage emergency situations, and ensure public safety. The aerial view provided by the drone offers a broader perspective, making it more effective than ground-based monitoring systems.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

- * Integration with thermal cameras
- * Implementation of object tracking
- * Edge AI optimization for lower power consumption
- * Integration with 5G communication
- * Autonomous navigation with obstacle avoidance

VIII. CONCLUSION

The object detection drone using YOLOv10 provides an efficient real time aerial monitoring solution. The integration of deep learning with UAV technology

enhances automation and reduces manual monitoring effort. The proposed system demonstrates high speed detection with improved accuracy, making it suitable for surveillance and smart monitoring applications. Future improvements can further enhance its performance and reliability.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Redmon et al., “You Only Look Once Unified Real Time Object Detection,” IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2016.
- [2] A. Bochkovskiy et al., “YOLOv4 Optimal Speed and Accuracy of Object Detection,” 2020.
- [3] Michael Gonzales, et-al., Object Detection for Drones: Models and Applications: Explores real-world drone use cases for object detection with popular AI models. Source: Robotics Tomorrow, vol.8, no.10, 2018.
- [4] Vaibhav Patel, et-al., YOLOv5 for Drone Detection: Implements YOLOv5 for drone-based object detection tasks. Source: GitHub, vol.12, 2023.
- [5] Wang, A., Liu, H., Zhang, L., et al., YOLOv10: Real-Time End-to-End Object Detection. arXiv preprint arXiv: 2405.14458, 2024.

SMART LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract— *The Smart Library Management System is an integrated and automated solution designed to simplify book issuing and returning processes in a library environment. The system uses RFID technology for student identification to accurately track which student borrows each book, improving security and accountability, while QR code scanning is used for fast and reliable book identification instead of RFID tags on books. A fingerprint sensor authenticates the librarian to ensure secure approval and recording of transactions, and an ESP32-CAM module captures images of issued books. The entire system is controlled by an ESP-32 module that manages all hardware components, including buzzers and LEDs for instant operational feedback. Student records, book details, and transaction history are securely stored in Google Sheets for future reference and analysis. The system also sends automatic Telegram alerts to students about due dates and overdue books, eliminating the need for GSM modules and reducing cost by using ESP-32 internet connectivity. Overall, the project modernizes library management by integrating advanced hardware and software technologies to improve efficiency, security, and user convenience.*

Keywords- *ESP-32Module, RFID Reader, QR code, R307 Fingerprint module, ESP-32 CAM, 16X2 I2C LCD Display, Push Button*

I. INTRODUCTION

Libraries play an important role in storing, organizing, and managing knowledge for students and users. However, traditional library systems rely on manual record-keeping, which is time-consuming and prone to human errors. Managing book issuing, returning, and tracking manually often causes delays and reduces efficiency. With the advancement of modern technology, libraries can be automated to improve accuracy, security, and user convenience. This project introduces a Smart Library Management System that integrates RFID technology for student identification, QR code scanning for book tracking, fingerprint authentication for secure librarian access, and IoT using ESP32-CAM and ESP-32 modules. The system helps automate library operations, maintain digital records, and provide a faster, more reliable, and user-friendly library management solution.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing traditional library system mainly uses manual or non-digital methods to manage books and records. Books are arranged using card catalogs where details are written on index cards. Librarians manually handle book issuing and returning, which takes more time and effort. Although the system is simple and low cost, it is prone to human errors, causes delays in searching and updating records, and provides limited accessibility compared to automated systems.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Smart Library Management System automates library operations using modern technologies to improve efficiency and accuracy. RFID tags are used for student identification, allowing quick and contactless access during book issuing and returning. QR codes are used to track books easily and reduce manual searching. A fingerprint sensor provides secure authentication for the librarian, ensuring that only authorized persons can approve transactions. The ESP-32 module acts as the main controller, coordinating all hardware components and managing system operations. The ESP32-CAM module enables monitoring and QR code scanning, enhancing security and automation. All transaction data and records are stored in Google Sheets, allowing easy access, real-time updates, and proper record management. This system reduces manual work, minimizes errors, and provides a faster, secure, and user-friendly library management solution.

IV. HARDWARE

ESP-32, R307 Fingerprint module, ESP-32 CAM , RFID Reader, 16x2 I2C LCD Display, Push button

A. ESP-32 MODULE

The ESP-32 module acts as the central processing unit of the Smart Library Management System. It controls components such as the RFID reader, fingerprint sensor, camera, push buttons, LEDs, and buzzer. The module processes data and manages book issue and return operations. With built-in Wi-Fi, it stores data online in Google Sheets and sends notifications through the internet. Using GPIO pins, it connects and communicates with all hardware devices, enabling smooth and efficient system operation.

B. RFID READER

The RC522 RFID reader is used for student identification in the Smart Library Management System. It works based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology, which allows contactless communication between the reader and RFID cards or tags. When a student places the RFID card near the reader, it reads the unique identification number stored inside the card and sends the data to the ESP-32 controller for verification. This process is fast, accurate, and reduces manual entry errors. The RFID system improves security and makes book issuing and returning easier by automatically identifying users. It also helps maintain proper records of library transactions and provides a convenient and efficient authentication method.

C. R307 FINGERPRINT MODULE

The RC522 RFID reader is used for student identification in the Smart Library Management System. It works based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology, which allows contactless communication between the reader and RFID cards or tags. When a student places the RFID card near the reader, it reads the unique identification number stored inside the card and sends the data to the ESP-32 controller for verification. This process is fast, accurate, and reduces manual entry errors. The RFID system improves security and makes book issuing and returning easier by automatically identifying users. It also helps maintain proper records of library transactions and provides a convenient and efficient authentication method.

D. ESP-32 CAM

The ESP32-CAM is a low-cost microcontroller with built-in Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and a camera. It is used to capture images of book QR codes during issue and return processes. The module can take photos, support video streaming, and store data using a microSD card. It helps automate book identification and improves system efficiency.

E. 16X2 I2C LCD DISPLAY

The 16×2 I2C LCD display shows transaction details like student ID, book ID, and system status. It uses I2C communication to reduce wiring and save ESP32 input/output pins. It is easy to program and helps display information clearly to users.

F. PUSH BUTTON

Push buttons are used to control book transactions in the Smart Library Management System. Two buttons are provided: Take for issuing a book and Return for returning a book. When pressed, they send signals to the ESP-32 to perform the required action, making the system simple and easy to use.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The Smart Library Management System operates by integrating several hardware modules controlled by the ESP-32 microcontroller. When a student wants to issue or return a book, the RFID reader scans the student's RFID card and identifies the user using a unique ID stored in the system database. After student identification, the fingerprint sensor authenticates the librarian to ensure that only authorized personnel can approve the transaction. Once verification is completed, the ESP32-CAM scans or captures the QR code of the book, allowing accurate tracking of book details such as book ID and availability status. The ESP-32 acts as the central controller, coordinating communication between all devices and processing the transaction in real time.

After successful processing, the system automatically updates student details, book records, and transaction history in Google Sheets through internet connectivity, enabling real-time data storage and easy monitoring. LEDs and a buzzer provide instant visual and audio feedback to indicate whether the operation is successful or if any error occurs. The LCD display shows important information such as student ID, book ID, and transaction status for user confirmation. The system can also send notifications or reminders about due dates and overdue books, helping students return books on time. Continuous monitoring through the ESP32-CAM improves security inside the library. Overall, the automated workflow reduces manual effort, prevents record loss, increases transaction speed, and ensures a secure, accurate, and efficient library management process.

VI. BLOCK DIAGRAM

VII. CONCLUSION

The Smart Library Management System provides a reliable, efficient, and secure solution for modern library operations. By integrating advanced technologies such as RFID for user identification, QR code scanning for book tracking, fingerprint authentication for secure access, and ESP32-CAM with ESP-32 for IoT-based automation, the system significantly reduces manual work and minimizes human errors. It automates important processes such as book issuing, returning, attendance tracking, and record maintenance, making library management faster and more accurate. The use of biometric authentication ensures that only authorized persons can access and manage transactions, thereby improving system security and accountability.

In addition, real-time data storage using online platforms allows easy monitoring and maintenance of library records without paperwork. The system sends timely notifications and reminders to students about due dates, helping to avoid delays and penalties. It also improves the overall user experience by providing quick responses and clear transaction updates through the LCD display and alert indicators. Furthermore, the system is flexible and scalable, meaning it can be expanded in the future by adding features such as mobile applications, cloud databases, or AI-based book recommendation systems. Overall, this project modernizes traditional libraries by making them smarter, more organized, time-saving, and user-friendly while supporting the digital transformation of educational institutions.

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REFERENCE

- I. Mrs. Bhargavi Ananth; Adithya D; Pavan Gowda HP; Apoorva B; Hema K Smart Library System: LED-based book tracking & navigation using LED beacons and mobile app/Kiosks (2024).
- II. Pawan Bhati; Komal; Prince; Stuti Saxena, Modern Library Management System: A Web-Based Framework For Resource Automation and user oversight (2024).
- III. TS Apeksha, C G Khushi Prasad & TO Geethamani; Smart IoT Based Library Management: Automated library management by barcode and cloud technology (2024)
- IV. Jieyang Zhao, Jig Nang, Xiangzha Chen, Pengfi Ya; Smart Library System Design based on AI and IoT: Implemented AI and IoT methods for more efficiency (2024).
- V. Manish Kumar, Kershav Shishodiya, Yogendra Singh Rajwal, Seema Nayek; Smart Library Management System: Integrates RFID and web applications enabling accuracy and efficiency(2023)

AUTONOMOUS CUSTOMER-FOLLOWING SMART TROLLEY WITH PRICE LIMIT DETECTION

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Abstract—The Autonomous Customer-Following Smart Trolley with Price Limit Detection is designed to enhance the shopping experience by combining automation, real-time billing, and budget control in a single system. The trolley uses an ESP32 microcontroller integrated with Bluetooth, RFID technology, IR sensors, and an ultrasonic sensor to automatically follow the customer while avoiding obstacles. Products placed in the trolley are scanned using an RFID reader, and the total cost is calculated instantly and displayed on an LCD screen. A predefined price limit feature alerts the user through a buzzer when the total amount exceeds the set budget. This system reduces physical effort, eliminates long billing queues, and provides real-time expense monitoring. Overall, the proposed smart trolley offers a convenient, efficient, and user-friendly solution for modern retail environments and demonstrates the potential of embedded systems in automated shopping applications.

Index Terms— Smart Trolley, ESP32, RFID, Automated Billing, Auto-Follow System, Embedded System.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the retail industry has undergone significant transformation due to technological advancements and the increasing demand for convenient shopping experiences. Supermarkets and hypermarkets have expanded in size, offering a wide variety of products under one roof. While this provides customers with more choices, it also introduces challenges such as navigation difficulties, long billing queues, and the physical effort required to push heavy trolleys. Traditional shopping trolleys are purely mechanical devices that provide no intelligent assistance. Customers must manually push the trolley, keep track of their purchases, and wait in line for barcode scanning and billing. During peak hours, checkout counters become overcrowded, leading to frustration and time loss. Moreover, manual billing processes are prone to human error and inefficiency. Automation and embedded systems offer promising solutions to these problems. By integrating sensors, microcontrollers, wireless communication, and identification technologies, it is possible to develop smart shopping systems that enhance user convenience and operational efficiency. One

such solution is the Smart Trolley System, which transforms a conventional cart into an intelligent assistant capable of performing multiple automated tasks. The proposed Smart Trolley System uses an ESP32 microcontroller as the central processing unit. The ESP32 is chosen due to its powerful processing capabilities, low power consumption, and built-in wireless connectivity. The system incorporates an RFID reader to detect tagged products placed inside the trolley. Each product is equipped with an RFID tag containing unique identification data. When a product is added, the system reads the tag, retrieves product information, and updates the total bill automatically. An LCD display mounted on the trolley provides real-time feedback to the customer, showing item names, prices, and the cumulative cost of purchases. This transparency allows customers to monitor their spending continuously and avoid unexpected expenses at checkout. A buzzer may be used to provide audio alerts for events such as successful item detection or budget limit warnings. A key feature of the proposed system is the auto-follow mechanism. Using sensors and motor control, the trolley can detect the user's movement and follow them automatically. This reduces the physical effort required to push the cart, making shopping more comfortable, especially for elderly individuals and people with physical limitations. Another important feature is the price limiter, which allows users to set a maximum budget. When the total cost exceeds the predefined limit, the system alerts the user through visual or audio signals. This functionality helps customers manage their expenses effectively and promotes responsible spending. The Smart Trolley System not only benefits customers but also improves store operations. Automated item detection reduces the workload on billing staff and minimizes queue lengths. It also decreases the likelihood of billing errors and enhances inventory tracking. In the long term, such systems can contribute to fully automated retail environments where checkout processes are seamless and contactless. Furthermore, the project demonstrates the practical application of embedded systems, wireless communication, and sensor technology in real-world scenarios. It serves as an example of how engineering solutions can address everyday problems and improve quality of life. In conclusion, the Smart Trolley System represents a significant step toward modernizing retail shopping through automation and intelligent assistance. By combining RFID technology,

ESP32 microcontroller capabilities, sensor-based navigation, and user-friendly interfaces, the system aims to provide a faster, safer, and more convenient shopping experience.

II. RELATED WORKS

1. RFID-Based Smart Shopping Cart System

This paper proposes a smart shopping cart that uses RFID technology to automate product identification and billing. Each product in the supermarket is equipped with an RFID tag, and the cart contains an RFID reader that scans items when placed inside. The system updates the total bill in real time and displays it to the customer. This approach reduces billing time and eliminates long queues at checkout counters. However, the system does not include mobility assistance or auto-follow functionality.

2. IoT-Based Smart Trolley for Automated Billing

The authors present an Internet of Things (IoT) enabled shopping trolley that communicates with a central server using wireless connectivity. The system maintains a database of products and prices, allowing real-time billing and inventory tracking. Customers can monitor their purchases through a display or mobile application. Although the system improves efficiency, it relies heavily on network connectivity and lacks physical assistance features.

3. Automated Shopping Cart with Barcode and RFID Integration

This research combines barcode scanning and RFID technology to enhance billing accuracy. The cart scans products automatically and updates the total cost on an embedded display. The dual identification method reduces the chances of missing items during billing. However, manual pushing of the cart is still required, and no intelligent navigation features are provided.

4. Smart Cart Using Wireless Communication

In this work, the trolley communicates wirelessly with the store's billing system to transmit purchase data. This enables faster checkout and centralized monitoring of transactions. The system demonstrates improved efficiency in busy retail environments but does not address user convenience in terms of movement or budget control.

5. Microcontroller-Based Intelligent Shopping Cart

This paper describes a microcontroller-driven shopping cart that processes data from sensors and identification modules. The system provides real-time billing and alerts for item addition or removal. While effective in reducing manual billing effort, the design focuses primarily on cost calculation and lacks advanced features such as auto-follow or user interaction enhancements.

6. Smart Shopping System Using Embedded Technology

The authors propose an embedded system that integrates sensors, display units, and identification technology to create a smart retail solution. The system improves operational efficiency and reduces human intervention. However, it does not provide assistance for physically challenged users or automated cart movement.

7. Autonomous Shopping Cart Navigation System

This study explores the concept of self-moving shopping carts capable of navigating through a store using sensors. The

system reduces the need for manual pushing and enhances user comfort. Despite its innovative approach, the implementation complexity and cost are relatively high, limiting practical adoption.

8. Budget Monitoring Shopping Cart

This paper introduces a shopping cart that helps customers manage their spending by tracking the total cost of items. The system alerts users when their budget limit is exceeded. While useful for financial planning, it does not automate billing or cart movement.

9. Wireless Sensor-Based Retail Automation

The authors present a system that uses wireless sensors to monitor products and customer interactions. The technology supports inventory management and theft detection. However, it focuses more on store operations than on improving the customer's shopping experience.

10. Smart Cart with LCD Display Interface

This research highlights the use of an LCD interface to display product details and billing information directly on the cart. Real-time feedback improves transparency and user awareness. Nevertheless, the system lacks advanced features such as wireless communication or autonomous movement.

11. Embedded System for Retail Assistance

The proposed system uses embedded hardware to assist customers by providing product information and billing updates. It demonstrates the potential of embedded technology in retail applications but does not address mobility challenges.

12. RFID-Based Inventory and Billing System

This paper focuses on using RFID technology for both inventory management and automated billing. The system improves accuracy and reduces manual workload. However, it is primarily designed for backend operations rather than direct customer assistance.

13. Intelligent Cart with Obstacle Detection

The authors propose a smart cart equipped with sensors to detect obstacles and prevent collisions. This enhances safety in crowded environments. While beneficial, the system does not include automatic billing or budget management features.

14. Smart Retail System Using Wireless Modules

This study describes a retail automation system that uses wireless modules to connect carts with central servers. It enables real-time data exchange and improved store management. However, the design does not incorporate autonomous navigation.

15. Automated Billing System for Supermarkets

The paper presents a system that eliminates manual billing through automatic product detection and cost calculation. This significantly reduces checkout time. The system, however, does not address customer convenience during shopping.

16. IoT-Based Smart Shopping Assistant

This research introduces an IoT-enabled assistant that helps customers track purchases and receive product recommendations. While informative, it relies on mobile devices rather than integrated trolley hardware.

17. ESP32-Based Smart Trolley System

The final paper discusses a smart trolley built around the ESP32 microcontroller, integrating wireless connectivity, sensors, and automated billing. The system demonstrates

improved performance and scalability compared to earlier designs. However, further enhancements such as advanced navigation and user interaction can improve practicality.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

To overcome the limitations of traditional shopping methods, this project proposes a Smart Trolley System equipped with advanced technologies to automate and enhance the shopping process. The system integrates RFID technology, sensors, wireless communication, and motor control to create an intelligent trolley capable of assisting customers throughout their shopping journey. In the proposed system, each product in the store is equipped with an RFID tag containing unique identification data. The trolley is fitted with an RFID reader that detects items as soon as they are placed inside. The information from the tag is processed by the ESP32 micro-controller, which retrieves product details and updates the total cost automatically. This eliminates the need for manual barcode scanning at checkout counters. A liquid crystal display (LCD) mounted on the trolley provides real-time information to the user, including item names, prices, and the cumulative bill amount. This feature allows customers to monitor their spending continuously and make informed purchasing decisions. One of the key innovations of the proposed system is the auto-follow mechanism. Using sensors and motor drivers, the trolley can detect the position of the user and move accordingly. This reduces the physical effort required to push the trolley, making shopping more comfortable and accessible. The system also incorporates a price limiter feature. Customers can set a maximum budget before shopping, and the trolley

will alert them if the total cost exceeds this limit. Alerts may be provided through visual indicators on the display or audio signals using a buzzer. This functionality helps users control their expenses and avoid financial inconvenience. By automating item detection and cost calculation, the proposed system significantly reduces waiting time at billing counters. In advanced implementations, the final bill can be generated automatically and transmitted wirelessly to the store's billing system, enabling a fast and seamless checkout process. The Smart Trolley System improves customer convenience, enhances store efficiency, reduces human errors, and supports modern retail automation. It represents a practical step toward intelligent shopping environments and future smart stores.

Block Diagram

IV. WORKING

The proposed Autonomous Customer-Following Smart Trolley with Price Limit Detection operates using an ESP32 microcontroller as the central control unit, integrating Bluetooth, RFID, ultrasonic sensor, IR sensors, motor driver, DC motors, LCD display, and buzzer. When the system is powered on, the ESP32 initializes all connected modules and establishes a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) connection with the customer's smartphone. The trolley continuously monitors the RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) value to estimate the distance between the user and the trolley. Based on the signal strength, the trolley moves forward, stops, or maintains position to ensure a safe following distance. Obstacle detection is achieved using the ultrasonic and IR sensors, which immediately stop the trolley and activate a buzzer alert if any object is detected within a predefined range. For billing, each product is equipped with an RFID tag that is scanned using the RC522 RFID reader, and the corresponding price is added to the total amount. The updated bill and item details are displayed on the LCD in real time. Additionally, a predefined budget limit is programmed into the system, and when the total cost exceeds this limit, a warning message is displayed and the buzzer is activated to notify the user.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

The prototype was tested in an indoor environment to evaluate its performance in terms of following accuracy, obstacle detection, and billing efficiency. The Bluetooth-based following mechanism maintained an average distance of approximately 0.5 to 1 meter with stable connectivity and achieved around 90–95% tracking accuracy under normal signal conditions. The ultrasonic sensor successfully detected obstacles within a range of 2 cm to 200 cm, and the trolley stopped within approximately 0.5 seconds after detection, ensuring safe operation. The RFID reader accurately scanned tagged products within a 3–5 cm range, achieving nearly 100% correct tag identification during testing. The billing system updated the total cost on the LCD display with a delay of less than one second. The price limit detection feature was also validated by setting different budget thresholds, and the system successfully triggered both

V1.CONCLUSION

The Smart Trolley System using ESP32 presents an effective solution to the limitations of conventional shopping methods in modern retail environments. Traditional trolleys require manual effort, involve long billing queues, and provide no real-time information about purchases. The proposed system

addresses these issues by integrating embedded technology, RFID-based product identification, sensors, and automated control mechanisms into a single intelligent platform.

The developed system is capable of automatically detecting items placed inside the trolley, calculating the total cost in real time, and displaying the information to the user. This significantly reduces the need for manual barcode scanning at checkout counters and minimizes waiting time. The inclusion of an auto-follow mechanism further enhances convenience by eliminating the need to push the trolley manually, making shopping easier for elderly individuals and people with physical limitations.

The price limiter feature allows users to monitor their expenses and receive alerts when a predefined budget is exceeded, promoting better financial control during shopping. The use of the ESP32 microcontroller ensures efficient processing, low power consumption, and support for wireless communication, making the system suitable for real-world deployment.

Overall, the Smart Trolley System improves customer comfort, reduces human effort, enhances billing efficiency, and contributes to the development of automated retail environments. The project demonstrates the practical application of embedded systems and IoT technologies in solving everyday problems. With further improvements and large-scale implementation, such systems can play a significant role in transforming traditional supermarkets into smart stores of the future.

VII. REFERENCE

- [1] R. C. Luo and T. M. Chen, "Autonomous mobile robot for indoor security surveillance," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 1131–1137, Oct. 2002.]
- [2] S. Thrun, W. Burgard, and D. Fox, *Probabilistic Robotics*, MIT Press, 2005.
- [3] J. Borenstein, H. R. Everett, and L. Feng, *Where am I? Sensors and Methods for Mobile Robot Positioning*, University of Michigan, 1996.
- [4] M. A. Fischler and R. C. Bolles, "Random sample consensus: A paradigm for model fitting," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 381–395, 1981.
- [5] D. H. Ballard and C. M. Brown, *Computer Vision*, Prentice Hall, 1982.
- [6] *Arduino Official Documentation*. [Online]. Available:
- [7] K. Ambekar, V. Dhole, S. Sharma, and T. Wadekar, "Smart Shopping Trolley Using RFID," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET)*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 3755–3758, Oct. 2015.
- [8] Z. Ali and R. Sonkusare, "RFID Based Smart Shopping and Billing," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 4823–4826, Dec. 2013.
- [9] M. Kaur, M. Sandhu, N. Mohan, and P. S. Sandhu, "RFID Technology Principles, Advantages, Limitations & Its Applications," *International Journal of Computer and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 151–157, Feb. 2011.
- [10] P. Chandrasekar and T. Sangeetha, "Smart Shopping Cart with Automatic Central Billing System through RFID

and ZigBee," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf.*, 2014, pp. 1–4.

[11] R. Doshi, A. Sutar, S. Aher, and S. Dalvi, "RFID Based Smart Trolley for Automatic Billing System," *Global Journal of Advanced Engineering Technologies*, vol. 5, no. 4, 2016.

[12] S. T. Dive, D. Kaware, and A. Ghadge, "Smart Trolley with Smart Billing System Using Arduino and RFID," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, vol. 8, no. 5, 2019.

Sensor Based Railway Track Obstacle Detection And Platform Safety

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Abstract—Railway transportation is one of the most important modes of transportation used worldwide due to its efficiency, affordability, and reliability. However, railway accidents caused by obstacles on tracks, wildlife crossings, human error, and unsafe passenger behavior at platforms remain major safety concerns. Traditional railway safety systems rely heavily on manual monitoring and driver response, which may result in delayed reaction and accidents. This paper proposes a smart railway obstacle detection and automated braking system using ultrasonic sensors, Arduino Uno microcontroller, and motor driver IC. The ultrasonic sensor continuously monitors the railway track and detects obstacles using ultrasonic wave reflection. When an obstacle is detected within a critical distance, Arduino processes the signal and sends commands to the motor driver IC to stop the DC motor, simulating automatic braking. Additionally, a platform safety system using ultrasonic sensors prevents passengers from entering unsafe areas near the platform edge and reduces the risk of accidental falls. The proposed system improves railway safety, reduces human error, enhances response time, and provides a reliable and cost-effective safety solution suitable for real-world railway implementation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Railways play a crucial role in transportation infrastructure by providing safe and efficient travel for passengers and goods. However, railway accidents remain a serious issue worldwide. These accidents are often caused by obstacles such as animals, debris, vehicles, or humans present on railway tracks. Additionally, unsafe passenger behavior at platforms, such as standing near platform edges or attempting to cross tracks, increases accident risk.

Traditional railway systems rely on train drivers to visually detect obstacles and apply brakes manually. However, human reaction time may not always be sufficient to prevent accidents, especially at high speeds or in poor visibility conditions such as fog, rain, or darkness.

Recent advancements in embedded systems, sensors, and automation have enabled the development of smart safety systems. Technologies such as ultrasonic sensors, IoT, artificial intelligence, and computer vision are being used to improve railway safety.

The proposed system uses ultrasonic sensors for obstacle detection and automated braking using Arduino and motor driver IC. The platform safety system further enhances passenger protection.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several research works have been conducted to improve railway safety.

Rahman [1] proposed real-time obstacle detection using deep neural networks. This system provides accurate detection but requires expensive computational hardware.

Jain et al. [2] developed an IoT-based railway barrier system and collision avoidance mechanism. This system improves railway crossing safety but does not directly control train braking.

Ranjith and Vijayaragavan [3] proposed an IoT-based automated calamity avoidance system for railway sectors, focusing on monitoring environmental hazards.

Fraga-Lamas et al. [4] developed smart railway monitoring systems using sensors and communication technologies.

Srinatha et al. [5] proposed railway track fault detection and obstacle avoidance using IoT.

Kalaskar et al. [6] studied automated railway safety systems and accident prevention mechanisms.

Chethan et al. [7] proposed railway track crack and break detection systems.

Kalaivani and Hemalatha [8] developed wildlife collision prevention systems.

Chunyan Rong et al. [9] proposed railway creature detection systems.

Yash Verma et al. [10] developed accident prevention systems.

Balamurugan et al. [11] proposed PLC-based railway automation systems.

However, most existing systems focus on detection and alerting rather than automatic braking and platform safety integration.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system consists of multiple hardware and software components working together.

A. Hardware Components

Arduino Uno acts as the main controller. It processes sensor data and controls motor driver IC.

Ultrasonic sensors detect obstacles by transmitting ultrasonic waves and receiving reflected signals.

Motor driver IC controls DC motor and implements automated braking.

DC motor represents train movement in prototype.

Platform ultrasonic sensor monitors passenger movement near platform.

Buzzer and LED provide warning signals.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM EXPLANATION

The system consists of three major blocks:

Input block consists of ultrasonic sensors.

Control block consists of Arduino microcontroller.

Output block consists of motor driver IC, motor, buzzer, and LED.

The sensors detect obstacles and send signals to Arduino.

Arduino processes signals and controls motor driver IC.

V. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM EXPLANATION

Ultrasonic sensor has four pins: VCC, GND, Trigger, Echo.

Trigger pin sends ultrasonic signal.

Echo pin receives reflected signal.

Motor driver IC connects Arduino and motor.

Arduino sends control signals to motor driver IC.

Motor driver IC controls motor operation.

VI. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The working principle of the proposed railway track obstacle detection and automated braking system with platform safety mechanism is based on distance measurement using ultrasonic sensors and automatic control using a microcontroller. Ultrasonic sensors operate by emitting high-frequency sound waves and measuring the time taken for the reflected waves to return after hitting an obstacle. This time delay is used to calculate the distance between the sensor and the object. In this system, ultrasonic sensors are placed at the front of the train model and near the platform edge. When the train moves forward, the ultrasonic sensor continuously monitors the track for any obstacle. If an object such as a person, animal, or debris is detected within the predefined safety distance, the sensor sends a signal to the Arduino microcontroller. The microcontroller processes this input and immediately sends a command to the motor driver IC to stop the DC motor, which simulates the stopping of the train. This automatic braking mechanism helps prevent collisions and reduces accidents caused by delayed human reaction.

Similarly, the platform safety mechanism operates using another ultrasonic sensor placed near the platform edge. When the train approaches the station, the sensor detects the presence of the train and sends a signal to the microcontroller. The microcontroller then activates a motor mechanism that closes the safety grill, preventing passengers from moving too close to the track. Once the train has safely stopped and conditions are secure, the grill can be opened again. The entire system works in real time and continuously monitors both track and platform conditions. The integration of sensors, microcontroller, and motor driver ensures automatic detection, decision-making, and actuation without human intervention, thereby improving

railway safety, preventing accidents, and enhancing passenger protection.

VII. ALGORITHM

Step 1: Start system

Step 2: Read sensor data

Step 3: Calculate distance

Step 4: Check obstacle condition

Step 5: Stop motor if obstacle detected

Step 6: Activate warning

Step 7: Monitor platform safety

Step 8: Repeat continuously

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed railway track obstacle detection and automated braking system with platform safety mechanism was successfully implemented and tested, demonstrating reliable and accurate performance. The ultrasonic sensor effectively detected obstacles placed on the track within the predefined safety range and transmitted the information to the Arduino microcontroller. Upon detection, the microcontroller immediately sent a signal to the motor driver IC, which stopped the DC motor, simulating the automatic braking of the train. The response time of the system was fast, ensuring timely stopping and preventing potential collisions. Similarly, the platform safety system successfully detected the arrival of the train and activated the safety grill mechanism, preventing unsafe passenger movement near the track and reducing the risk of falling. The system operated consistently during multiple trials, showing stable coordination between sensing, processing, and actuation components. These results confirm that the proposed system improves railway safety by enabling automatic obstacle detection, quick braking response, and enhanced platform protection, thereby reducing dependence on manual monitoring and minimizing accident risks.

IX. ADVANTAGES

The proposed railway safety system provides significant improvements in railway accident prevention, passenger safety, and automation efficiency. One of the major advantages of this system is its ability to detect obstacles on railway tracks using ultrasonic sensors in real time. Ultrasonic sensors continuously monitor the track ahead and detect the presence of any object such as humans, animals, debris, or broken components. Once an obstacle is detected within the predefined safety distance, the system immediately sends a signal to the Arduino microcontroller, which activates the motor driver IC to stop the train motor automatically. This reduces dependence on human reaction time and minimizes the possibility of accidents caused by delayed manual braking. This automatic braking mechanism enhances safety, especially in poor visibility conditions such as fog, rain, nighttime, or curved tracks where drivers may not clearly see obstacles. Another important advantage is the platform safety mechanism integrated into the system. Many railway accidents occur due to passengers accidentally falling onto tracks or stepping too close to the edge when trains arrive.

The ultrasonic sensor placed at the platform continuously monitors the gap between the train and the platform. When a train approaches, the system activates a safety grill mechanism that prevents passengers from moving toward the track. This helps prevent accidental falls, overcrowding hazards, and unsafe movements. The system improves passenger discipline and provides an additional protective barrier without requiring manual supervision.

X. LIMITATIONS

Despite its advantages, the proposed system has certain limitations that need to be considered. One of the primary limitations is the limited range of ultrasonic sensors. Ultrasonic sensors typically have an effective detection range of approximately 2 cm to 400 cm. This range may not be sufficient for high-speed trains, which require obstacle detection at much longer distances to ensure safe braking. If an obstacle is detected too late, the train may not stop in time due to its momentum and braking distance requirements. Another limitation is the sensitivity of ultrasonic sensors to environmental conditions. Factors such as heavy rain, strong wind, extreme temperatures, and dust can affect the accuracy of ultrasonic sensor readings. Ultrasonic waves may scatter or weaken under such conditions, resulting in reduced detection performance. Additionally, soft materials or irregular-shaped objects may absorb ultrasonic waves, making detection less reliable in certain situations. The current system is designed as a prototype using a DC motor to simulate train movement. In real railway systems, trains are much heavier and operate at higher speeds, requiring more complex and powerful braking mechanisms. The motor driver IC used in the prototype may not directly control real train braking systems without additional interfacing with railway braking infrastructure such as pneumatic or electromagnetic braking systems.

XI. FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed system has significant future scope for improvement and real-world implementation. One major future enhancement is the integration of advanced sensors such as LiDAR, radar, and camera-based vision systems. These sensors provide longer detection ranges, higher accuracy, and better object classification capabilities. Combining ultrasonic sensors with LiDAR and computer vision can create a more reliable and intelligent obstacle detection system. Another important future improvement is integration with real railway braking systems. Instead of controlling a DC motor, the system can be connected to actual train braking systems such as pneumatic brakes, electromagnetic brakes, or regenerative braking systems. This would allow direct automatic braking of real trains in emergency situations. The system can also be enhanced by adding wireless communication technologies such as GSM, IoT, or RF modules. This would allow the system to send real-time alerts to train drivers, railway control centers, and monitoring stations. Centralized monitoring systems can improve overall railway management and emergency response.

XII. CONCLUSION

The proposed railway track obstacle detection and automated braking system with platform safety mechanism provides an effective and reliable solution to improve railway safety and passenger protection. By using ultrasonic sensors, the system continuously monitors the railway track and platform area to detect obstacles and approaching trains. The Arduino microcontroller processes the sensor data and automatically activates the motor driver IC to stop the DC motor, simulating the automatic braking action of a train. This reduces the risk of collisions caused by human error or delayed reaction. Additionally, the platform safety grill mechanism helps prevent passengers from accidentally falling onto the track or moving too close to the edge when a train is arriving. The system operates in real time and ensures quick response, accuracy, and efficiency. Overall, the proposed system enhances railway safety, reduces accidents, and demonstrates a low-cost, automated, and practical solution that can be further developed and implemented in real railway environments for improved transportation safety.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fahim Ur Rahman, Real-Time Obstacle Detection Over Railway Track using Deep Neural Networks
- [2] Jain et al., Automatic railway barrier system using IoT, 2017
- [3] Ranjith and Vijayaragavan, IoT based calamity avoidance system, 2020
- [4] Fraga-Lamas et al., Smart Railway Monitoring, Sensors Journal, 2017
- [5] Srinatha et al., Railway Track Fault Detection, IJARST, 2023
- [6] Kalaskar et al., Railway Safety System, 2020
- [7] Chethan et al., Railway Track Crack Detection System, 2019
- [8] Kalaivani and Hemalatha, Wildlife Collision Prevention System
- [9] Chunyan Rong et al., Railway Creature Detection System, 2021
- [10] Yash Verma et al., Accident Prevention System, 2022
- [11] Balamurugan et al., PLC Based Railway Automation System

SAFECRUISE

Automatic Vehicle Speed Control System for Safe Zones Using RF Communication

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Abstract—Road accidents caused by over-speeding in restricted areas such as school zones, hospital surroundings, and residential regions have become a serious safety concern. Drivers often fail to maintain proper speed limits due to negligence or lack of monitoring systems. This paper presents SAFECRUISE, an automatic vehicle speed control system designed to automatically reduce vehicle speed automatically in restricted zones using Radio Frequency (RF) communication technology. The system consists of a transmitter unit placed in safe zones and a receiver unit installed inside the vehicle. The transmitter continuously broadcasts predefined speed-limit signals, which are received and processed by an ESP32 microcontroller. Based on the received signal, the controller regulates vehicle speed through an L298N motor driver using Pulse Width Modulation (PWM). The proposed system operates in real time without driver intervention and does not require GPS or internet connectivity. Experimental results show reliable communication, fast response time, and efficient speed regulation, making the system suitable for intelligent transportation and road safety applications.

Index Terms—RF Communication, ESP32, Automatic Speed Control, Smart Transportation, Road Safety, PWM, Embedded Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Road safety has become a major concern in modern transportation systems due to the increasing number of vehicles and road accidents. One of the primary causes of accidents is over-speeding, especially in sensitive and restricted areas such as school zones, hospital surroundings, and residential regions. Maintaining controlled vehicle speed in these areas is essential to ensure pedestrian safety and reduce accident risks.

In many real-world situations, drivers fail to follow speed regulations because of negligence, lack of awareness, or absence of strict monitoring systems. To address this issue, SAFECRUISE is developed as an intelligent automatic vehicle speed control system. The system reduces vehicle speed automatically whenever the vehicle enters a restricted zone without requiring driver intervention.

The proposed system is based on RF communication technology, which provides a low-cost and efficient wireless communication method. The system consists of a transmitter unit placed in restricted zones and a receiver unit installed inside the vehicle. The transmitter continuously broadcasts speed-

limit information using RF signals. When the vehicle enters the RF coverage area, the receiver detects the signal and sends it to the ESP32 controller. The controller processes the information and controls the motor speed using PWM through an L298N motor driver.

One of the important advantages of the SAFECRUISE system is that it does not depend on GPS or internet connectivity, making it more reliable in areas with poor network availability. The system is easy to implement, cost-effective, and suitable for intelligent transportation and road safety applications.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several automatic vehicle speed control systems have been developed using wireless communication and embedded technologies.

Geo-fencing based vehicle speed control systems use GPS technology to track vehicle location and automatically reduce speed in restricted zones. Although these systems provide accurate location tracking, they depend heavily on internet connectivity and satellite availability.

RF-based speed control systems use wireless transmitters installed in restricted zones to transmit speed-limit information to approaching vehicles. These systems are cost-effective, easy to implement, and suitable for short-range communication applications.

RFID-based speed control systems use RFID tags and readers for zone identification and automatic speed regulation. These systems provide reliable communication but require RFID infrastructure installation in every restricted area.

IoT-based vehicle monitoring and control systems provide real-time monitoring through cloud platforms and internet connectivity. Although these systems offer advanced monitoring features, they increase system complexity and operational cost.

From the literature review, it is observed that RF communication based systems provide a simple, reliable, and low-cost solution for automatic vehicle speed regulation in restricted zones.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The SAFECRUISE system is designed to automatically regulate vehicle speed in restricted areas using RF communication technology. The system mainly consists of two sections:

- Transmitter Unit
- Receiver Unit

The transmitter unit is installed in restricted zones such as schools and hospitals. It continuously transmits predefined speed-limit information using a 433 MHz RF transmitter.

The receiver unit is installed inside the vehicle and consists of an RF receiver, ESP32 microcontroller, L298N motor driver, LCD display, buzzer, and DC motor. When the vehicle enters the RF coverage area, the RF receiver detects the transmitted signal and sends it to the ESP32 controller.

The ESP32 processes the received information and automatically reduces the motor speed using PWM control through the L298N motor driver. Simultaneously, the LCD displays warning messages and speed-limit information while the buzzer provides alert indications to the driver.

When the vehicle exits the restricted zone, the controller restores the motor speed to normal operation.

IV. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

A. *Arduino Nano*

The Arduino Nano is used in the transmitter section for controlling RF signal transmission. It is based on the ATmega328P microcontroller and provides compact size, low power consumption, and easy interfacing.

B. *RF Transmitter and Receiver*

The RF transmitter converts electrical signals into radio waves and broadcasts speed-limit information. The RF receiver captures these signals and transfers the received data to the ESP32 controller.

C. *ESP32 Microcontroller*

The ESP32 acts as the main processing unit of the receiver section. It processes RF signals, controls motor speed, updates the LCD display, and activates the buzzer.

D. *L298N Motor Driver*

The L298N motor driver controls the speed and direction of the DC motor using PWM signals generated by the ESP32.

E. *DC Motor*

The DC motor represents the vehicle motor in the prototype system and demonstrates automatic speed control operation.

F. *LCD Display*

The LCD display shows speed-limit information, warning messages, and system status in real time.

G. *Buzzer*

The buzzer provides audible alerts whenever the vehicle enters a restricted zone.

V. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The working principle of the SAFECRUISE system is based on wireless RF communication and embedded motor control.

- 1) The RF transmitter continuously broadcasts speed-limit signals within the restricted zone.
- 2) The RF receiver installed inside the vehicle detects the transmitted signal.
- 3) The received signal is processed by the ESP32 microcontroller.
- 4) The ESP32 compares the received speed information with predefined values.
- 5) The controller generates PWM signals to regulate motor speed through the L298N motor driver.
- 6) The LCD display shows the speed-limit information and the buzzer alerts the driver.
- 7) When the vehicle exits the RF coverage area, the motor speed is restored to normal.

VI. METHODOLOGY

The implementation of the SAFECRUISE system follows the following methodology:

A. *Zone Signal Transmission*

The transmitter section broadcasts predefined speed-limit information continuously using RF communication.

B. *Signal Reception*

The receiver section detects RF signals using a 433 MHz RF receiver module.

C. *Signal Processing*

The ESP32 microcontroller processes the received data and determines the appropriate speed limit.

D. *Motor Speed Regulation*

PWM signals generated by the ESP32 are applied to the L298N motor driver to regulate motor speed.

E. *Driver Alert System*

The LCD display and buzzer provide visual and audible indications whenever the vehicle enters a restricted zone.

VII. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram of the SAFECRUISE system consists of a transmitter section and a receiver section. The transmitter section includes an Arduino Nano and RF transmitter module. The receiver section includes an RF receiver, ESP32 controller, motor driver, DC motor, LCD display, buzzer, and power supply.

Fig. 1. Block Diagram of RF Based Automatic Vehicle Speed Control System (SAFECRUISE)

Fig. 1. SAFECRUISE Block Diagram

VIII. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The circuit diagram shows the interfacing connections between the ESP32, RF receiver, L298N motor driver, LCD display, buzzer, and DC motor.

The RF receiver DATA pin is connected to the ESP32 GPIO pin for receiving transmitted data. The motor driver control pins are connected to PWM-enabled GPIO pins for motor speed regulation.

The LCD display uses I2C communication through SDA and SCL pins, while the buzzer is connected to another GPIO pin for alert generation.

Fig. 2. SAFECRUISE Circuit Diagram

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SAFECRUISE system demonstrated reliable and efficient performance during testing. The RF communication between the transmitter and receiver operated successfully within the specified range without significant signal interruption.

The system responded quickly whenever the vehicle entered a restricted zone. The motor speed reduction was smooth and controlled without sudden braking effects.

The LCD display successfully showed warning messages and speed-limit information, while the buzzer provided immediate audio alerts. The system worked automatically without requiring manual driver intervention.

Experimental observations confirmed that the proposed system effectively improves road safety by reducing vehicle speed automatically in restricted zones.

Fig. 3. SAFECRUISE Prototype Model

X. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The SAFECRUISE system demonstrated stable RF communication and reliable speed regulation during testing. The response time between signal detection and motor speed adjustment was observed to be fast enough for real-time restricted-zone applications.

The PWM-based motor control mechanism provided smooth speed reduction without abrupt changes in motor operation. The ESP32 controller processed RF signals efficiently while maintaining stable system performance.

The proposed system achieved the following major performance characteristics:

- Reliable RF signal detection within the defined zone range
- Automatic speed regulation without driver intervention
- Stable PWM motor control operation
- Low system complexity and reduced implementation cost
- Fast response suitable for real-time applications

XI. APPLICATIONS

- School and college zones
- Hospital and silent zones
- Residential areas
- Industrial safety zones
- Smart transportation systems
- Intelligent traffic management applications

XII. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

Future improvements to the SAFECRUISE system may include integration with IoT platforms, GPS-based tracking, and cloud-based monitoring systems. Advanced communication technologies with longer operating range can also be implemented to improve system coverage.

Artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms may be incorporated in future designs for adaptive traffic control and intelligent vehicle management.

XIII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented SAFECRUISE, an automatic vehicle speed control system using RF communication technology for restricted zones. The system successfully reduces vehicle speed automatically whenever the vehicle enters predefined safe zones such as school and hospital areas.

The proposed system uses RF communication, ESP32 microcontroller, PWM motor control, LCD display, and buzzer alerts to provide reliable and real-time operation. Experimental results confirmed that the system improves road safety and reduces the risk of accidents caused by over-speeding.

The SAFECRUISE system provides a low-cost, efficient, and practical solution for intelligent transportation and smart road safety applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Rao, S. P. Pydee, S. K. Tripathi, and S. Halakundi, "Automobile Speed Control Using Geo-fencing," *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, Feb. 2019.
- [2] Z. N. Kamal, A. R. Ramul, A. F. Al-Baghdadi, and H. N. Jasim, "Automatic Control Speed of Vehicles Near Schools and Colleges," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 29, no. 3, Mar. 2023.
- [3] S. Jeeva Paulin, N. Patchi Raja, and R. Rajasree, "Automatic Vehicle Speed Control System in a School Zone," *Journal of Information and Computational Science*, vol. 12, no. 6, 2022.
- [4] A. Karthikeyan, G. Arshad Parvez, K. Kishore Kumar, M. Lavanya, and R. Mathuprakas, "RFID Based Automatic Vehicle Speed Control," *JETIR*, vol. 10, no. 1, Jan. 2023.
- [5] V. Bhagat, K. Chavhan, M. Wandafale, V. Gedam, S. Ghawade, and M. Hedau, "Automatic Vehicle Speed Control System Using RF Module and Arduino," *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, vol. 7, no. 4, Apr. 2025.
- [6] S. Guttaedar and H. Reddy, "Automatic Vehicle Speed Controller System for Accident Prevention," *IRJET*, vol. 6, no. 5, May 2019.
- [7] V. Kranthi Sai Reddy, V. Sai Jahnavi, and P. Sheela, "Intelligent Smart Zone Based Vehicle Speed Control System Using RF," *IJRECE*, vol. 6, no. 4, Dec. 2018.
- [8] A. Mishra, J. Solanki, H. Bakshi, P. Saxena, and P. Paranjpe, "Design of RF Based Speed Control System for Vehicle," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 8, Oct. 2012.
- [9] M. Krishnan, K. Neeraja, P. Pavithra, S. Dhanalakshmi, and M. Poon-gothai, "IoT Based Vehicle Speed Monitoring and Controlling System," *Grenze International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, Jan. 2024.
- [10] K. Govindaraju, S. Boopathi, F. Parvez Ahmed, S. Thulasi Ram, and M. Jagadeeshraja, "Embedded Based Vehicle Speed Control System Using Wireless Technology," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Electrical, Electronics, Instrumentation and Control Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 8, Aug. 2014.